

Deliverable 2.1: I-ENERGY Technology Requirements & User Stories

28th of February 2022

Lead: COMS

Version: 1.1

Classification: Public

I-ENERGY project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101016508

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from the European Union's Horizon 2020
Research and Innovation programme
under grant agreement No 101016508

I-ENERGY Project Profile

Grant Agreement No.:	101016508
Acronym:	I-ENERGY
Title:	Artificial Intelligence for Next Generation Energy
Type:	Innovation Action (IA)
URL:	https://i-nergy.eu/
Start Date:	01/01/2021
Duration:	36 months
Work Package:	WP2 – Requirements, Specifications, Synergies and Alignment with AI4EU
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Status:	Final
Date of Delivery:	1st version: 11th June 2021, 2nd Version: 28th of February 2022
Version:	1.1
Classification:	Public

Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks
0.1	23/04/2021	Andrej Čampa (COMS)	ToC
0.2	14/05/2021	Andrej Čampa, Denis Sodin (COMS)	Sections 1,2
0.3	02/06/2021	Andrej Čampa, Denis Sodin (COMS)	Sections 3, 4, Appendix
0.4	02/06/2021	Andrej Čampa, Denis Sodin (COMS)	Review, Appendix
1.0	11/06/2021	Andrej Čampa, Denis Sodin (COMS), Spiros Mouzakitis (ICCS)	Final version
1.1	15/02/2022	Andrej Čampa	Addressed review comments

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15	VEOLIA SERVICIOS LECAM SOCIEDAD ANONIMA UNIPERSONAL	VEOLIA	ES	
16	RIGA MUNICIPAL AGENCY "RIGA ENERGY AGENCY"	REA	LV	
17	FUNDACION ASTURIANA DE LA ENERGIA	FAEN	ES	

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the work done to define the Usage Scenarios and derive from them the initial list of services. The objective is to identify the user needs and requirements for the proposed technical infrastructure of the I-ENERGY project. The following deliverable is part of the WP2 task T2.1: *AI-on-demand Energy Services Specifications*. The result of the work is a collection of commonly agreed and methodologically aligned Usage Scenarios providing valuable inputs for continuation of the project work.

The I-ENERGY project aims at developing an open modular framework for supporting AI-on-demand in the energy sector by capitalising on state-of-the-art AI, IoT, semantics, federated learning and analytic tools. The Services and solutions will be tested and evaluated in nine pilots in Portugal, Spain, Italy, Greece, Croatia, Slovenia and Latvia, which span over the complete energy value chain. Collected and diverse Usage Scenarios of this deliverable present the initial work done in the project and bring starting ideas of the project closer to technical work packages. Furthermore, Usage Scenarios bridge the gap between initial ideas and process of shaping the solution, therefore facilitating the development of the solutions, which will be tested and evaluated in the I-ENERGY pilots.

Napaka! Vira sklicevanja ni bilo mogoče najti. shows relations of task T2.1 to other tasks in WP2 that are closely related, namely:

- T2.2 *AI HLEG/AI4EU Ethics Guidelines Compliance Assurance, Data protection and IPR*
- T2.3 *AI Conceptual Architecture build on Existing Resources of the AI4EU Platform*
- T2.4 *Specification of I-ENERGY – AI4EU Cross-Fertilisation, Synergies & Alignment*

Figure 1. Main interactions of T2.1 and WP2 with other tasks and work packages.

Apart from WP2, the efforts of T2.1 are also closely related to task T5.1 *Pilot Planning, Requirements, KPIs and Preparation* and WP6 *I-ENERGY Open Call Management and Ecosystem building*. By identifying preconditions, requirements and a list of services, the work of T2.1 is a prerequisite for later

stages of the project and activities related to implementation (WP3, WP4). Furthermore, it also shapes the goals and metrics necessary for the I-ENERGY pilot's evaluation and demonstration (WP5).

The first two steps of the methodology (as described in Section 2) helped to identify 93 Usage Scenarios, resulting from project pilots' objectives and interactive workshops. A final list of Usage Scenarios is distributed across three different domains:

- AI for energy networks (I-NET)
- AI for renewable energy sources (I-DER)
- AI for enabling synergies/implications on other energy and non-energy domains (I-ENEF)

A full description of Usage scenarios is presented in Appendix 5.5.

The third step of the methodology, related to defining the I-ENERGY Use Cases, is part of future work and will be presented in more detail in D2.5. Nevertheless, a preview of the Use Cases being linked to I-ENERGY domains is illustrated in Figure 2. The table on the left-hand side of the figure presents which I-ENERGY domains and perspectives each pilot will cover. Use Cases related to pilots are shown on the right-hand-side of the figure and are marked with the same colour as corresponding pilot.

Figure 2. I-ENERGY Pilot / Use case classification according to identified I-ENERGY domains.

The results of the used methodology are Test cards, User Stories, Services, Data description and Usage Scenarios. All the filled templates are available in Appendix I to V. With the help of Usage Scenarios and supplied Data templates, the first list of Services was built.

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Glossary

Term	Definition	Term	Definition	Term	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface	EPES	Electric Power & Energy Systems	P2P	Peer-to-peer
AI	Artificial Intelligence	ESCO	Energy Service Companies	P	Pilot
AlaaS	AI-as-a-Service	EU	European Union	PaaS	Platform as a Service
DER	Distributed Energy Resource	EV	Electric Vehicle	PMUs	Phasor Measurement Units
DL	Deep Learning	FSTP	Financial Support to Third Parties	PV	Photovoltaic
DLT	Distributed ledger technology	IA	Innovation Action	RES	Renewable Energy Sources
DoW	Description of Work	IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service	SCADA	Supervisory/Control/Data Acquisit
DSM	Digital Surface Model	ICT	Information and Control Tech	SME	Small to Medium Enterprise
DSO	Distribution Service Operator	IoT	Internet of Things	TB	Testbed
DT	Digital Twin	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights	TRL	Technology Readiness Level
EC	European Commission	KPI	Key Performance Indicator	TSO	Transmission system operator
ENEF	Energy Efficiency	ML	Machine Learning	UC	Use Case
				WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The I-ENERGY project aims at developing an open modular framework for supporting AI-on demand in the energy sector by capitalising on state-of-the-art AI [1], IoT [2], semantics, federated learning and analytics tools. One of the main challenges today is how to fully exploit the AI over the full energy value chain, considering energy and non-energy services along with non-technical or low-technical end users.

1.1 Scope of the document

The following deliverable serves as a presentation of methodology and work done on Usage Scenarios, covering all aspects of the I-ENERGY project. Using the proposed method, we have systematically described a specific system's requirements from a Persona point of view for identifying the wide scope of Usage Scenarios. Simultaneous analysis of the requirements from both technical and socio-economic perspectives resulted in a comprehensive description, which will also be the basis for defining I-ENERGY Use Cases later in D2.5. We have identified different Personas and their position on the market in the energy value chain and aligned Usage Scenarios with the project's main goals.

The Usage Scenarios were the starting point for determining the pilot's required Services, which resulted in the initial list of required Services that will be developed in WP3 and WP4 by technical partners. The Usage Scenarios and Test cards are an important prerequisite for creating validation and assessment plan in WP5.

In parallel, the data availability template is the first step in identifying what is available and how the data is accessible. The identified historical and live data will be used as a starting point for creating the data models that will be later used to train and create the I-ENERGY AI models (WP3).

1.2 Structure of the document

The remainder of this deliverable has the following structure:

- **Section 1** continues with the I-ENERGY project vision and objectives and introduces different groups of energy services. It also describes geographical and domain span of the pilot.
- **Section 2** covers the methodology for Usage Scenario creation and guidelines for writing Usage Scenario by providing examples of *Test Card*, *Persona* and *User Story*. Furthermore, it covers the Service and Data template used in the process of identifying the Services. A complete list of Test Cards can be found in Appendix 5.1, User Stories in Appendix 5.2, Services in Appendix 5.3, Data description in Appendix 0 and Usage Scenarios in Appendix 5.5.
- **Section 3** provides a mapping of Usage Scenarios to concrete work packages and correlated tasks within them.

The document is concluded with conclusions, references and Appendix.

1.3 Project vision and objectives

The overall vision and main objective of I-ENERGY is to deliver an energy-specific open modular framework for supporting AI-on-Demand in the energy sector (AI4 Energy), by capitalising on state-of-the-art AI, as well as IoT, semantics and data analytics technologies. I-ENERGY will enable AI-based cross-sector multistakeholder analytical tools for integrated and optimised smart energy management, based on seamless data-information-knowledge exchange under respective sovereignty and regulatory principles. I-ENERGY aims at evolving, scaling up and demonstrating innovative AI-as-a-Service (AlaaS) Energy Analytics Applications, which will significantly contribute to achieve a techno-economic optimal management of the EPES value chain, especially for SMEs and non-tech industries, while leveraging on and complementing the AI resources and tools made available by the AI4EU platform. The technical solution follows the I-ENERGY Conceptual Architecture and it consists of four main pillars:

- 'I-ENERGY Data Services', encompassing modules related to interoperable data collection;
- 'I-ENERGY AI Trained Models', including federated privacy preserving machine learning, cross-stakeholder transfer learning and adaptive self-learning;
- 'I-ENERGY Application Layer', providing a set of AI-powered analytics tools as a service [AlaaS / PaaS (Platform as a Service) / IaaS (Infrastructure as a Service) models];
- 'I-ENERGY - AI4EU Interconnection Layer', including open APIs for making available I-ENERGY technology enablers to the AI4EU community.

On top of the I-ENERGY framework, the project defines AI energy analytics services and Digital Twins (grouped under the 'Energy Commodities Networks', 'Distributed Energy Resources' and 'Energy Efficiency and Non-energy related Services' categories) that will be developed and tested in the context of 9 pilot hubs (consisting of 15 Use Cases).

The pilot hubs and the technology transfer projects will range from optimal risk assessment for energy efficiency investments planning, to optimised management of grid and non-grid owned assets, improved efficiency and reliability of electricity networks operation, as well as new socially and environmentally sustainable business models. I-ENERGY will adapt, upscale and deploy a novel holistic framework that enables the EPES community to utilise a variety of data sources from the grid / building operations and assets that underpin AI and ML algorithms, in order to optimise grid asset management and forecasting systems, enhance the energy efficiency and other energy and non-energy domains (i.e. heat, transport, water, personal safety, AAL, finance), and optimise customer engagement in demand response local marketplaces with real-time predictive insights.

The addressed project visions are divided into the following objectives:

1. Strengthening European-wide Research and Innovation on AI through synchronising, liaising, contributing and extending the AI4EU Platform service and research across a variety of cross-fertilisation activities, which bring AI4 Energy vertical center stage [WPs 2-7];
2. Delivering a TRL 7 DLT/blockchain/smart contract-based implementation of an energy data decentralised governance technological enabler [WP3]
3. Adapting, evolving, upscaling and deploying a TRL 7 technology enabler for advanced AI-based data management, learning and analytics, and deploying the I-ENERGY Energy Analytics Applications along different deployment modes, ranging from experimental on-premise sandboxes to AI-as-a-Service (AlaaS) Energy Analytics operation [WP4];

4. Validating the I-ENERGY analytics by developing a variety of near real time edge-level AI-based descriptive, predictive and prescriptive analytics, along a number of cross-function, cross-stakeholders, cross-domain piloted applications [WP5];
5. Laying the foundation for pan European AI for energy ecosystem, boosting EU-scale data economy and use-cases experiments by leveraging on systematic community-building and financing support to innovative technology/solution provider from EPES community [WPs 2, 6, 7]

1.4 Relations to I-ENERGY environment

The I-ENERGY project proposal relates to the topic ICT-49-2020 'Artificial Intelligence on demand platform'. The following topics will be addressed:

- 1 Consolidating the AI-on-demand eco-system by bringing in a larger user community, especially from the non-tech sector;
- 2 Reinforcing the service layer of the AI-on-demand-platform funded in ICT-26;
- 3 Reaching out to new user domains and boosting the use of the platform through Use Cases and small-scale experiments;
- 4 Ensuring continuity with AI4EU - the project selected under ICT26.

1.5 Geographical and domain span of the project

The overall I-ENERGY service analytics framework will be applied, implemented, demonstrated and validated in real life. I-ENERGY consists of 9 pilot (P) hubs (15 Use Cases, UC), 2 test-bed (TB) facilities and Digital Twins (DT) across 8 countries as shown in Figure 3. The large geographical coverage of the demo sites aims to support the EU-wide replicability and market take-up of AI-driven solutions in different socio-economical contexts to maximise the impact of I-ENERGY services across Europe. I-ENERGY pilot's approach will comprehensively test the analytics devised to cover the initially detected interests of relevant EPES stakeholders within the energy value chain, covering their whole energy market: from the operation and maintenance to the society, as well as cross-cutting interests, such as policy making and research. The energy sector will be considered from different perspectives: buildings as individual elements (building level) to their aggregation at varied scales (districts / communities) and territories. This holistic approach will enable to test the non-exhaustive set of I-ENERGY open services which could be expanded by third parties through the Open Calls.

Figure 3. Geographic span of I-ENERGY's pilot cases.

In each of the 9 pilots' specific application and testing of the AI analytics devised in I-ENERGY (representing different business models or situations among EPES stakeholders under 15 Use Cases) will be performed. Rationale of pilot applications is to address in a combined way two of the major challenges actually hindering AI analytics value capturing in the energy sector, i.e.:

- nurturing the shifting towards Predictive/prescriptive analytics.
- enabling multiple data source (cross-functional and/or cross-contexts and/or cross-domain) analytics for multiple applications.

In each of the pilots, the interests of different EPES stakeholders will be pictured and the perspective to the energy challenge at hand in each of them. Each one is led by the most representative EPES actor, bridging the real problems encountered by these stakeholders in their everyday undertaking to I-ENERGY solutions. In total, three groups of holistic energy services will be developed, as explained below:

- I-NET (UC1, UC2, UC3 and UC6): AI for energy networks (electricity network / district heating network) optimised operation. The applications will focus on asset management and predictive maintenance, network loads and demand forecasting, as well as smart grid enhanced reliability.
- I-DER (UC4, UC7, UC9, UC10 and UC11): AI for Renewable Energy Sources (RES) generation, buildings, districts, communities. The applications will focus on DER-level energy management, flexibility providers matching with the marketplace for virtual power plant, consumers matchmaking for green energy marketplaces.
- I-ENEF (UC5, UC8, UC12, UC13, UC14 and UC15): AI for enabling synergies/implications on other energy and non-energy domains (i.e. heat, transport, water, personal safety, AAL, finance). The applications will focus on dynamic energy-efficient end-user comfort, building-scale management and renewable investments financial risk assessment management, cross-commodity (power vs heat) home/building optimal energy

management, cross-sector energy-driven services, including personal safety/security and care management services for elderly people.

One of the added values of the I-ENERGY consortium is diverse pilots that also cover different regions with their market prices. The so-called price coupling of regions (PCR) is becoming increasingly important to achieve a harmonized European market. Three principles are important for PCR to increase liquidity, efficiency and social welfare [3]:

1. Common algorithm to calculate electricity prices across Europe, with welfare optimization functions for increased transparency.
2. Robust operation with decentralized data sharing.
3. Individual accountability through the PCR Matcher and Broker service.

This is the basis for I-ENERGY's activities, which is followed by all pilots and use cases, none of which violate these three principles. Moreover, the solutions developed by the I-ENERGY consortium are not limited to a specific market or region. The AI-based solutions can be extended to other markets outside the energy sector or applied to a broader region. With the UCs (UC1, UC3, UC4, UC6, UC7, UC9, and UC10), we address the rapid digitization of the energy market on the one hand, and on the other hand, we try to identify the long-term changes that will affect the energy market (UC2, UC5, UC8, UC11, UC12, UC13, UC14, and UC15). Consumers or citizens are becoming more and more involved in the energy market. Their role is expanding and their view and indirect influence on energy and non-energy services is becoming more important[4], they are becoming active players (UC11, UC12). They are also transforming the traditional market into a consumer-oriented market [5]. The so-called local energy market is based on community (UC7 local community, UC10 EV-based community, and UC11 virtual community). The non-energy services (UC4, UC8, UC12, UC13, and UC14) complement the services offered by the traditional energy market and can use the existing infrastructure.

1.6 Use cases mapping to services and pilots

In the previous section, we analysed the use cases from the stakeholder perspective and their value to the market. However, to strengthen the use cases also in terms of services, we need to carefully analyse the use cases and group them according to some common functionalities. This first attempt to define the services is presented in Section 3.1. Since this deliverable is only a starting point, the services may change during the execution of the project depending on the needs of the pilots and the availability of resources on the AI4EU platform (T2.4). In this way, we ensure that we focus only on a) things that have not yet been developed, 2) state-of-the-art solutions, and 3) integrating envisaged services of I-ENERGY into the AI4EU platform. In order to be able to integrate existing components and focus only on the developing and integrating of state-of-the-art solutions, I-ENERGY will use the AI-as-a-Service approach based on the modular approach of AI microservices (Task 2.3).

The UCs can be categorized into three types of AI services:

- 1 Data analysis of patterns and forecasting (UC1, UC6, UC7, UC9, UC11, UC12, UC13, UC14, and UC15).
- 2 Optimization-related services to improve user experience (UC3, UC4, and UC5):
- 3 Distribution network optimization (UC2 and UC10).

These services will be developed under different tasks of WP3 and WP4. Here we summarize the pilots in terms of the AI-based categorization and use cases mentioned above. A more detailed description of the UCs can be found in Appendix 5.5.

Pilot 1 covers two use cases: UC1 and UC2. The main objective is to use the existing data to analyse asset patterns and create predictive maintenance of assets (UC1). In addition, UC2 deals with load forecasting. All of this aims to optimize operational planning.

Pilot 2 covers three use cases: UC3, UC4, and UC5. In Pilot 2, AI analytics is going to be applied at the district level. The main objective is to optimize the district heating network (UC3) to achieve economic benefits and energy savings (UC5). In addition, the business model will be developed to achieve an appropriate balance between investments and energy savings achieved (UC4).

Pilot 3 covers three use cases: UC6, UC7 and UC8. The main objective of the pilot is to address the grid stability problems caused by the increasing share of renewable energy sources and new assets. The main activities are related to predictive asset analysis (UC6), prediction of consumption and flexibility (UC7), and demonstration of novel AI-based non-energy services (UC8)

Pilot 4 covers UC9. The main objective of the pilot is to enable AI-based predictive maintenance of PV power plants to improve operational efficiency through optimized maintenance and to increase self-consumption.

Pilot 5 covers UC10. The main objective of the pilot is to predict the load profile of charging stations to better utilize EV charging stations and distribute the load evenly among stations.

Pilot 6 covers UC11. The main objective of the pilot is to forecast loads and renewable energy sources to leverage peer-to-peer trading within the virtual community.

Pilot 7 covers UC12. The main objective of the pilot is to improve non-energy services by modelling devices and citizen behaviour and better matching local production and self-consumption.

Pilot 8 consists of a use case UC13. The main objective of the pilot is to improve energy performance contracting and make it more reliable by using AI to better predict energy consumption.

Pilot 9 covers two use cases: UC14 and UC15. The main objective of the pilot is to use AI to better predict long-term climate change in RES and in energy demand (UC15), as well as the impact on the reliability of energy performance certificates (UC14).

2 Methodology

This chapter describes the methodology used by I-ENERGY partners to fulfil the requirements defined in the task T2.1 *User Stories and AI Energy Services specification*. According to the Grant Agreement, the content covers the main parts: Activities related to the main user requirements generation process, high-level Usage Scenario creation, identification of the Services and finally results. The Use Case generation process was divided into three steps, as it will be further explained in Section 2.1. This document focuses only on the first two steps, whereas the third step will be developed and described in D2.5. The outcome of the methodology are requirements, goals, metrics, collection of available data and an initial list of services to be developed (D2.1). In this context, this deliverable aims to identify initial requirements and prerequisites, therefore contributing to an efficient start of other tasks and preparing the ground for a complete and more detailed version of Use Cases (D2.5). Results and final Usage Scenarios are described in detail in Appendix 5.5. In addition, Appendices from 5.1 to 0 are provided, where Test Cards, User Stories, Services and Data of partners are presented, respectively.

2.1 Definitions

The process of defining user requirements was designed in detail by CARTIF and enhanced by COMS. The user requirements were derived from pilot partners using a set of Test Cards and Personas templates. With the help of templates, the pilots derived simple user (Persona) scenarios, which resulted in development of typical User Stories, describing the typical user needs and operations. The complex array of input data was reviewed and Usage Scenarios were generated from User Stories. Usage Scenarios consist of very detailed User Stories and matrices of specific information and concerned services' needs. The main advantage of this process is that it gives a better overview of requirements and needs compared to standard UC methodology according to IEC 62559-2 [6]. Personas introduced in this process might be third party Personas not directly involved in the process. For instance, they can present the end-user, with its unique view of the process, resulting in identifying otherwise unseen requirements. This multi-perspective approach gives a better overview of the process and the possibility to find a better way of creating more complete Use Cases.

The process continued in finding similar or same patterns in defined Usage Scenarios that common project's services could deploy. The user requirements resulted from defined common Usage Scenarios.

The search and generation process of user requirements consists of three steps described below:

- Step 1: Generation of Test Cards (specification of hypothesis) and Personas (behavioural archetype) + User Stories (what the user wants to be able to do);
- Step 2: Creation of Usage Scenarios (motivation for service instantiation and exemplification of the user interaction), creating the initial list of Services that need to be developed;
- Step 3: The final Use Cases creation and matching with requirements specification (part of D2.5).

An overview of the methodology used in the I-ENERGY project and relations to other project tasks are presented in Figure 4. In addition, detailed steps taken by the used methodology are presented in more detail with a flowchart of the methodology, Figure 5. The scope of D2.1 covers the first two

steps that are important for defining the initial I-ENERGY architecture (T2.3) and later the full architecture.

Figure 4. Methodology overview and main interactions with other I-ENERGY tasks.

Figure 5. I-ENERGY methodology flowchart.

2.1.1 Step 1

The first step of the methodology, Figure 5, is done by the pilot owners and starts with the simple identification of pilot overarching goals measures and target groups. This step's goal is to identify all actors and to draft main user types, characters or roles, called *Personas*, and their typical needs or operations, called *User Stories*.

Test Cards

The first step was based on so-called Test Cards template. A Test Card helps to create a high-level description of the Pilots Use Case by answering four simple questions. The purpose of the test card is to structure the experiments (service hypothesis) envisioned to be tested in a given pilot and by considered stakeholder. It served as the first part in concluding steps of the methodology by defining the basic and only high-level characteristics of the pilot and its objectives by filling the four simple sections in the card:

- **Name** of the pilot, as defined in DoW.
- **Goals** of the pilot that will allow the potential users to achieve their goals; Bulleted list with short goals in bold and additional brief description of the goal.
- **Metrics** used to determine if the pilot achieves the goals; From these metrics, KPIs will be later derived that will serve as the basis for all the following steps.
- **Target group** - these are the potential users (beneficiaries) of the pilot service(s). It can be expanded by expressing the traits, intentions and needs of the users through the development of *Personas* (characters).

Test card presents the first hypothesis towards a detailed definition of the use cases. Therefore, the metrics are only a descriptive representation; a basis from which the KPIs will be derived and quantified as a part of Task 5.1. The purpose of the metrics and goals presented here is to analyse them from the various perspectives of other stakeholders/personas who may not even be directly involved in the final use case. This holistic approach of screening requirements and effectively capturing all possible goals and metrics is the prerequisite for the final definitions in T5.1.

The Target Group is the group of stakeholders or another kind of users/beneficiaries from the service. The target groups are not necessarily technical groups, but their idea is to also cover a non-technical aspect. The most common target groups were prepared in advance and categorized to have a common classification and naming:

- DERs Operators
- Energy suppliers
- Researchers (research organizations and universities)
- Facility Managers
- ESCOs (energy services companies)
- Real estate developers
- Utilities (public and private utilities and aggregators)
- Institutions (relevant national and European institutions or departments)
- Investors (industry and investors related to the real estate management and development)
- Policy makers (policy authorities and policy makers (local to European level), e.g., urban planning department)
- Designers

- Constructors (construction companies and consulting firms)
- Citizens and Owners (building operators)
- Third parties

An example of a test card is shown below.

Test card – EXAMPLE

Name (Pilot name)	
Pilot 7. [SONCE - Slovenia]	
Goal (Overarching pilot goals)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancement of demand-side management: Expose potentials for flexibility 	
Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved operation and maintenance of the pilot buildings • New potentials for energy efficiency and flexibility are discovered, evaluated and exposed to energy service providers • Higher customer trust 	
Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)	
Target group	Personas
Facility manager	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed facility manager • Sustainability supporting facility managers • Cost-conscious facility manager
Citizen	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitive owner • Informed owner

Figure 6. Example of Test Card.

Personas

Personas were extracted from Test Cards and furtherly evolved with Persona template. Personas are fictional characters created with the aim to highlight the needs, preferences and behaviors of the target groups and to ensure that we are thinking from their perspective. Each Persona represents a different point of view of each target group, all together forming a holistic approach of looking at the same goal from different aspects and more easily defining technical and non-

technical requirements. Thus, for each target group, several Personas or characters can exist simultaneously. The step of describing the target group is very important since different Personas might have a completely different view on the same problem and their goals might be different, even though they are members of the same target group. Therefore, each Persona opens a new and unique perspective on the same overarching pilot goal.

For instance, for the target group “Citizens and Owners”, there can be different Personas/characters: the careless owner (who doesn't care about energy consumption and doesn't pay attention to their bills), the technology-aware owner (who is fully aware of what technology can offer in terms of comfort in their homes and has the latest gadgets installed), the technology-hating owner (who, in contrast to technology-aware inhabitant, isn't prone to using technology), the bill-aware owner (who is mostly worried about the economic aspects of their energy consumption), etc. The pilots provided the Personas characters as the next step after Test Cards. The personas were elaborated through person card examining details of the role, such as:

- **Persona** name and appropriate **target group**, both extracted from Test card.
- **User context** – description of the Persona, for example work he/she does, their main tasks and their possible involvement in reaching the overarching goals.
- **Pain points** – the main pain points the Persona has to overcome to reach the goal. The Persona expect that these pain points will be solved by I-ENERGY services.
- **Goals** – how the Pilot services help this Persona to achieve the goals (solving his/her pain points).
- **Usefulness of the service** – how the Pilot services are incorporated into his/her work or life.
- **Attitudes and sentiments** – emotions that the Pilot services will create, for example calmness and security because of solving the pain.

The Personas were defined within each UC. An example of the Personas card is below.

Persona – EXAMPLE

User	Persona
Facility Managers	Informed facility manager
User Context	Informed facility manager works at the large shopping, entertainment, business, commercial and logistics centre. He is responsible for closing the gap between theory and practice and providing the necessary background and help for decision-makers when dealing with the facility and energy-related issues.
Pain points	The Informed facility manager does not know which facility management or energy efficiency measure should be implemented first. He is not sure which are the best solutions to propose to be implemented in each building.
Goals	Pilot services can help them: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to create reliable implementation action plans • to do preventive maintenance of the most critical systems • to expose selected energy efficiency and flexibility projects to the potential investors • to validate achieved energy and cost savings
The usefulness of the service	The Pilot service will help Informed facility manager by providing the needed information to establish their cost-assessment and a reliable evaluation of the available energy and maintenance improvement opportunities for the context of each building
Attitudes & Sentiments	Calm and secure because he will have reliable and transparent support for his activities.

Figure 7. Example of Persona.

User Stories

The expansion of Persona leads to User Stories as the last part of the Step 1. The User Story is a method used to capture a description of a service feature from the user's perspective (in contrast to the product-based requirement documents). User Stories are written in a natural language and are placed at the center of the user experience. They should provide means to structure ideas and identify features for the implementation by answering:

- **Who** is it for?
- **What** does it expect from the system?
- **Why** is it important?

There are usually several User Stories for each Persona. User Stories were prepared by pilot partners.

An example of User Stories for Persona “Informed Facility Manager” is as follows:

User story – EXAMPLE

Persona: Informed Facility Manager	
Story 1	As an Informed facility manager working for a large shopping centre, I want to create reliable implementation action plans for identified energy efficiency and facility management measures so that I can propose optimal solutions to implement in building and provide sound decision support for the management board.
Story 2	As an Informed facility manager working for a large shopping centre, I want to identify a proper list of energy efficiency and flexibility projects so that I can expose them to potential investors.

Figure 8. Example of User Story.

2.1.2 Step 2

Sessions with pilots

The second step started with a series of individual sessions with pilots. The main topics of discussion were:

- Review of Test Cards, Personas and User Stories, their presentation and clarification.
- Data availability and formats, data gathering process with the template, data examples.
- Presentation of Usage Scenario template and generation of Usage Scenarios.
- Presentation of Service template.
- Service identification by pilots’ owners through filling Usage Scenarios and prior identification of the Services according to tasks requirements by technical partners.
- Harmonizing, additionally creating or removing initially envisioned Services to match Usage Stories identified needs.

Usage Scenarios

A Usage Scenario is derived from User Stories and describes, in an exemplificatory and narrative manner, how the user is going to interact or is influenced by the identified service during a specific situation. These services are not harmonized at this point but just initially identified by pilot owners as possible services. Writing Usage Scenarios require to identify a specific context in which the action takes place, as well as characters and needs that defines the attitude of the Persona. The Usage Scenarios can be first written as stories, describing the experience step by step.

The information that Usage Scenario should provide is the following:

- **Usage Scenario ID** in form of X.Y, where X represents corresponding Use Case number and Y represents consequent User Story number.
- **Persona** that is involved in this scenario.

- **Related User Story**, which is copied from the User Story template.
- **Precondition**, which specifies environmental conditions/states and user motivations that need to be defined/fulfilled for successful execution of the activity (e.g. specific data is available, a specific process has finished, etc.).
- **Postcondition**, which specifies what should be the end goal of the activity (i.e., expected results at the end of the process, achieved outcomes of the Persona, etc.)
- **Step by step analysis**, is a detailed description of how the goal is achieved and which steps in the process are needed to achieve the goal, from the Persona point of view. Steps are sequentially marked and explained/described in more detail in the action column. The idea is that pilot owners try to identify all of the required services (main and auxiliary) to complete the step. Note, that not every step requires the service and that more steps can share the same service. Step by step analysis also provides the first attempt in identifying the needed services from the pilot and Persona point of view. The services can be linked to WP3 and WP4 related activities or just auxiliary services that need to be done to complete the scenario successfully. Pilot owners are able to identify AI-based and auxiliary services. In the end, the refinement was done to extract only the main and AI-based services.

An example of a completed Usage Scenario is presented in Figure 9.

Usage Scenario - EXAMPLE

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 12.1

Involved Persona

Informed Facility Manager

Related User story

As an Informed facility manager working for a retirement home, **I want to** lower the costs of living in the retirement home by participating in DR programs with non-energy services **so that** I can improve the well-being of the elderly by improving their daily/weekly schedules.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions

- Number of citizen involved is high enough
- Citizen consent
- Citizen are grouped according to their preferences
- SM are installed and available

Postcondition

Createion of optimized schedules for Elderly

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Informed Facility manager identifies the citizen that will participate in the program	
2	From the installed AMI the data is collected and dissagregation of loads is performed	Dissagregation service
3	Aggregation of results is performed according to informed facility manager clustering of citizens	Dissagregation service
4	For each type of citizen the new optimal schedule is identified.	EMS optimization service
5	Facility manager validates the results and if needed provides additional parameters	
6	Informed facility manager activates the new schedules	

Figure 9. Example of Usage Scenario.

In parallel to forming Usage Scenarios two processes took place. On the one hand, the collection of Services from technical partners (WP3/WP4 related tasks) was performed. The partners were asked to fill out the template, which is explained in more detail in

Figure 10. A full list of Services identified by partners is provided in Appendix 5.3. After the harmonization, the service list name is different and more complete to the services determined by the Usage scenario template.

I-ENERGY Service description

Name (Service name)	
Service Name [Partner developing]	
Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	Describe with one sentence what your service does.
Objective	Describe with one sentence what is the final benefit that can be achieved with service.
Related Usage Scenario	Specify to which usage scenario this service can be mapped
Pilot	Specify in which pilot this service will be implemented/validated.
Narrative of the service	
Provide a description of the service	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service input requirements, service operation, service output 	
Type of service - implementation specifics	
Online/offline	
Execution frequency	Options to select <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time • Periodically (specify frequency) • On-demand (specify trigger) •
Developing language	E.g. Python, C/C++, Matlab,...
Connections	Specify ALL internal and external connections For example <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection to DB (type of connection, which DB) • Connecting to external service (e.g. weather forecast, specify API used if possible) • Connecting to another I-ENERGY service (specify which)
Licence type	Proprietary/open source
Data requirements	
Input data	Specify all input data needed for the service and the period e.g. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Weather data (once per day 15 min interval (time UTC,))

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Specify period (e.g. Once per day, on-demand triggered by Service X, event,...) b. The granularity of data or time resolution (e.g. 1s, 1min, 15min, not applicable for reports) c. Quantities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Smart meter data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Real-time b. 1 min c. Timestamp, Voltages per phase, Active and Reactive power 3. Historical data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Once per request b. 15 minute c. Timestamp, Quantity 1, Quantity 2,...
Output data	<p>Description of the service output (check input data for examples)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Report <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generated once per execution b. Not applicable c. Estimated Energy Savings
Hyperparameters	<p>List of the hyperparameters within the tool that the app user can modify to adapt the service to its specific use case. Some examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nominal power [kW] 2. Location [longitude, latitude] 3. Time zone 4. Optimisation setting

Figure 10. I-ENERGY template for Service description.

On the other hand, the pilot partners were asked to provide more details regarding data sources and the availability of sharing the data with I-ENERGY consortium. A template of data questionnaire is presented in

Figure 11, whereas the list of filled out questionnaires can be found in Appendix 0, at the end of the document. The data template has two sections for historical data and live data available at the start of the project. The data template provides a short description of data and the main technical information for easier and faster integration and usage of data in the service development.

I-ENERGY Data description

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]	
Pilot No. [Pilot owner - Location]	
One table per different data source!	
Historical Data available	
Short data description	<p>Examples (only one per table!):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Historical weather data for location X 2. Historical dataset of ... for AI training
System providing information	Example: SCADA, GIS, EMS, DB
Data Format and information model	Examples:

	1. JSON, Proprietary data model 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model 3. XML, CIM
Suggested communication protocol	FTP, MQTT, HTTP,...
Number of data sources	Examples: 100 smart meters, 10 homes with EMS,...
Granularity	1 min
Time window	2 years (from 1.1.2019 to 31.12.2020)
Nature of data	Sensitive/Proprietary/open

Live Data available

Short data description	Examples (only one per table!): 1. Smart meter measurements 2. EV Charging data from EV EMS
Data source	Example: e.g. smart meter, IoT, (x)EMS
Data Format and information model	Examples: 1. JSON, Proprietary data model 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model 3. XML, CIM
Suggested communication protocol	I1/P1, MQTT, ...
Number of data sources	Examples: 100 smart meters, 10 homes with EMS,...
Granularity	1 min
Nature of data	Sensitive/Proprietary/open

Data examples

Provide the examples of data if already exists from the Data source for example:

1. PMU data (Messages as JSON objects)

A sample message:

```
{
  "node_id": "",
  "stn": "Station-0",
  "soc": 1602078510,
  "fracsec": 0,
  "vm1": 230.31439208984375,
  "vph1": -47.657395631859266,
  "vm2": 230.9148406982422,
  "vph2": 72.33367040491599,
  "vm3": 231.7793426513672,
  "vph3": -167.5164955836807,
  "vm4": 230.86802673339844,
  "vph4": -167.50331331858257,
  "im1": 0.000057650599046610296,
  "iph1": 52.590786627846114,
  "im2": 0.00003093302439083345,
  "iph2": -111.98963261279414,
  "im3": 0.000042565585317788646,
  "iph3": 76.26046227197222,
  "im4": 0.000029644323149113916,
  "iph4": 149.5296841780724,
  "f": 49.98057174682617,
  "df": 0.06389617919921875,
  "digita": 0,
  "analog": 0,
  "vzsm": 0.3782951235771179,
  "vzsp": -164.22327889422402,
  "izsm": 0.00002246705480501987,
```

```
"izsph": 60.14759522742692
}
```

2. Disaggregated data (Raw data)

Energy:419.895
light_livingroom:1584642981000,7.611,-1.402
stove:1584642383000,-959.607,30.551
light_bathroom:1584642638000,-78.074,1.3575
light_bathroom:1584643985000,78.639,-1.043
light_bathroom:1584644221000,78.375,-1.193

Figure 11. I-ENERGY template for data availability.

Tasks meetings were arranged on a weekly basis in attempt to synchronize Usage Scenarios, identified services and data availability and seek for their cross section (Figure 5). This was an iterative process, involving all partners, which contributed to the creation of new services and removing unneeded auxiliary services, which in turn resulted in the complete list of harmonized services.

2.1.3 Step 3

The last step is dedicated to creating the final Use Cases by analysing all Usage Scenarios and Services. The mapping of Usage Scenarios and their clustering according to the similarities will be reflected in the final Use Case. Since this is a work in progress and needs the iterative approach among partners, the final results and steps describing final Use Case creation will be provided later in deliverable D2.5.

2.2 Identification of Functional and Non-Functional Requirements

The Use Case writing process enables identifying and documenting the preconditions and requirements efficiently already during the step 1 and step 2 of the methodology. Since this is an initial process of identifying the relations and steps, it has to be noted that Usage Scenarios are generic, and they cannot identify all preconditions and requirements. Therefore, the requirements and preconditions related to the development of algorithms and tools are not captured by the methodology.

A **precondition** is a requirement that has to be met in order to successfully initiate basis scenario use case.

A **functional requirement** describes a system's functions that need to be performed. A system functions are inputs and outputs. The functional requirements correspond to each sentence of the step-by-step description of the Usage scenario, for example, what the Persona must do.

Non-Functional requirement describes the quality attribute of a software system. It also allows user to impose restrictions on the system. It is a requirement that defines criteria that can be used to determine a system's operation rather than specific actions.

3 I-ENERGY concepts

I-ENERGY project aims to increase innovation capacity in the smart grid energy market by exploring new concepts, solutions and business models. Furthermore, I-ENERGY will focus on boosting the deployment of AI-based solutions and services, enabling a larger user community to reap the economic benefits of AI, especially SME and non-technology sectors. The AI-based analytic services are the bridge between the data provider and the data analyst and will result in:

- Optimizing consumer involvement as an active stakeholder within the energy value chain.
- Enabling energy business and regulated operators in charge of operating energy distribution as a service of public interest.
- Redesigning a value chain by adding new stakeholders such as Equipment manufacturers and P2P Block Chain technology providers.
- Linking energy services to non-energy services (care management, ambient assisted living, safety,...).
- Reinforcing social cohesion of the local communities.
- Enabling creation of new AI specialist skills jobs.
- Integrating a larger share of renewable energy resources.
- Mitigating climate change effects.

3.1 Services to be developed in the project

The project's DoW does not explicitly define the services to be developed, so they need to be determined during the process of writing the Use Cases according to the requirements and needs of the pilots. Therefore, the services definition process was established to address and find the AI based services efficiently.

3.1.1 Service definition process

The service definition started from two aspects:

- Technical partners had first identified the possible services from the WP4 and WP3 task description
- Pilot owners have, according to the Usage Scenario and Persona point of view, identified all possible Services (AI and auxiliary services) that are required to finish the Usage Scenario successfully

In the next step, followed by few online harmonization meetings, the iterative process of defining and refining the services took part. After few iterations, the main services related only to the AI were identified. The advantage of this approach is that it enables one to look at the same service from different perspectives, from the pilot owner perspective, technical partner and last but not least from persona point of view, allowing identification of all requirements to efficiently address all the technical and non-technical requirements.

Deliverable 2.1: -NERGY Technology Requirements & User Stories

Services needed per Use Case	T3.1 Blockchain platform for data and model sharing - Do you need a safe way to share data or AI Models (With blockchain)?	T3.2 Common harmonised data repository (do you want easy access to data from different sources - satellite, weather, market, open data)	T3.3 & T3.5 AI model creation (e.g. classification, prediction/regression) not covered in T4.2 - T4.4	T3.4 Could the pilot benefit / test Cross-transfer learning techniques (e.g. take a model and apply it in other location / country / domain)	T4.1- Visualisations / Charts	T4.2 - DT for Electrical / Thermal flexibility, load patterns - Profiling & user behaviour	T4.3 Digital Twin / Simulation Models for Distributed Energy Resources Coordination (using DPSim Software)	T4.4 Energy flexibility forecasting Energy load/consumption/demand forecasting	T4.5 - i-ENERGY Virtual Workbench - Marketplace (catalog of ML models and Data sources to facilitate the creation of new application) - Do you plan to share the models in the Marketplace?
Pilot 1									
UC1 - Predictive Maintenance for Circuit Breakers	No	Yes	Yes - Predictive Maintenance Model for Circuit Breakers	No	Yes				No
UC2 - (Net load forecasting) Forecast of aggregated net load on day ahead timeframe	No	Yes			Yes			Yes	
Pilot 2									
UC3 - AI for energy demand prediction to optimise DHN operation	no	yes - Weather data	no	yes	Yes	no	no	Yes	no
UC4 - Measurement and verification of energy savings (IPMVP)	no	yes	no	yes	Yes		no	no	no
UC5 - Optimization of the production mix - Match the demand to the generation for multi energy systems decision-support.	no	yes	no		Yes		no	yes	no
Pilot 3									
UC6 - Predictive Maintenance Analytics - Analyse distribution network asset data and derive predictive maintenance schedule	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
UC7 - Generation and load forecasting - Analyse historical distribution network generation and load profiles in relation to historical meteorological profiles. Derive probabilistic forecast for generation and consumption under consideration of meteorological forecast.	Yes	Yes - Data from the market	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
UC8 - Flexibility assessment - Analyse distribution network flexibility potential-based on forecasts regarding distribution network generation, storage and consumption, together with the knowledge of the network topology and the device's flexibility options	No	Yes - Data from water system	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Pilot 4									
UC9 - Analyse distribution DER (PV) devices data and derive predictive plants maintenance	no	yes - Weather data	Yes - Predictive Maintenance Model for PV Plants		Yes				
Pilot 5									
UC10 - Present electricity demand in building and EV charging stations					Yes				
UC10 - Provides real time data related to electricity consumption centres and specifically EV charging stations					Yes				
UC10- Variable pricing algorithm to enable charge point operators distribute charging load evenly through time intervals		YES - Weather, Market, Traffic				Yes			
Pilot 6									
UC11 - A virtual renewable energy community Reports based on services rendered within the virtual renewable energy community oPV production forecast (household) oFlexibility forecast (household/ community) oEMS optimisation (household/ cluster / community)		YES		YES	Yes	Yes (Profiling and user behaviour?)		Yes	
Pilot 7									
UC12 - Disaggregation service				yes	Yes				
UC12 - Optimisation of the flexibility; Consumer Digital Twin		yes	yes		Yes			yes	
UC12 - User profiling (or DT of citizen)					Yes	yes			
Pilot 8									
UC13 - Assess alternative energy efficiency action plans for buildings in terms of anticipated energy savings and prioritise them according to the user's criteria	no	yes	no	no	Yes			yes	no
Pilot 9									
UC14 - Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement	no	yes	yes	no	Yes	no	no	no	no
UC14 - Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation	no	yes	yes	no	Yes	no	no	no	no
UC15 - Solar Radiation forecasting	no	yes	no	no	yes	no	no	yes	no

Figure 12. An example of an initial pilots service needs mapping to the tasks from which services were derived.

In Figure 12, the example of the intermediate step is shown from the process of identifying the Services. The excel file with the mapping of pilots' needs to tasks is shown to identify easier the requirements that will lead to Services. Technical partners populated this excel sheet requirements. In another sheet, the working example is shown in Figure 13, where the identification of the Service took place. This list was consolidated in an iterative process that took place between technical partners and pilot owners.

Task	Service name	comment:	
T4.1	Visual analytics dashboard for electricity consumption centers		General services
T4.2	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres		ML services
	Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement		Auxiliary services
	Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation		
			>> I've changed the name adding Climate change since I think it fits better. If it is Ok I will do so in the doc with the explanation of the service
	Climate change solar radiation forecasting	Change of name to Long term Solar radiation forecasting?, so we can distinguish it from weather forecasting services	
T4.3	Digital Twin: DER simulation for supporting system level scenario evaluation		
	Analyse distribution DER (PV) devices data and derive predictive plants maintenance	Can we simplify the Service name?	
	Measurement and verification of energy savings (IPMVP)		
T4.4.	Energy flexibility forecasting		
	Energy load/consumption/demand forecasting		
	AI for energy demand prediction to optimise DHN operation		
	Optimization of the production mix		
T4.5	I-nergy Virtual Workbench - Marketplace (catalog of ML models and Data sources to facilitate the creation of new application)		
T3.3	Predictive Maintenance Model for PV Plants	Is this same as T4.3 Analyse distributed DER... ?	
T3.4	Disaggregation of loads from SM measurements	should we remove it from this list?	
	Activity recognition and forecasting		
	Anomalous behaviour detection		

Figure 13. Initial Service list that was refined during the service identification process.

3.1.2 Services to be developed by I-ENERGY

After the iterative process was finished, the list of Services was identified. Most of the Services are related to AI analytical Services; however, three supportive Services were identified that are common to most of the pilots (S1, S13 and S16). In addition, Usage Scenarios identified other auxiliary services needed to support the implementation of the Usage Scenario to a specific pilot. Due to their specific nature, they are not listed here and are considered to be developed by pilot owners or technical partners. The nature of these Services is mostly non-analytical.

The list of Services (labelled with S and the corresponding number) are:

- S1: Visual analytics dashboard for electricity consumption centers
- S2: Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
- S3: Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement
- S4: Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation
- S5: Climate change solar radiation forecasting
- S6: Digital Twin: DER simulation for supporting system level scenario evaluation
- S7: Predictive Maintenance Analytics
- S8: Measurement and verification of energy savings
- S9: Energy flexibility forecasting
- S10: Energy load/consumption/demand forecasting
- S11: AI for energy demand prediction to optimise DHN operation
- S12: Optimization of the production mix
- S13: I-ENERGY Virtual Workbench - Marketplace (catalogue of ML models and Data sources to facilitate the creation of new application)
- S14: Activity recognition and forecasting
- S15: Anomalous behaviour detection
- S16: Blockchain Hybrid energy data storage

3.2 Mapping of Services

The determined Services were described in more detail, identifying technical requirements such as implementation specifics and data requirements. A more detailed description of the Services can be found in Appendix 5.3. The Services might have more than one developer since the same goal can be achieved with different inputs. Therefore, more variants of the Service, developed by various technical partners, might exist. In the first Service description, the inputs were provided, which are relevant at the start of the project based on the pilots' specifications and available pilot data. However, these inputs might change during the project execution when more data sources are available. The services were mapped to the I-ENERGY domains: I-NET, I-DER and I-ENEF as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14. Mapping of services to I-ENERGY domains.

All I-NET, I-DER and I-ENEF Services are AI-based; there might also exist some variants of the Service where the parametric approach is considered in parallel to AI. More details can be seen in the Services description. Three Services S1, S13 and S16, are the general services that are not linked to the I-ENERGY domains. S1 is the visualization dashboard that enriches the output of other Services, whereas the scope of Service S13 is to help create new Services based on AI models and distributed data and S16 scope is to leverage on blockchain to enable a secure, trusted and flexible data sharing for B2B cross-stakeholders.

4 Conclusions

The scope of the deliverable was to set the foundation for further work in the I-ENERGY project. By structurally collecting and synchronizing the requirements among the pilot owners and technical partners, we efficiently addressed the open issues of creating novel solutions as proposed in the I-ENERGY project. Moreover, the methodology used by the I-ENERGY project partners gave us a unique opportunity of shaping the ideas from a broad Persona point of view. Thus, the Personas were not only technical actors directly involved in the process but also indirectly involved Personas, which might cover technical and also social-economic perspective, resulting in a comprehensive description of all possible needs.

During this top-down approach of collecting the necessary information, we started collecting the first requirements by filling the Test Card template. Altogether, the number of Test Cards is the same as Use Cases defined in DoW. From Test Cards, Personas were extracted, their User Stories were derived, and Usage Scenarios were defined. In this process, we have collected 93 unique User Stories, which resulted in the same number of Usage Scenarios.

The main outcome of these steps is a detailed definition and specification of AI value chain functionalities across the I-ENERGY ecosystem. This was followed by identifying the initial list of Services to be developed in WP3 and WP4 by collecting some technical details to facilitate the initial activities at related tasks. The 13 I-ENERGY AI-based Services, together with three general Services, are more in detail described in Appendix 5.3.

As described in Section 2, the delivered work provides a primary tool to empower the project from specifications, analysis, implementation and piloting.

References

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5 Appendix

5.1 APPENDIX I - Test Cards

5.1.1 Pilot 1

Common Test Card for Use Case 1: AI for enhanced network assets predictive maintenance, integrating off-grid data with condition-based monitoring and Use Case 2: AI for network loads and demand forecasting towards efficient operational planning.

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 1 [RDN/REN - Portugal]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Asset maintenance analytics models:** Apply data analytics techniques to historic transmission system asset data (e.g. Circuit Breakers). Use extracted insights and models to build optimal condition and predictive based maintenance plans for these assets.
- **Design forecast methodologies:** Apply AI-based forecasting techniques to support internal processes of TSOs, including operational planning. This includes aggregated and disaggregated forecasting of energy load.

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Improved TSO asset operation
- Extended asset lifetime
- Optimized operation and maintenance costs
- Potential enhancement in the analysis of asset state and asset incident analysis
- AI-based forecasting techniques improve on internal forecast methods

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
<i>Specify users of the pilot service</i>	<i>Develop different personas around the groups</i>
Transmission System Operators (TSO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asset management departments • System Management Division

5.1.2 Pilot 2

5.1.2.1 Use Case 3: AI for energy demand prediction to optimise District Heating Network (DHN) operation

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot 2. [VEOLIA -Spain]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Accurate demand forecasting:**
 - Economic benefit optimization.
 - Energy consumption reduction.
 - GHG emissions reduction.
- **Accurate model calibration for DHNs design:** Refined design of new DHN branches or new DHNs, with an upgraded veracity and reducing risks.
- **Improved facility analysis:** Optimized operation and maintenance due to reliable data analysis.
- **Improved ROI.**

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Energy consumption and GHG emissions reduction.
- Failure rates in facilities decrease.
- Profit increase.
- Easier development of new DHNs.

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Facility Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability supporter DHN manager. • Cost-conscious DHN manager.
Designer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Profit-oriented DHN designer.
Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefit-oriented bank. • Sustainability supporter bank.
Citizens and Owners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed owner

5.1.2.2 Use Case 4: AI for energy saving verification service, increasing the trust on Energy Performance Contracts

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot 2. [VEOLIA -Spain]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Cost-effective assessment and new EP Contract (EPC) simulations:**
 - Energy savings verification service to boost EP Contracts trust.
 - Improvement on the deployment of M&V Protocols (i.e. IPMVP) to generate analytics to aid in calculating energy savings with the aim of supporting EP Contracts.
 - Identification of new savings.
- **Energy-efficient refurbishments:** Assist in the design of energy-efficient renovations at facilities with EP Contracts.
- **Advanced facility analysis:**
 - Prediction of behavioural usage.
 - Facility errors detection.
 - Advanced reporting.
- **Improved ROI.**

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Reduced error rates in facilities and following costs.
- Better evaluation of EP Contracts.
- Development of further saving measures.

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
ESCOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced ESCO. • EPC facilitator.
Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefit-oriented bank. • Sustainability supporter bank.
Citizens and Owners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motivated owner.

5.1.2.3 Use Case 5: AI for multi energy systems decision-support - Reina Sofia

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot 2. [VEOLIA –Spain]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Accurate demand forecasting:**
 - Economic benefit optimization.
 - Energy consumption reduction.
 - GHG emissions reduction.
- **Energy consumption reduction:**
 - Cost and GHG emissions reduction
- **Optimization of the production mix:** match the demand to the generation.
- **Improved operation and maintenance of the network.**
- **Energy efficiency increase.**
- **Advanced facility analysis:**
 - Behavioural usage prediction.
 - Error's detection of facilities.
 - Advanced reporting.

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Error rates in facilities reduction and following costs.
- Reduced energy consumption and GHG emissions reduction.
- Energy efficiency increase.
- O&M costs reduction.
- Energy costs reduction.

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Facility Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability supporter FM. • Cost-conscious FM.
Investors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability supporter bank.
Designer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Efficiency-oriented designer

5.1.3 Pilot 3

5.1.3.1 Use Case 6: Cross-functional AI-based predictive analytics to support integrated DSOs asset management and network operation

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 3 [ASM – Italy]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Goal 1:** Prediction of assets failure (Transformers, lines)
- **Goal 2:** Optimization of grid operation at the MV and LV level.

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- SAIDI, SAIFI
- Number of replaced assets yearly
- Reduction of power losses in the distribution grid

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Utility	Informed utility manager Head of the maintenance service

5.1.3.2 Use Case 7: AI-based consumption and flexibility prediction for local community optimal aggregation and flexibility trading

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 3 [ASM – Italy]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Goal 1:** Reduction of the reverse power flow at the secondary substation
- **Goal 2:** validate decentralised Virtual Power Plant-based community-level aggregation
- **Goal 3:** local flexibility trading by leveraging on P2P DLT and smart contract-based negotiation along heterogeneous customer types

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Reduction of congestions in the distribution grid
- Reduction of Reverse Power Flow
- Number of customers included in the local flexibility market

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Utility	Head of the network operation/ remote management Informed utility manager
Service company	Aggregator
Citizen and users	Energy consumers Prosumers

5.1.3.3 Use Case 8: AI-based energy-driven and non-energy services

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 3 [ASM – Italy]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Goal 1:** Demonstrate and validate other AI-based energy driven and non-energy services, which leverage the massive deployment and availability of fine-grained metering electricity consumption data.

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Prediction of energy flexibility taking into account users' comfort and needs
- Predicting abnormal intrusion and abnormal consumption patterns for electric loads
- The exploitation of energy flexibility from the water system
- Improvement of energy distribution service (e.g., reduction of outages and losses)

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Utility	Informed utility manager Manager of the water system
Citizens and owners	Technology-aware owner Technology-hater owner

5.1.3.4 Overall summary

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 3 [ASM – Italy]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Goal 1:** Prediction of assets failure (Transformers, lines)
- **Goal 2:** Optimization of grid operation at the MV and LV level.
- **Goal 3:** The need for reducing the reverse power flow, a strong requirement for local power network congestion management takes place.
- **Goal 4:** Demonstrate and validate other AI-based energy driven and non-energy services, which leverage the massive deployment and availability of fine-grained metering electricity consumption data.

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- SAIDI, SAIFI
- Number of replaced assets yearly
- Reduction of power losses in the distribution grid
- Reduction of Reverse Power Flow
- Prediction of energy flexibility taking into account users' comfort and needs
- Predicting abnormal intrusion and abnormal consumption patterns for electric loads

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Service Provider	Informed utility manager Head of the maintenance service Manager of the water system Head of the network operation/ remote management
Service company	Aggregator
Citizens and owners	Energy consumer Prosumers Technology-aware owner Technology-hater owner

5.1.4 Pilot 4

5.1.4.1 Use Case 9: AI-based IoT-enabled PV module-level portfolio optimal predictive maintenance and PV-enhanced industrial plant optimal operation

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 4 [BFP – Italy]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Goal 1:** Improvement of predictive maintenance.
- **Goal 2:** Data flow availability at PV module level provided by IoT sensors and drones.
- **Goal 3:** Data-driven O&M management strategy.
- **Goal 4:** Optimization of industrial plant operation (energy bill reduction, auto-consumption strategy, monetary gain rise).

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Reduction of power losses.
- Reduction of replaced PV modules.
- Prediction of electrical faults.
- Energy bill analysis.
- Optimization of operation and maintenance strategies.

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Plants operator group	O&M manager
Plants operator group	Asset manager
Owner	Owner representative

5.1.5 Pilot 5

5.1.5.1 Use Case 10: AI in EV charging infrastructure

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No. 5 [HERON/PARITY - Greece]

- Goal** (Overarching pilot goals)
- **Goal 1:** Identify load patterns for residential customers that they own/operate EV charging stations.
 - **Goal 2:** Identify patterns in the charging transactions in publicly accessible charging stations to develop.
 - **Goal 3:** Provide incentives for drivers to distribute charging load evenly across public charging stations and time intervals.
 - **Goal 4:** Demonstrate and validate AI-based algorithms to better predict the load distribution from pilot end-users to identify an optimum EV charging schedule as well as leverage the real-time electricity consumption data.
 - **Goal 5:** Identify energy flexibility taking into account users' comfort and needs.

- Metrics** (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)
- Total kWh/month and year used for EV charging.
 - Total kWh/month and year consumed for an EV owner/user.
 - Number of times where the EV charging was done when the electricity cost was the cheapest.
 - Number of times of loads shifting to off-peak hours.
 - Data analysis and predictions based on usage patterns of customers can be used to provide useful insights into how home devices, including EV asset, are used.

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Utility	Distribution System Operator (DSO) Retailers
Citizens & owners	EV owner/user Technology-aware consumer

5.1.6 Pilot 6

5.1.6.1 Use Case 11: AI for peer-to-peer renewable energy trading in virtual energy community

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No.6 [ZEZcoop - Croatia]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Renewable energy community:** Organising 100 prosumers in a virtual renewable energy community. Education of citizens and creating favourable social momentum.
- **Peer-to-peer energy trading:** utilization of AI toolbox developed within the project for the goal to allow peer-to-peer energy trading within the community.
- **Demand-side management:** Expose potentials for flexibility, with the end goal to allow the appearance of the virtual energy community on the auxiliary services market.
- **Policy recommendations:** Support policy change through advocacy for energy communities.
- **Prosumer business models:** Develop a collaboration model that will be easily replicable and demonstrate the added value of a virtual energy community to further utilise RES local potential and growth of the local economy.

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Number of prosumers (citizens and public buildings) gathered in a virtual renewable energy community
- Number of citizens engaged/educated
- Number of the market (solar entrepreneurs) and institutional partners (policy makers, DSO, cities, faculties etc.) engaged

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
<i>Specify users of the pilot service</i>	<i>Develop different personas around the groups</i>
User 1 Citizens (prosumers)	1. Traditionalists / Savers 2. Eco-conscious
User 2 Public buildings (local authorities)	1. Eco-conscious
User 3 Solar entrepreneurs (e.g. installers)	1. Informed solar installer

5.1.7 Pilot 7

5.1.7.1 Use Case 12: AI for the Ambient Assisted Living and personal safety/security at home

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot 7. [SONCE - Slovenia]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Improve non-energy services** (security, safety AAL) by utilizing the fingerprinting methods for modelling devices and behaviour
- **Improve flexibility** by creating a virtual community with dynamic load management based on non-energy services
- **Cost optimization**, holistic analysis to increase and better match local production and self-consumption

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Number of citizens responding to the proposed solution
- kWh from RES self-consumed
- Increased daily flexibility
- Profit increase
- Number of new non-energy services offered

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Facility Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed • Sustainability supporting • Cost-conscious
Marketplace operator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Profit-oriented
Citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed • Careless

5.1.8 Pilot 8

5.1.8.1 Use Case 13: AI for energy efficiency investments de-risking

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No. 8 [REA – Latvia]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Goal 1:** Cost-effective assessment that ensures low-risk investments in energy efficiency and helps to categorize investment priorities
- **Goal 2:** Holistic and reliable analysis that provides predictive maintenance warnings

**Goals of the pilot that allow*

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- Measure1: Assessment of economic costs of applied measures
- Measure 2: Better evaluation of EPCs
- Measure 3: Development of further saving measure

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
<i>Specify users of the pilot service</i>	<i>Develop different personas around the groups</i>
User 1* Institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ambitious head of department • Project manager
User 2 Facility Managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible managers • Careless managers
User 3 Policy Maker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Informed policy makers

5.1.9 Pilot 9

5.1.9.1 Use Case 14: AI for improved Energy Performance Certificates Reliability

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No. 9 [FAEN – Spain]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Goal 1:** Make Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) more reliable, user-friendly, cost-effective, better quality and EU legislation-compliant, as well as removing ‘reliability’ barriers (to take advantage of the high potential of EPCs significant in energy efficiency in the building sector).
- **Goal 2:** Support policy makers to generate trust in EPCs and boost the energy refurbishment market.
- **Goal 3:** Support policy makers to predict the optimal building energy retrofitting planning dates.
- **Goal 4:** Support the EPCs quality checking mechanisms deployed by certification authorities by contrasting existing EPCs with alarms raised when AI inferred energy values greatly differ from existing EPCs.

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals. Each measure related to previous goals)

- **Measure 1:** EPCs quality is improved
- **Measure 2:** Energy refurbishment market boosted (thanks to EPCs trust generated)
- **Measure 3:** Policy makers are able to select the optimal building energy retrofitting planning
- **Measure 4:** EPCs quality checking mechanisms are improved and useful for policy makers in charge of EPCs

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy makers in charge of EPCs • Policy makers in charge of energy retrofitting/refurbishment strategies.

5.1.9.2 Use Case 15: AI for predicting the climate change impact in RES and energy demand at regional (local) level

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 9 [FAEN – Spain]

Goal (Overarching pilot goals)

- **Goal 1:** Support policy makers in the generation of energy strategies (mainly those related to renewable energy resources, with a special interest in solar energy) at the regional level, to plan the deployment of renewable sources in an effective manner, contemplating Climate Change impacts.
- **Goal 2:** Predict the potential (long term) of renewable resources (solar radiation mainly) at the regional level (Asturias), by assessing vulnerabilities that may arise from the Climate Change impacts.

Metrics (The measures to determine if the pilot achieves the goals)

- **Measure 1:** Increased information (reports, studies...) about the main effects of Climate Change in renewable energy resources.
- **Measure 2:** Methods (models) provided to predict the potential of renewable energy sources (solar radiation) for its exploitation at the regional level (assessing Climate Change vulnerabilities).

Target group (The users and stakeholders benefited by the pilot service/development. Development of PERSONAS)

Target group	Personas
Policy makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Strategies planners – Fundación Asturiana de la Energía

5.2 APPENDIX II - User Stories

5.2.1 Pilot 1

5.2.1.1 Use Case 1: AI for enhanced network assets predictive maintenance, integrating off-grid data with condition-based monitoring

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 1 [RDN/REN - Portugal]

Persona: Asset Management Division of TSO	
Story 1	As a TSO asset manager, I want to be able to be able to take advantage and utilize the large amounts of oscillography data generated by the tripping of circuit breakers, so that better optimized maintenance practices can be derived for this class of assets
Story 2	As a TSO asset manager, I want to be able to automatically extract data insights, related to individual circuit breaker tripping incidents (such as fault detection time, elimination time, maximum faulted current or incident type), from COMTRADE files, so that those faults can be analysed in an automatic and fast way.
Story 3	As a TSO asset manager, I want to be able to correlate faults recorded in COMTRADE files with off-grid data (e.g. time-of-year, weather, forest fires), so that that the external factors with the highest impact on incidents can be studied.

5.2.1.2 Use Case 2: AI for network loads and demand forecasting towards efficient operational planning

Persona: TSO System Operator	
Story 1	As a system operator, I want to improve the current methodologies used to forecast net load, using AI techniques, so that those internal processes which rely on the accuracy of these forecasts (e.g. cross border trading and operational planning) can be optimized

5.2.2 Pilot 2

5.2.2.1 Use Case 3: AI for energy demand prediction to optimise District Heating Network (DHN) operation

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]	
Pilot No. 2 [VEOLIA -Spain]	
Persona: Sustainability supporter DHN manager.	
Story 1	As a Sustainability supporter DHN manager, I want to get a better understanding of how the facility operates, so that the failures decrease and the efficiency increases.
Story 2	As a Sustainability supporter DHN manager, I want to forecast the behaviour of the facility and its reaction to potential changes, so that the energy consumption and the GHG emissions are reduced.
Story 3	As a Sustainability supporter DHN manager, I want to get an accurate DHN model, so that network expansion and new energy efficiency measures can be implemented more easily.
Persona: Cost-conscious DHN manager.	
Story 1	As a Cost-conscious DHN manager, I want to get a better understanding of how the facility operates, so that the failures and costs are reduced, and the efficiency is increased.
Story 2	As a Cost-conscious DHN manager, I want to forecast the behaviour of the facility and its reaction to potential changes, so that there is a de-risking when implementing energy efficiency measures.
Story 3	As a Cost-conscious DHN manager, I want to get an accurate DHN model, so that the risks of expanding or retrofit the DHN and its costs are lowered.
Persona: Profit-oriented DHN designer.	
Story 1	As a Profit-oriented DHN designer, I want to get a better understanding of how the facility operates, so that the design can be better adapted to the specifications.
Story 2	As a Profit-oriented DHN designer, I want to get an accurate DHN baseline model, so that it is simpler to design the installation in a more efficient and cost-effective way.
Persona: Benefit-oriented bank.	
Story 1	As a Benefit-oriented bank, I want to minimize the risk of DHN renovations investment, so that I can invest in more facilities with conviction and obtain a profit.
Story 2	As a Benefit-oriented bank, I want to accurately predict the profit and the return on investment when making this kind of investment, so that I can make better forecast about my investment plan.
Story 3	As a Benefit-oriented bank, I want to match energy savings to profit, so that I can comprehend the upsides.
Persona: Sustainability supporter bank.	

Story 1	As a Sustainability supporter bank, I want to predict the economic and environmental impact of the DHN renovations, so that I can understand the upsides of the intervention, helping me to decide.
Story 2	As a Sustainability supporter bank, I want to increase the ROI on my investment, so that I can encourage more energy efficiency interventions.

Persona:	Informed owner
Story 1	As an Informed owner, I want to benefit from an EP Contract, so that I can avoid the initial costs of the DHN renovation.
Story 2	As an Informed owner, I want the facility to be more efficient, so that there is an increase of the service availability and the comfort.

5.2.2.2 Use Case 4: AI for energy saving verification service, increasing the trust on Energy Performance Contracts

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 2 [VEOLIA –Spain]

Persona: **Advanced ESCO.**

Story 1 **As an** Advanced ESCO, **I want to** implement energy efficiency measures in different facilities, **so that** the efficiency of these facilities is reduced, lowering costs and GHG emissions.

Story 2 **As an** Advanced ESCO, **I want to** be able to obtain accurate energy savings predictions, **so that** the EP Contracts are calculated with more precision.

Persona: **EPC facilitator.**

Story 1 **As an** EP Contract facilitator, **I want to** show the economic and environmental benefits of introducing energy efficiency measures in the buildings, **so that** owners can encourage the building or facility renovation.

Story 2 **As an** EPC facilitator, **I want to** provide reliable information about the behaviour of the facilities before and after and intervention, **so that** owners realise the upsides of the energy efficiency measures.

Persona: **Benefit-oriented bank.**

Story 1 **As a** Benefit-oriented bank, **I want to** decrease the risk in the investment in energy efficiency measures, **so that** it can be more likely to participate in or provide credit for this type of business.

Story 2 **As a** Benefit-oriented bank, **I want to** accurately predict the return on investment and the profit obtained when making this kind of investment, **so that** I can make better predictions about my investment plan.

Persona: **Sustainability supporter bank.**

Story 1 **As a** Sustainability supporter bank, **I want to** predict the economic and environmental impact of the energy efficiency measures, **so that** I can understand the advantages of the intervention, helping me to decide.

Story 2 **As a** Sustainability supporter bank, **I want to** increase the ROI on my investment, **so that** I can encourage more energy efficiency interventions.

Persona: **Motivated owner.**

Story 1 **As a** Motivated owner, **I want to** persuade other owners of the upsides of energy efficiency interventions, **so that** they become encouraged to implement these measures too.

Story 2 **As a** Motivated owner, **I want to** avoid the initial costs of the interventions by using EP Contracts, **so that** the energy efficiency intervention can be carried out even if I cannot afford it.

Story 3 **As a** Motivated owner, **I want to** implement energy efficiency measures in my building, **so that** the value of the building increases.

5.2.2.3 Use Case 5: AI for multi energy systems decision-support - Reina Sofia

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 2 [VEOLIA -Spain]

Persona: Sustainability supporter FM.

Story 1	As a Sustainability supporter FM, I want to get a better understanding of how the facility operates, so that the failures decrease, the efficiency increases, and the production mix can be optimized.
Story 2	As a Sustainability supporter FM, I want to forecast accurately the facility's behaviour and its response to potential changes, so that the energy consumption and the GHG emissions are reduced.
Story 3	As a Sustainability supporter FM, I want to get an accurate facility model, so that new energy efficiency measures can be implemented more easily, and the production mix can be optimized.

Persona: Cost-conscious FM.

Story 1	As a Cost-conscious FM, I want to get a better understanding of how the facility operates, so that the failures and costs are reduced, and the efficiency is increased.
Story 2	As a Cost-conscious FM, I want to forecast accurately the facility's behaviour and its response to potential changes, so that there is a de-risking when implementing energy efficiency measures.
Story 3	As a Cost-conscious FM, I want to get an accurate facility model, so that the costs of implementing new energy efficiency measures and of the optimization of the production mix are reduced due to the selection of the best choice.

Persona: Sustainability supporter bank.

Story 1	As a Sustainability supporter bank, I want to predict the economic and environmental impact of the facility optimization, so that I can understand the upsides of the intervention, helping me to decide where to invest.
Story 2	As a Sustainability supporter bank, I want to increase the ROI on my investment, so that I can encourage more energy efficiency interventions.

Persona: Efficiency-oriented designer.

Story 1	As an Efficiency-oriented designer, I want to easily understand how the facility operates, so that I have an accurate picture of how the facility works depending on the different configuration that can be suggested.
Story 2	As an Efficiency-oriented designer, I want to get accurate TMY (Typical Meteorological Year), so that the installation is designed accurately.
Story 3	As an Efficiency-oriented designer, I want to provide the manager with an accurate model of the installation, so that he is able to manage it properly.

5.2.3 Pilot 3

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 3 [ASM – Italy]

Persona: Informed utility manager

Story 1 **As an** Informed utility manager, **I want to** adopt innovative scheduling programmes for the maintenance , **so that** I can reduce the cost for equipment replacement, penalties related to interruptions and I can improve the maintenance activities.

Story 2 **As an** Informed utility manager, **I want to** support the deployment of a flexibility marketplace, **so that** I can participate to new business model and improve network reliability.

Story 3 **As an** Informed utility manager, **I want to** provide new services and analytics to the final users, **so that** I can increase the interaction with them leading energy transition which is customer centric.

Persona: Head of maintenance service

Story 1 **As a** Head of the maintenance, **I want to** use analytics to increase the efficiency of my activities, **so that** I can improve the performances of my department.

Persona: Head of the network operation/ remote management

Story 1 **As a** Head of the network operation, **I want to** use flexibility in order to manage the distribution network, **so that** I can reduce issues on the distribution grid and improve awareness about the current status of the infrastructure.

Persona: Aggregator

Story 1 **As an** Aggregator, **I want to** participate to flexibility marketplace including customers in a pool, **so that** I can make profits and build up a robust business model

Persona: Energy consumers

Story 1 **As an** Energy consumer, **I want to** take economic advantage, **so that** I can reduce the cost for equipment replacement, penalties related to interruptions and I can improve the maintenance activities.

Persona: Prosumers

Story 1 **As a** prosumer, **I want to** adopt technologies that enable participation to flexibility marketplace, **so that** I can improve the awareness about consumption and increase economic benefits

Persona: Manager of the water system

Story 1 **As a** Manager of the water system, **I want to** adopt innovative scheduling programmes for the pumps, **so that** I can increase energy efficiency, participate in new business models related to energy flexibility

Persona:	Technology-aware owner
Story 1	As a Technology-aware owner, I want to adopt new services that estimate my flexibility taking into account my needs, so that I can participate in the energy flexibility marketplace
Persona:	Technology-hater owner
Story 1	As a Technology-hater owner, I want to receive static analytics of my consumption patterns, so that I can evaluate the feasibility and usefulness of adopting technologies that enable participation in energy flexibility market.

5.2.4 Pilot 4

5.2.4.1 Use Case 9: AI-based IoT-enabled PV module-level portfolio optimal predictive maintenance and PV-enhanced industrial plant optimal operation

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 4 [BFP – Italy]

Persona: O&M manager	
Story 1	As an O&M manager, I want to evaluate new technical solutions, so that we can apply more efficient procedures on-site in order to reduce electrical faults, the number of interventions, the use of spare parts and the costs.
Story 2	As an O&M manager, I want to evaluate new technical solutions, so that we can reach the scheduled goals with a time-saving benefit so to improve the work conditions on-site.

Persona: Asset manager	
Story 1	As an asset manager, I want to evaluate innovative, more efficient technical solutions, so that we can reduce the stops of the plants which are usually needed for carrying out maintenance.
Story 2	As an asset manager, I want to apply, more efficient technical solutions, so that we can increase the production and so the environmental/energy benefits for the community and economical ones for the investors.

Persona: Owner representative	
Story 1	As an Owner representative, I want to evaluate innovative technical solutions, so that we can optimize the business model, maximizing the production and reducing the costs at the same time.
Story 2	As an Owner representative, I want to apply new technical solutions, so that we can increase the monetary gain and reduce the plant payback time.

5.2.5 Pilot 5

5.2.5.1 Use Case 10: AI in EV charging infrastructure

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No. 5 [HERON/PARITY - Greece]

Persona: **Distribution System Operator (DSO)**

- | | |
|----------------|--|
| Story 1 | As an operator of the distribution network, I want to solve local/regional constraints with local resources with the best value of money and implement new investment deferral strategies, so that I can create a regional/local flexibility portfolio for congestion management and voltage control. |
| Story 2 | As an operator of the distribution network, I want to integrate EV charging stations into the grid to monitor and control voltage stability as well as power reliability, so that it can provide services to flatten the demand during peak hours. |

Persona: **Retailer**

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|----------------|---|
| Story 1 | As a retailer I want to broaden my flexibility pool and deploy demand-side flexibility, so that I can foster active participation in flexibility market-based programs for favouring dynamic pricing of EV charging. |
|----------------|---|

Persona: **EV owner/user**

- | | |
|----------------|--|
| Story 1 | As an EV owner/user I want to charge during times when the energy cost is lower and get my EV fully charged as fast as needed, so that I save more money and get my EV charged without losing time. |
|----------------|--|

Persona: **Technology-aware consumer**

- | | |
|----------------|--|
| Story 1 | As a technology-aware consumer I want to charge my EV at the lowest cost within flexibility, so that I manage my devices efficiently and optimize my consumption. |
| Story 2 | As a technology-aware consumer I want to be informed about the system-proposed flexibility, so that I can decide whether I want to accept them. |

5.2.6 Pilot 6

5.2.6.1 Use Case 11: AI for peer-to-peer renewable energy trading in virtual energy community

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 6 [ZEZcoop - Croatia]

Persona: Citizen prosumer (traditionalist & saver)

Story 1 As a traditionalist owner of a solar PV system for self-consumption, I want to optimize the system production to achieve bigger financial savings or additional revenues for my households. I want to be able to validate costs and energy savings.

Persona: Citizen prosumer (eco-conscious)

Story 1 As an eco-conscious owner of a solar PV system for self-consumption, I want to support distributed renewable energy production. I want to promote green and sustainable solutions (share my experience) , e.g. through participation in a renewable energy community.

Persona: Public building (eco-conscious local authorities)

Story 1 As an eco-conscious local authority and owner of a public building with rooftop solar PV, I want to have access to reliable information and validation of cost and energy savings so that I can better plan for future costs and investments.

Story 2 As an eco-conscious local authority and owner of a public building with rooftop solar PV, I want to engage local citizens and public officers (e.g. public facility managers) so that they become part of the green transition of the city (e.g. through active involvement in the market as prosumers).

Persona: Informed solar installer

Story 1 As an informed solar installer, I want to upgrade my services and expand my expertise so that I continue growing my business and gain new customers on the local level (e.g. through participation in a virtual energy community).

5.2.7 Pilot 7

5.2.7.1 Use Case 12: AI for the Ambient Assisted Living and personal safety/security at home

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot 7. [SONCE – Slovenia]

Persona: Informed Facility Manager

Story 1 **As an** Informed facility manager working for a retirement home, **I want to** lower the costs of living in the retirement home by participating in DR programs with non-energy services **so that** I can improve the well-being of the elderly by improving their daily/weekly schedules.

Persona: Sustainability supporting Facility Manager

Story 1 **As a** Sustainability supporting facility manager working for a retirement home, **I want to** improve the self-consumption from renewable resources **so that** I can decrease the running costs and create a greener image of the retirement home.

Persona: Cost-conscious Facility Manager

Story 1 **As a** Cost-conscious facility manager working for a retirement home, **I want to** improve the running cost by increasing self-consumption and better utilizing the care facilities **so that** I can decrease the running costs by optimizing schedules for care facilities and employees using it.

Persona: Profit-oriented Marketplace operator

Story 1 **As a** Profit-oriented Marketplace operator, **I want to** extend the P2P energy trading platform also to non-energy related services **so that** I can get new users to the platform and improve the competitiveness of the business.

Story 2 **As a** Profit-oriented Marketplace operator, **I want to** extend the P2P energy trading platform also by connecting fingerprinting assets on the platform **so that** I can get an average profile of the assets for a more accurate prediction of consumption and production.

Persona: Informed Citizens

Story 1 **As an** Informed citizen living at a retirement home, **I want to** become aware of comfort improvements opportunities **so that** I can improve my wellbeing with an optimized schedule.

Story 2 **As an** Informed citizen living at a retirement home, **I want to** participate in DR programs **so that** I can improve the wellbeing of the community.

Persona: Careless Citizens

Story 1 **As a** Careless citizen living at a retirement home, **I want to** participate only in the DR programs without sacrificing comfort **so that** I can reduce the costs of living in the retirement home.

5.2.8 Pilot 8

5.2.8.1 Use Case 13: AI for energy efficiency investments de-risking

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No. 8 [REA – Latvia]

Persona: **Ambitious head of department**

Story 1	As an ambitious head of department working for a government, I want to know how to manage energy consumption in buildings effectively, so that I have a cost-assessment and reliable information in the context of each building.
Story 2	As an ambitious head of department working for a government, I want to know which buildings would need to make priority investments in energy efficiency, so that I have a cost-assessment and reliable information in the context of each building.
Story 3	As an ambitious head of department working for a local municipality, I want to know which buildings would need to make priority investments in energy efficiency, so that I can know which is the best refurbishment solution for each building

Persona: **Project manager**

Story 1	As a project manager working for a government institution, I want to know how to manage energy consumption in buildings effectively, so that I can translate these energy savings into economic ones and establish the investment terms and their recovery.
Story 2	As a project manager working for a local municipality, I want to spend time as little as possible managing energy consumption in buildings, so that I focus on different responsibilities. Energy efficiency is important, but sometimes it just takes too much time.
Story 3	As a project manager working for a local municipality, I want energy consumption data to be recorded on a regular basis, so that I can be sure that the results set out in the project have been achieved without financial corrections.

Persona: **Responsible facility manager**

Story 1	As a facility manager managing the governmental building, I want to be sure which investments in energy efficiency will be the most efficient or most needed, so that I know which is the best refurbishment solution for each building.
Story 2	As a facility manager managing private business buildings, I want to be sure which investments in energy efficiency will be the most efficient or most needed, so that I can translate these energy savings into economic ones and establish the investment terms and their recovery.
Story 3	As a facility manager managing local school premises, I want to be sure which investments in energy efficiency will be the most efficient or most needed, so that I know with predictions what will be the energy savings in the future.

Persona: **Careless manager**

Story 1	As a facility manager managing the governmental building, I want to make decisions quickly and without spending a lot of time analyzing information, so that I know which is the best refurbishment solution for each building.
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Story 2	As a facility manager managing the governmental building, I want to make decisions quickly and without spending a lot of time analyzing information, so that I can know with predictions what will be the energy savings.
Story 3	As a facility manager managing the governmental building, I want to make decisions quickly and without spending a lot of time analyzing information, so that I can translate these energy savings into economic ones and establish the investment terms and their recovery.

Persona:	Informed policy maker
Story 1	As a policy maker working for a government institution, I want to have a sufficient understanding or supporting information of the energy efficiency situation in the state or local government, so that I can translate these energy savings into economic ones and establish the investment terms and their recovery.
Story 2	As a policy maker working for a government institution, I want to have a sufficient understanding or supporting information of the energy efficiency situation in the state or local government, so that I know which building is the priority for investments
Story 3	As a policy maker working for a government institution, I want to have a sufficient understanding or supporting information of the energy efficiency situation in the state or local government, so that I know with predictions what will be the energy savings.

5.2.9 Pilot 9

5.2.9.1 Use Case 14: AI for improved Energy Performance Certificates Reliability

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 9 [FAEN - Spain]

Persona: Policy makers in charge of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)

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|----------------|---|
| Story 1 | As a Policy maker in charge of managing EPCs working in the Energy Performance Certification Official Register I want to improve the quality of the EPCs so that , I will increase my confidence in them. |
| Story 2 | As a Policy maker in charge of managing EPCs working in the Energy Performance Certification Official Register I want to obtain a quality checking tool so that , I will obtain a more efficient and automatic way to do the verification. |
| Story 3 | As a Policy maker in charge of managing EPCs working in the Energy Performance Certification Official Register I want to improve the EPC reception and management so that , I will save time and ease the data management work. |

Persona: Policy makers in charge of energy retrofitting strategies

- | | |
|----------------|---|
| Story 1 | As a Policy maker in charge of planning and designing the public strategies for the energy retrofitting of buildings, I want to obtain an energetic characterization of the stock of buildings so that I will obtain a good vision of its current state. |
| Story 2 | As a Policy maker in charge of planning and designing the public strategies for the energy retrofitting of buildings, I want to obtain a better vision of the need for energy improvements plans so that I will obtain a reliable tool to help in the planning of the actions related to the improvement of energy performance in buildings. |
| Story 3 | As a Policy maker in charge of planning and designing the public strategies for the energy retrofitting of buildings, I want to obtain a more effective allocation of funds for the energy rehabilitation of buildings so that I will comply with the national /European energy efficiency commitments in buildings. |

5.2.9.2 Use Case 15: AI for predicting the climate change impact in RES and energy demand at regional (local) level

Name: AI for predicting the climate change impact in RES and energy demand at regional (local) level

Pilot No. 9 [FAEN - Spain]

Persona: Fundación Asturiana de la Energía (FAEN)

- | | |
|----------------|---|
| Story 1 | As the Regional Energy Agency, work in the planning of renewable energy strategies at the regional level, I want to know the potential of solar radiation in the different areas (taking into account climate change effects in renewable energy sources) So that I can better plan the exploitation of renewable energy resources in Asturias. |
|----------------|---|

5.3 APPENDIX III - Services to be developed

5.3.1 Service 1

Name (Service name)	
Visual analytics dashboard for electricity consumption centers	

Scope and objective of Service

Scope	The service provides a visual dashboard for data related to electricity consumption centres such as EV charging stations and buildings.
Objective	Present data related to electricity demand in building and EV charging stations in user-friendly way. Focus is placed on spatial representation. Demand centres are represented as points on a map and user can access data through cards on the map and demand centre specific dashboards.
Related Usage Scenario	5.1, 5.2, 5.3, & 5.4
Pilot	Pilot 5 Heron SA and Parity Platform

Narrative of the service

The service enables owners of charging stations and building administrators to monitor the electricity consumption of their assets in real-time. The service receives data related to demand centres indirectly via appropriate webhooks or directly via WebSocket connection to the IoT device. Through a front-end dashboard building administrators and owners of charging stations can identify their assets on the map and receive information concisely through icons and colour grading that update in real-time to match the status of the asset. They can quickly review data across the range of their assets through the map environment or aggregated list. Detailed information will be available through asset specific dashboards.

Type of service - implementation specifics

Online/offline	Online
Execution frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time status and dashboard updates
Developing language	Python Django, React, Redux
Connections	Specify ALL internal and external connections <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connection to building administrator, energy provider or charge point operator web hooks Connecting directly to IoT devices via WebSocket protocol.
Licence type	Proprietary

Data requirements	
Input data	<p>Specify all input data needed for the service and the period e.g.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data from building smart meters <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. 10 min update intervals b. Timestamp c. Device status (available, operating, offline, fault) d. Capacity (in kW) e. KWh in the current session. f. Device type g. location 2. Historical data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. On request via the online platform by specifying date and asset b. Duration and kWh per past session c. End reason for past sessions
Output data	<p>Description of the service output (check input data for examples)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spatial representation of energy demand centres in dynamic map with relevant visual information (status, capacity level) 2. Real-time status dashboard in a web environment for each asset 3. Past session visualization
Hyperparameters	<p>List of the hyperparameters within the tool that the app user can modify to adapt the service to its specific use case.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Map sandbox limits (to specify specific area scrollable in the map to match locations of specific use case assets) 2. Update intervals for building data (Range 3 min – 60 min)

5.3.2 Service 2

Name (Service name)	
Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres	

Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	The service provides real-time data related to electricity consumption centres and specifically EV charging stations via WebSocket connection protocol.
Objective	Efficiently manage EV charging stations and integrate variable pricing to incentivize drivers at specific intervals (low charging station occupancy)
Related Usage Scenario	5.1, 5.2, 5.3 & 5.4
Pilot	Pilot 5 Heron SA and Parity Platform

Narrative of the service	
<p>The service enables owners of charging stations and charge point operators to monitor charging station operation in real-time. The service connects to the EV charging station via WebSocket and receives status updates in 10-sec intervals. Through a front-end dashboard, owners of charging stations monitor the operation of the charging stations. They can quickly review whether the charging station is occupied, charging or offline. Data for running sessions are also provided. Historical data can also be accessed per charging station. Data related to upcoming charging reservations in specific charging stations are also visualized in the dashboards. The service also draws wholesale price data in hourly intervals from Heron SA webhook. Based on these input data, the service also proposes pricing changes to the charging station owner in hourly intervals. For example, for hourly intervals with low wholesale energy price and low projected station occupancy, a significant price reduction in cost per kWh will be proposed to the charging station owner to attract EV drivers.</p>	

Type of service - implementation specifics	
Online/offline	Online
Execution frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time status updates Hourly pricing proposals
Developing language	Python Django, React, Redux
Connections	Specify ALL internal and external connections <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connection to DB of EV charging stations (EV Loader application) PostgreSQL Connecting to external service (grid-related data such as wholesale price provided by Heron SA)
Licence type	Proprietary

Data requirements	
Input data	<p>Specify all input data needed for the service and the period e.g.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data from EV charging stations. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Real-time status update b. 10-sec update intervals c. Timestamp d. Charging station status (available, occupied, charging, fault, finishing) e. Charging capacity (in kW) f. KWh charged in the current session. 2. Historical data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. On request via the online platform by specifying the date and charging stations b. Duration and kWh per past session c. End reason for past sessions 3. Date for upcoming reservations in specific charging stations provided by EV Loader (when applicable) 4. Wholesale energy price data from Heron SA in hourly intervals
Output data	<p>Description of the service output (check input data for examples)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Real-time status dashboard in a web environment for each station 2. Past session visualization 3. Proposed cost per kWh for each charging station based on input data in hourly intervals 4. Classification of charging stations (home charging, public AC, public DC)
Hyperparameters	<p>List of the hyperparameters within the tool that the app user can modify to adapt the service to its specific use case.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Grid data source webhook

5.3.3 Service 3

Name (Service name)	
Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement	
Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	Enhancement of data reliability of the Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) through checking, geo-referenced information, as well as coherence and comparison analyses.
Objective	Data from EPCs will be more reliable and management of EPCs will be optimised through an automatic and efficient manner to check data.
Related Usage Scenario	14.1, 14.2 & 14.3
Pilot	FAEN (Use Case 14)
Narrative of the service	
<p>EPCs will increase their reliability through improvement in the certificates' identification, location (geo-referenced information), increasing the data reliability by checking data (for possible errors), checking the coherence of the EPC (analysing if the letter of the certificate is in line with the information of the building) and comparing the EPC data with other sources to make an additional check.</p> <p>Service input:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Historical EPCs data from Asturias region (in xml) • Cadastral data (in GML) <p>Service output:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data checker 2. Geo-reference & information added from the cadastre 3. EPC coherence 4. EPC comparison 	
Type of service - implementation specifics	
Online/offline	Online
Execution frequency	The execution frequency of the service is on-demand, depending on when the analysis of EPCs wants to be performed / reports want to be generated.
Developing language	To be defined
Connections	To be defined
Licence type	Proprietary
Data requirements	
Input data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Cadastral data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. On-demand b. N/A c. Timestamp, Voltages per phase, Active and Reactive power 2. Energy Performance Certificate data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Once per request b. N/A c. +200 variables
Output data	Report generated once per execution
Hyperparameters	To be defined

5.3.4 Service 4

Name (Service name)
Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation

Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	The service will exploit the data contained in energy performance certificates in the Asturias region in order to support decision-making around the building stock in this region.
Objective	Support the decision-making at the regional level (Asturias region) by providing a better understanding of building stock status that will allow a better design of building energy retrofiting plans and strategies.
Related Usage Scenario	14.4, 14.5 & 14.6
Pilot	FAEN (Use Case 14)

Narrative of the service	
The exploitation of data contained in the EPCs of the Asturias region will support the decision-making around building stock. It will be built upon service “Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement”, after having enhanced the reliability of the EPC data.	
Service input:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Historical EPCs data from Asturias region (in XML) 	
Service operation:	
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Exploit information from certificates – analyse the data contained inside XMLs to extract knowledge of the building stock (specific data to be defined > to be decided) Infer information to the other buildings where we do not have certificates 	
Service output:	
Reports exported for the ministry / for their own use (FAEN, Asturias regional government)	

Type of service - implementation specifics	
Online/offline	Online
Execution frequency	The execution frequency of the service is on-demand, depending on when the analysis of EPCs wants to be performed / reports want to be generated.
Developing language	To be defined
Connections	To be defined
Licence type	Proprietary

Data requirements	
Input data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Weather data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> On-demand and historical 1 hour Temperature (other to be defined) Cadastral data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> On-demand N/A Timestamp, Voltages per phase, Active and Reactive power Energy Performance Certificate data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Once per request N/A +200 variables
Output data	Report generated once per execution

Hyperparameters	To be defined
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5.3.5 Service 5

Name (Service name)

Climate change solar radiation forecasting

Scope and objective of Service

Scope	Forecasting of Solar radiation
Objective	Forecast the Solar radiation received in the Asturias region for the prediction of its mid to long-term potential under different RPC scenarios that represents the impacts of climate change.
Related Usage Scenario	15.1
Pilot	FAEN (Use Case 15)

Narrative of the service

Forecast of Solar radiation plays an important role in planning the future deployment of renewable sources in an effective manner, also contemplating the effects of climate change through the assessment of vulnerabilities that may arise from them. The solar radiation will be predicted in terms of mid and long-term potential from weather stations data, Copernicus C3S and knowledge from studies of Climate Change effects in solar energy.

Service input:

- Historical solar radiation data (from regional weather stations) and other climate data (e.g. temperature).
- Regional weather forecast.
- PVGIS historical isolation (satellite) to complete historical datasets at weather stations.
- Copernicus C3S data from climate change in solar radiation.
- Copernicus CAMS data (SoDA) to calibrate bias adjust solar radiation data. Turbidity and atmosphere composition to obtain clear sky calculations.
- Digital surface model (DSM) to calculate landscape slope and aspects.

Service output: medium- and long-term prediction of the solar radiation considering the specificities of Asturias at different spatial and temporal resolution.

Type of service - implementation specifics

Online/offline	Online
Execution frequency	The execution frequency of the service is on-demand (daily or monthly by default), depending on when the analysis of solar radiation wants to be performed / policies or strategies want to be planned.
Developing language	Python and R
Connections	To be defined
Licence type	Proprietary

Data requirements	
Input data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Historical solar radiation data (from regional weather stations) and other climate data (e.g. temperature). <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. On-demand b. Radiation data: hourly or daily c. Temperature: hourly or daily 2. Regional weather forecast. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. On-demand b. Hourly data at 3 forecast days 3. PVGIS historical isolation (satellite) to complete historical datasets at weather stations <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. On-demand b. Radiation data: hourly or daily c. Temperature: hourly or daily 4. Copernicus C3S data from climate change in solar radiation <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. 3h, 6h, daily, monthly and seasonal 2m mean temperature. b. 3h, 6h, daily, monthly and seasonal surface solar radiation downward. 5. Copernicus CAMS data (SoDA) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Radiation data: hourly or daily b. Temperature: hourly or daily 6. Digital surface model to calculate slope and aspects <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. On-demand b. Static data c. Turbidity of the atmosphere
Output data	Medium- and long-term prediction of the solar radiation considering the specificities of Asturias.
Hyperparameters	To be defined

5.3.6 Service 6

Name (Service name)	
Digital Twin: DER simulation for supporting system level scenario evaluation	
Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	This service will build a digital replica of the grid and its assets to support system-level scenario evaluation online or offline.
Objective	The digital twin replica of the electrical grid and its assets will be simulated using DPsim. By providing the digital twin, further services will be enabled to carry out grid analysis for evaluating the impacts on the grid when planning to introduce new solutions.
Related Usage Scenario	UC 7, Usage scenario 3.2, 3.5 (ASM)
Pilot	ASM Terni: UC8 - Flexibility assessment - Analyse distribution network flexibility potential- Based on forecasts regarding distribution network generation, storage and consumption, together with the knowledge of the network topology and the device's flexibility options

Narrative of the service

For the derivation of flexibility schedules with the goal of mitigating problematic grid situations, the constraints from the grid need to be taken into account. For this, a digital twin of the grid and its assets is made available. The service will allow for grid analysis , e.g. for a better understanding of the anticipated grid congestion situation. This can be combined with a flexibility analysis to achieve a holistic view of both energy distribution and grid situation.

The service is realized by the simulation software DPsim.

Input requirements:

- o Static data: Network topology
- o Static data: Specification of assets
- o Measured data: Smart meter data from assets

Service operation:

The DPsim supports both electromagnetic transient and dynamic phasor simulation. A power flow solver will carry out computation on the assets' static, dynamic and IoT data during the simulation. The DPsim can load models in the IEC61970 common information model (CIM).

Service output:

Service output is a digital replica of the grid topology and power flow situation. Further analysis can be derived from this simulation in combination with other services (e.g. flexibility or congestion analysis/forecast).

Type of service - implementation specifics

Online/offline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online • Offline
Execution frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time • On-Demand
Developing language	E.g. Python, C/C++
Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection to individual assets via smart meters
Licence type	Open-source

Data requirements	
Input data	Specify all input data needed for the service and the period e.g. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Static data: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Asset specification, e.g. line/transformer parameters, the capacity of storage components b. Asset Location data c. Network Topology d. CIM data can be read directly by DPsim, avoiding the manual entry of data 2. Electrical data of assets through smart meters <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Real-time b. 15 min c. Timestamp, Voltages and current per phase, Active and Reactive power, loading
Output data	Description of the service output <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Simulation of grid partition
Hyperparameters	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Grid partition to be considered

5.3.7 Service 7

Name (Service name)	
Predictive Maintenance Analytics	
Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	Analyse asset to derive predictive maintenance.
Objective	Development of innovative portfolio maintenance to reduce operational infrastructure costs.
Related Usage Scenario	Use Case 1, 4, 6, Usage Scenario 6.1, 6.2 (ASM)
Pilot	1, 3, 4

Narrative of the service

Variant a:

Based on operational data acquired from DER devices such as PV, as well as historical data on replaced

- Service input requirements:
 - Static data: Asset specification
 - Static data: Asset Location data
 - Static data: Network topology
 - Measured data: Loading data
 - Measured data: Voltage and current data
 - Measured data: weather-related data
 - Historical data: historical interruptions
- service operation
 - Derivation of PV plant health state
 - Unavailability analysis, Statistical extrapolation of interruptions
- service output
 - Proposal of predictive maintenance

Variant b:

Circuit breakers are associated with several recorded operations (mainly trips due to faults and switching operations), mainly represented as COMTRADE files for the oscillography representation. For each incident there are a list of recorded of analog and digital channels, recorded in the protection systems. These time series contain many subjacent information that can be useful for asset management departments to gain better insights from incidents and fuel predictive maintenance plans.

This service aims to use the features extracted from this incident data, to optimize predictive maintenance techniques of assets.

- Service input requirements:
 - Historical data: historical COMTRADE record data
 - Static data: Asset specification
 - Measured data: Voltage and current channel data from oscillographies
 - Measured data: weather-related and fires-related data
- Service operation
 - Classify/Typify incident fault types
 - Identify assets in need for maintenance activities
 - Cluster incidents based on relevance
 - Correlate incidents with external causes
- Service output
 - Derivation of improved maintenance plan based on developed data processing and analytics models

Variant c:

Based on operational data acquired from the power grid, as well as historical data on replaced

- Service input requirements:
 - Static data: Asset specification
 - Static data: Asset Location data
 - Static data: Network topology
 - Measured data: Loading data
 - Measured data: Voltage and current data
 - Measured data: weather-related data
 - Historical data: historical interruptions
- service operation
 - Derivation of electrical transformers health state
 - Derivation of electrical power lines health state
 - Unavailability analysis, Statistical extrapolation of faults
- service output
 - Proposal of predictive maintenance

Type of service - implementation specifics	
Online/offline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offline for historical data extrapolation • Online for measured data
Execution frequency	Options to select <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Periodically (bi-monthly for predictive maintenance without the occurrence of abnormal events) • In addition On-demand (if certain value > threshold, immediate maintenance) •
Developing language	TBD
Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connecting to internal service: weather data (current) • Connecting to internal meters • Connecting to incident data acquisition systems
Licence type	TBD

Data requirements	
Input data	<p>Variant a and c:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Weather data (once per day 15 min interval (time UTC,)) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Specify period: probably once per day is sufficient b. The granularity of data or time resolution: report of max and min during the day c. Quantities: temperature, irradiation 2. Static data: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Asset specification, e.g. line/transformer parameters b. Asset Location data c. Network topology 3. Electrical data of assets <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Real-time

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. 15 min c. Timestamp, Voltages per phase, Active and Reactive power, loading <p>4. Historical data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Once per request b. 24 hours c. Timestamp, outage nr and duration <p>Variant b:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. COMTRADE fault record data, composed of one .CFG and .DAT files per incident <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. When there is a CB tripping incident b. Includes at least 3 voltage analog channels and 3 current analog channels 2. Weather data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Resolution tbd b. Temperature (°C), Storm occurrences, etc.
Output data	<p>Description of the service output (check input data for examples)</p> <p>Variant a and c:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Report on the health state of assets <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generated once per execution b. Assessment of health state 2. Report on extrapolation of interruptions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generated once per execution b. Purely statistical analysis 3. Proposal of predictive maintenance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Based on the two reports above b. Optionally including information on the impact of potential failure. <p>Variant b:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Report on assets to be maintained <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generated once per execution b. Insights and visualisations of incidents, with incident type classification and information on how asset responded (response times, such as fault clearance time) 2. Report on the Priority list of asset maintenance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generated once per execution b. Insights and visualisations of vulnerabilities per asset 3. Report on the association to external causes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generated once per execution b. Insights and visualisations to explain the association with external incidents
Hyperparameters	<p>List of the hyperparameters within the tool that the app user can modify to adapt the service to its specific use case.</p> <p>Variant a and c:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Threshold for asset loading (%) 2. Threshold for temperature min/max (°C) 3. Threshold for voltage (V) 4. Threshold for performance ratio <p>Variant b:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Thresholds for asset operation

	<ol style="list-style-type: none">2. Fault identification system thresholds3. Metrics to be extracted from COMTRADE files
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5.3.8 Service 8

Name (Service name)	
Measurement and verification of energy savings	

Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	Methodology compliant with the International Performance Measurement and Verification Protocol (IPMVP)
Objective	Establishes the basis to guarantee that savings on energy and economic terms are correctly measured /estimated
Related Usage Scenario	4.1, 4.2*, 4.3*, 4.4*, 4.5*, 4.6*, 4.7*, 4.8*, 4.9*, 4.10, 4.11 *to be confirmed
Pilot	Pilot 2 (VEOLIA) – Use case 4: AI for energy-saving verification service, increasing the trust on Energy Performance Contracts

Narrative of the service

The service follows the IPMVP protocol and establishes a workflow to measure and verify energy and economic savings after renovation/installation of energy efficiency measures in buildings. It gives the users the possibility to demonstrate these savings.

Input requirements:

Users must indicate to the service the energy efficiency measures that are going to be installed on the building and validated by the IPMVP service. Independent variables and static factors have to be defined in the service as well. Energy reference data from the building before the renovation is needed in order to define the mathematical model.

Service operation:

The service follows the IPMVP and establishes a workflow to measure and identify energy and economic savings after renovation/installation of energy efficiency measures in buildings. It gives the users the possibility to demonstrate these savings. Depending on the inputs given by the user, the service decides/offers the user which is the most accurate option of the IPMVP (A, B, C or D).

Depending on the previous result (mainly in case C), the service will calculate a mathematical model of the building behaviour before the intervention. (Options A and B usually do not need to calculate mathematical models, and option D uses other kind of non-mathematical models but simulation models instead, such as energy+ or TRNSYS models).

Once the building is renovated (including the Energy efficiency measures), the service will receive reporting period data (energy and independent variables; changes in static factors) and will provide the user with the energy/economic savings.

The service is used firstly to introduce data and configure some relevant parameters, secondly to calculate energy models, and then after the intervention is used to calculate savings periodically.

Service output: Service outputs are the measurement and verification plans and the savings reports after renovation/installation of energy efficiency measures. These results can be shown directly in the service, and/or included in a report (.pdf, .docx, .xlsx, etc).

Type of service - implementation specifics	
Online/offline	Online
Execution frequency	On-demand
Developing language	.NET (preliminarily)
Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection to VEOLIA'S DB [to be defined specifically how]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection to external service: weather database [to be determined which] • Other to be defined • Input data through files (.xlsx, .csv, .json, others) [to be determined in case] • Web Forms to introduce some data and configurations.
Licence type	Proprietary

Data requirements

Input data	<p>Specify all input data needed for the service and the period e.g.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Weather data (once per day 15 min interval (time UTC,)) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Period: once per day (to be confirmed) b. Granularity; 5 min, 15 min (to be confirmed) c. Temperature, Humidity, (other variables to be checked) 2. Smart meter data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Real-time b. 1 min, 5 min, 15 min, once per day in case of energy, to be defined c. Timestamp, Voltages per phase, Active and Reactive power, energy consumption 3. Historical data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Once per request 4. Configuration of relevant variables (independent variables). 5. Selection of the desired option from the IPMVP
Output data	<p>Description of the service output (check input data for examples)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. M&V plan 2. Report <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generated once per execution b. Not applicable c. Estimated Energy Savings
Hyperparameters	<p>List of the hyperparameters within the tool that the app user can modify to adapt the service to its specific use case. Some examples:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nominal power [kW] 2. Location [longitude, latitude] 3. Time zone 4. Optimization setting

5.3.9 Service 9

Name (Service name)	
Energy flexibility forecasting	

Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	Energy flexibility forecasting
Objective	Flexibility forecasting for DR optimisation at grid asset level on day ahead timeframe.
Related Usage Scenario	Use cases (11, 12) Use case 7 Usage scenario 3.2, 3.5, 3.7, 3.8 Use case 8, Usage scenario 3.10, 3.11 Use Case 11, Usage scenario 6.1
Pilot	Pilot 3 (Pilot 6, Pilot 7)

Narrative of the service

Flexibility forecasting is one of the pillars of DR programs. Flexibility aggregators require prior knowledge and estimations of the flexibility functions that characterise different clusters of prosumers (households, buildings, districts) according to their load types/profiles, in order to enable their participation in flexibility schemes with dynamic load management. Such predictions can serve DSO requests for flexibility while it also enables the efficient cost allocation of TSOs by reducing congestions and reverse power flows. In terms of sustainability, flexibility forecasting can facilitate economic benefit optimization, energy consumption reduction and GHG emissions reduction, always based on the criteria that drive the forecasts.

Service input

- Historical time series of energy demand and generation at the points of interest of the grid
- Timestamps of demand response signals (if automated flexibility schemes are already implemented through dedicated controllers)
- Real-time energy demand and generation forecasts
- Grid topology and grid asset characteristics.
- Different flexibility types, preferences of flexibility providers

Service operation

- Extract discrete flexibility clusters – Inference via load profile characteristics and/or consumer data.
- Produce optimised day ahead flexibility schedules through ML/DL/Timeseries models

Service output

- Day Ahead flexibility forecasts

Type of service - implementation specifics

Online/offline	Online / Offline
Execution frequency	Options to select <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Daily
Developing language	Python and/or R
Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection to I-ENERGY harmonised database, or pilot partner's database • Connection with demand/generation forecasting service
Licence type	TBD

Data requirements

Input data	<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Historical time series of energy demand and generation at the points of interest of the grid2. Timestamps of demand response signals (if automated flexibility schemes are already implemented through dedicated controllers)3. Real-time energy demand and generation forecasts4. Grid topology and grid asset characteristics.5. Different flexibility types, preferences of flexibility providers
Output data	Flexibility schemes/schedules for one day ahead
Hyperparameters	Flexibility sources to be considered in the schedule

5.3.10 Service 10

Name (Service name)	
Energy load/consumption/demand forecasting	

Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	Forecast of energy load/consumption/demand on a day-ahead timeframe
Objective	Increase efficiency and cost allocation of TSOs, using AI-based tools to increase the load forecast predictive capabilities, essential to internal processes of a TSO. Facilitate economic benefit optimization, energy consumption reduction and GHG emissions reduction.
Related Usage Scenario	Use cases 2, 3, 5, 7, 11 and 12 Use Case 6, Usage scenario 3.1, 3.4 Use Case 7, Usage scenario 3.2, 3.5 Use Case 8, usage scenario 3.3 Use Case 11, Usage scenario 6.1
Pilot	Pilot 1, Pilot 2, Pilot 3, Pilot 6, Pilot 7

Narrative of the service

Service input	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time series data for net load External data like weather data more inputs pertinent to energy consumption (e.g. location, geometry) based on pilot specific requirements 	
service operation	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Predict net load one day ahead through ML models suitable for time-series predictions, using one or multiple (ensemble) approaches 	
service output	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Day Ahead net load prediction 	

Type of service - implementation specifics

Online/offline	Online time-series data Historical time-series data
Execution frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Daily
Developing language	Python and/or R
Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connection to I-ENERGY harmonised database, or pilot partner's database Connection with external weather services
Licence type	To be defined

Data requirements

Input data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Weather data and day-ahead weather forecast Time series net load/consumption/demand historical and real-time data
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Output data	Predicted net load/consumption/demand for one day ahead
Hyperparameters	none

5.3.11 Service 11

Name (Service name)

AI for energy demand prediction to optimise DHN operation

Scope and objective of Service

Scope	Optimal operation planning based on energy use forecasting.
Objective	The objective is to reduce operation cost and non-renewable energy use.
Related Usage Scenario	3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.6, 3.7, 3.8, 3.9, 3.10 & 3.15
Pilot	Pilot 2 [VEOLIA] UC3: AI for energy demand prediction to optimise District Heating Network Operation

Narrative of the service

The service provides estimations of future values of the energy demanded by the DHN. The forecasts are generated on a regular basis and the forecasting horizon can be up to 24 hours. The inputs needed by the service are weather forecasts, past energy demand values and other data like calendar day.

Type of service - implementation specifics

Online/offline	Online
Execution frequency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Periodically. Between 1 minute and 1 hour, depending on inputs sampling frequency.
Developing language	Python. Alternatively, R.
Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connection to DB where past use of energy is stored. Connecting to the weather forecast.
Licence type	Proprietary

Data requirements

Input data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Weather data Historical data Calendar data
Output data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Future values of the energy demanded by the DHN that can be used by other service.
Hyperparameters	To be defined

5.3.12 Service 12

Name (Service name)	
Optimization of the production mix	

Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	Match the demand to the generation for multi-energy systems decision-support.
Objective	Increase in energy efficiency and increase the ROI.
Related Usage Scenario	5.1, 5.2, 5.3, 5.6 & 5.11, ... [TBC]
Pilot	Pilot 2 (VEOLIA) - Use Case 5: AI for multi-energy systems decision-support.

Narrative of the service	
<p>Through a better understanding of how the facility operates, the production mix can be optimized and the efficiency will increase.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service input requirements <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Static data: Asset specification, e.g. energy sources ○ Static data: Asset Location data ○ Measured data: Weather forecast data ○ Historical data: production mix ○ Historical data: Weather data • Service operation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Depending on the inputs, the service offers the user which is the most efficient/a set of possible production mix option/s. • Service output <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Proposal of production mix schedule 	

Type of service - implementation specifics	
Online/offline	Online
Execution frequency	Periodically (daily)
Developing language	Python, C/C++, Matlab, ...
Connections	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection to DB (type of connection, which DB) • Connecting to external service: weather forecast, • Connecting to another I-ENERGY service (specify which)
Licence type	Proprietary

Data requirements	
Input data	<p>Specify all input data needed for the service and the period e.g.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Weather data (once per day 15 min interval (time UTC,)) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Specify period (e.g. Once per day, on-demand triggered by Service X, event,...) b. The granularity of data or time resolution (e.g. 1s, 1min, 15min, not applicable for reports) c. Quantities 2. BEMS data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Real-time b. Data frequency: 15 min 3. Historical data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a.
Output data	To be defined
Hyperparameters	<p>List of the hyperparameters within the tool that the app user can modify to adapt the service to its specific use case.</p> <p>Some examples:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Nominal power [kW] 2. Location [longitude, latitude] 3. Time zone 4. Optimization setting

5.3.13 Service 13

Name (Service name)

I-ENERGY Virtual Workbench – Marketplace (catalogue of ML models and Data sources to facilitate the creation of new application)

Scope and objective of Service

Scope	Provide a tool that will help in building new services based on distributed data and AI models.
Objective	This tool will provide SMEs, developers and potential innovators a graphical interface that will facilitate the development of new applications based on the existing data sets and the available set of the developed and trained models being produced by I-ENERGY. The tool will allow to select the specific algorithms/models among a set of available ones (classification via ML, correlation, feature extraction) and the type of analytic to be executed (descriptive, predictive, prescriptive). The library of reusable AI-based ML models will be made available to the Marketplace with a view to promote quick adaptation and reuse of ML models along with different contexts.
Related Usage Scenario	Use Case 7, Usage scenario 3.6, 3.7 (ASM)
Pilot	Pilot 3

Narrative of the service

The I-ENERGY Marketplace will be a PaaS, address developers and stakeholders interested in creating new services for the building sector.

The I-ENERGY Marketplace will provide a user interface that will help in building new services based on distributed data and AI models. In this line, the I-ENERGY Marketplace will expose the different data sources, via the distributed storage mechanisms and will enable their selection for feeding the data processing layer. On top of the selected data, the marketplace will provide access to the Training Models Library and will ease the model configuration and calibration by providing estimation on their accuracy and performance.

Type of service - implementation specifics

Online/offline	Online/offline
Execution frequency	Options to select <ul style="list-style-type: none"> On-demand
Developing language	
Connections	Specify ALL internal and external connections <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connection to I-ENERGY harmonised database, or pilot partner's database
Licence type	Open-source

Data requirements

Input data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data from the data service layer based on the ML models needs
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Output data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generated once per execution as a result of the ML models algorithms
Hyperparameters	

5.3.14 Service 14

Name (Service name)	
Activity recognition and forecasting	
Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	Recognizing the activity of the user and forecasting its activity according to its typical behaviour.
Objective	Creates activity schedules of the Citizens according to its typical behaviour.
Related Usage Scenario	US11.x US12.x TBD UC 7, Usage scenario 3.6, 3.7, 3.8 (ASM) UC 8, Usage scenario 3.3 (ASM)
Pilot	Pilot 3, Pilot 6 and Pilot 7

Narrative of the service

The Citizen's activity is one of the most important parameters that determine the flexibility of the demand response activity. By grouping the loads, we are able to create the activity schemes. The service will also perform clustering to group citizens with the same behaviour, creating a virtual community. Additionally, with clustering, anonymization will be enabled.

Service input is the labelled data from the NILM service.

Service output is the Activity schedule of the citizen.

Type of service - implementation specifics

Online/offline	offline
Execution frequency	Options to select <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Once a day
Developing language	TBD
Connections	Specify ALL internal and external connections For example <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Connection to SM Connecting to DB for input and output
Licence type	TBD

Data requirements	
Input data	Specify all input data needed for the service and the period e.g. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Disaggregated data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Once to few times a day b. ~1 s c. Time, Labelled data 2. National calendar <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Once a day b. daily c. days of the week, holidays
Output data	Description of the service output (check input data for examples) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Report <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generated once per day b. Not applicable c. Schedule of the activity (Activity, timestamp, estimated Energy used)
Hyperparameters	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Database of citizens

5.3.15 Service 15

Name (Service name)	
Anomalous behaviour detection	
Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	From the Labeled smart meter data, the service detects anomalies in the citizen patterns and reporting them.
Objective	Detecting unexpected behaviour of Citizen.
Related Usage Scenario	US11.x US12.x TBD UC 8, Usage scenario 3.10, 3.11 (ASM)
Pilot	Pilot 3, Pilot 6 and Pilot 7
Narrative of the service	
<p>The Citizen's activity is one of the most important parameters that can be detected using a disaggregation algorithm and creating on top auxiliary services that can improve ambient assisting living, especial in the domain of resident care. By monitoring the typical behaviour of the Citizens, their specific profiles can be defined. The service will determine if the citizen profile is in the expected margins, otherwise, it will trigger the new event, which can be exploited for security, triggering remote or local assistance or any other action.</p> <p>Service input is the labelled data from the NILM service. Service output labelled anomalies.</p>	
Type of service - implementation specifics	
Online/offline	online
Execution frequency	Options to select <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time
Developing language	TBD
Connections	Specify ALL internal and external connections For example <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connection to SM • Connecting to DB for historical input output
Licence type	TBD
Data requirements	
Input data	Specify all input data needed for the service and the period e.g. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Disaggregated data <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Once to few times a day b. ~1 s c. Time, Labelled data 2. National calendar <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Once a day b. daily c. days of the week, holidays
Output data	Description of the service output (check input data for examples) <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Report <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. Generated once per execution (~1h) b. Not applicable c. Anomaly (Label, timestamp)

Hyperparameters	1. Database of citizens
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5.3.16 Service 16

Name (Service name)	
Blockchain Hybrid energy data storage	
Scope and objective of Service	
Scope	The service leverage blockchain to enable secure, trusted and flexible data sharing for B2B cross-stakeholders. It can be modelled over a private permissioned blockchain in which each prosumer can manage energy data.
Objective	Blockchain has been identified as a potential game-changer enabling technology, with a promising level of maturity, Blockchain Hybrid approaches for data storage minimise the costs and assure the necessary scaling up. Distributed databases and off-chain approach used to improve the storage capabilities without losing the advantages provided by a distributed system.
Related Usage Scenario	UC7 (maybe UC8)
Pilot	Pilot 3

Narrative of the service

Our solution will combine the *on-chain* data storage together with distributed databases for *off-chain* data storage according to a hybrid approach. In order to minimize the amount of data to be stored on the blockchain, raw data from the data sources will be stored using a distributed database: the blockchain will be then used periodically to store a fixed-length hash of the data received in the last time interval. The hybrid approach combines the scalability of a distributed NoSQL database with the blockchain, making tampering attempts evident, enabling provenance tracking, non-repudiability, and the use of self-enforcing smart contracts.

Each data source will be connected to a gateway, an embedded device that takes care of pre-processing, calculating digital fingerprints, and storing the data off-chain. A private network based on Ethereum will be used as a blockchain network. The Ethereum nodes provide the networking capabilities and the rules needed to determine consensus among them. The private network will be used as a platform for running smart contracts and register data with a timestamp.

Thanks to dedicated APIs, every node in the network can be queried and it is possible to build dedicated applications on top of this stack for monitoring the process, validating the off-chain data against the data stored on-chain, provide limited access for auditing purposes, or provide even finer-grained access to specific users for specific purposes, interacting with smart contracts deployed in the network.

The service will support the insertion of new data, the retrieval of previously stored data, and the validation/notarization of the data stored in the database by comparing its hash with the one recorded on the blockchain. The hashing mechanism will be known as a priori, so it will be possible also to validate the inserted data autonomously.

Type of service - implementation specifics	
Online/offline	Online
Execution frequency	The service module will collect data with a frequency of 3 minutes or lower.
Developing language	The services will be implemented with Solidity and based on the Ethereum decentralized platform
Connections	The Ethereum nodes provide the networking capabilities and the rules needed to determine consensus among them. The private network will be used as a platform for running smart contracts and register data with a timestamp.
Licence type	Proprietary, with the usage of some third-parties licenses embedded inside the solutions developed

Data requirements	
Input data	Smart meter data: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. timestamp, power, voltage, frequency 2. 3 min granularity
Output data	Notarization service receipt: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Request status (OK/KO) 2. Data hash 3. Data reference ("key" used for querying data on distributed DB) 4. Block/Tx ID
Hyperparameters	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Execution frequency

5.4 APPENDIX IV - Data

5.4.1 Pilot 1

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No. 1 [RDN/REN - Portugal]

Historical Data available	
Short data description	Examples: 1. Historical COMTRADE data, which includes, per incident observation: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A configuration file • A data file include oscillography time series
System providing information	SCADA
Data Format and information model	ASCII and Binary text file, structured according to COMTRADE IEEE standard. Data processing and feature extraction work is needed to process this data
Suggested communication protocol	-
Number of data sources	Unknown
Granularity	Varies
Time window	At least 4 years
Nature of data	Sensitive

Live Data available	
Short data description	-
Data source	-
Data Format and information model	-
Suggested communication protocol	-
Number of data sources	-
Granularity	-
Nature of data	Sensitive

Data examples

Example of COMTRADE record data. Each incident includes 2 of the following files:
1. Configuration file in ASCII format (information on channels recorded, sample rate and number, etc)

```
63, 6A, 4D
1, IA, A, 1, A, 1.98380545288257440e-002, 2.46835408585820910e+000, 0.000000e+000, -
99999, 99998, 2.500000e+003, 5.000000e+000, P
2, IB, B, 2, A, 2.00860868137631430e-002, 8.58835114887574490e+000, 0.000000e+000, -
99999, 99998, 2.500000e+003, 5.000000e+000, P
3, IC, C, 3, A, 2.01378325850669030e-002, 2.46575739285481180e+000, 0.000000e+000, -
99999, 99998, 2.500000e+003, 5.000000e+000, P
4, VA, A, 5, V, 4.94803589046023190e-002, -3.36905864867276250e+000, 0.000000e+000, -
99999, 99998, 6.000000e+000, 1.000000e-001, P
5, VB, B, 6, V, 4.94642331744351150e-002, 8.14484930408707440e+000, 0.000000e+000, -
99999, 99998, 6.000000e+000, 1.000000e-001, P
6, VC_G1, C, 7, V, 4.94776147228145890e-002, -3.04093502076284490e+000, 0.000000e+000, -
99999, 99998, 6.000000e+000, 1.000000e-001, P
1, 86_G1, , GER 1, 0
2, 87UA_G1, , GER 1, 0
3, 87UB_G1, , GER 1, 0
4, 87UC_G1, , GER 1, 0
```

```
50.0
1
5760.000000,24768
25/06/2007,19:13:57.789757
25/06/2007,19:13:58.089757
ASCII
1.000000
```

2. Data file in ASCII format (includes oscillography time-series data points, for each channel in configuration file)

```
1,0,093678,-71445,-19634,099353,-45923,-53996,0,0,0,0
2,174,095165,-67662,-24756,099312,-40793,-58829,0,0,0,0
3,347,095784,-63879,-29634,098351,-35786,-62877,0,0,0,0
.
.
.
24768,4299826,070382,-96704,027316,092192,-79329,-13707,0,0,0,0
```

Historical Data available

Short data description	Examples: 2. Historical time-series net load data
System providing information	-
Data Format and information model	ASCII and Binary text file, structured according to COMTRADE IEEE standard. Data processing and feature extraction work is needed to process this data
Suggested communication protocol	-
Number of data sources	Unknown
Granularity	15 minutes
Time window	At least 10 years
Nature of data	Open
Number of data sources	-
Granularity	-
Nature of data	Sensitive

Data examples

Time series sample:

```
Date;Load
2009-01-01 00:00:00;5363.894619
2009-01-01 00:15:00;5325.519064
2009-01-01 00:30:00;5252.920221
2009-01-01 00:45:00;5236.375564
2009-01-01 01:00:00;5155.823346
2009-01-01 01:15:00;5033.318991
2009-01-01 01:30:00;4921.037406
2009-01-01 01:45:00;4877.968691
2009-01-01 02:00:00;4747.525371
2009-01-01 02:15:00;4684.717209
2009-01-01 02:30:00;4570.333753
2009-01-01 02:45:00;4536.869468
2009-01-01 03:00:00;4461.373289
2009-01-01 03:15:00;4383.268694
2009-01-01 03:30:00;4348.394485
2009-01-01 03:45:00;4288.869832
2009-01-01 04:00:00;4223.419199
2009-01-01 04:15:00;4208.144405
2009-01-01 04:30:00;4167.453035
2009-01-01 04:45:00;4116.217978
2009-01-01 05:00:00;4120.159671
2009-01-01 05:15:00;4088.482796
2009-01-01 05:30:00;4062.34768
2009-01-01 05:45:00;4052.106429
```

2009-01-01 06:00:00;4051.876466
2009-01-01 06:15:00;4038.098538
2009-01-01 06:30:00;4030.9108
2009-01-01 06:45:00;4012.388618
2009-01-01 07:00:00;4043.095406
2009-01-01 07:15:00;3972.458454
2009-01-01 07:30:00;3973.403735
2009-01-01 07:45:00;3870.096143
2009-01-01 08:00:00;3758.267644
2009-01-01 08:15:00;3721.844067
2009-01-01 08:30:00;3786.890888
2009-01-01 08:45:00;3830.236522
2009-01-01 09:00:00;3888.981949
2009-01-01 09:15:00;3984.532962
2009-01-01 09:30:00;4082.459754
2009-01-01 09:45:00;4163.420664
2009-01-01 10:00:00;4300.462124
2009-01-01 10:15:00;4387.544915
2009-01-01 10:30:00;4495.771481
2009-01-01 10:45:00;4589.426177
2009-01-01 11:00:00;4711.588851
2009-01-01 11:15:00;4835.187993
2009-01-01 11:30:00;4907.919833
2009-01-01 11:45:00;5015.904067
2009-01-01 12:00:00;5071.363524
2009-01-01 12:15:00;5075.161639
2009-01-01 12:30:00;5113.018412
2009-01-01 12:45:00;5060.586469
2009-01-01 13:00:00;4949.297991
2009-01-01 13:15:00;4879.125116
2009-01-01 13:30:00;4836.409768
2009-01-01 13:45:00;4813.320927
2009-01-01 14:00:00;4775.320647
2009-01-01 14:15:00;4735.302544
2009-01-01 14:30:00;4765.683207
2009-01-01 14:45:00;4763.029359
2009-01-01 15:00:00;4755.666839
2009-01-01 15:15:00;4710.114155
2009-01-01 15:30:00;4737.795556
2009-01-01 15:45:00;4750.947368
2009-01-01 16:00:00;4771.197306
2009-01-01 16:15:00;4799.01155
2009-01-01 16:30:00;4865.133649
2009-01-01 16:45:00;4929.371695
2009-01-01 17:00:00;5128.497253
2009-01-01 17:15:00;5370.743893
2009-01-01 17:30:00;5631.404177
2009-01-01 17:45:00;5759.226344
2009-01-01 18:00:00;5822.019578
2009-01-01 18:15:00;5926.312634
2009-01-01 18:30:00;5979.979305
2009-01-01 18:45:00;5976.777945

5.4.2 Pilot 2

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]	
Pilot No. 2 [VEOLIA – Spain]	
Historical Data available	
Short data description	Monitoring data (BEMS & DEMS): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Energy 2. Temperature 3. Flow 4. Etc.
System providing information	DataBase
Data Format and information model	CSV
Suggested communication protocol	Tbd
Number of data sources	Around 55 smart energy meters
Granularity	15 min
Time window	UC3: 09/2019 to 04/2021 UC4: 05/2017 to 04/2021 UC5: 11/2017 to 04/2021
Nature of data	Sensitive/Proprietary/open
Live Data available	
Short data description	Smart meters measurements
Data source	Remote Management System
Data Format and information model	SCADA
Suggested communication protocol	BACnet
Number of data sources	Around 55 smart energy meters
Granularity	15 min
Nature of data	Sensitive/Proprietary/open

5.4.3 Pilot 3

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]	
Pilot No. 3 [ASM – Italy]	
Historical Data available	
Short data description	Smart Meters Data related to the heterogenous type of customers scattered in the city.
System providing information	MQTT broker
Data Format and information model	JSON
Suggested communication protocol	MQTT
Number of data sources	150 smart meters
Granularity	5 seconds
Time window	3 years (from 2018 to 2020)
Nature of data	Proprietary
Historical Data available	
Short data description	PQA in ASM district Data related to: photovoltaic plant, battery system, headquarter facilities
System providing information	REST API
Data Format and information model	CSV / JSON
Suggested communication protocol	http - curl
Number of data sources	6
Granularity	10 minutes
Time window	3 years (from 2018 to 2020)
Nature of data	Proprietary
Historical Data available	
Short data description	BEMS Data in ASM district
System providing information	Modbus TCP
Data Format and information model	CSV
Suggested communication protocol	Modbus Interface
Number of data sources	1
Granularity	15 minutes
Time window	2 years (from 2019 to 2020)
Nature of data	Proprietary
Historical Data available	
Short data description	PMU in 1 Secondary Substation and in 1 Primary Substation
System providing information	MQTT broker
Data Format and information model	JSON
Suggested communication protocol	MQTT
Number of data sources	2
Granularity	1 second
Time window	9 months (since August 2021)
Nature of data	Proprietary

Data examples

Provide the examples of data if already exists from the Data source for example:

1. Near real time smart meter

```
{
  "LD01": {
    "1-1-1-8-0-255": {
      "-2": "1709608.3358",
      "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
      "Description": "Energy A+",
      "Unit": "kWh",
      "1-1-14-7-0-255": {
        "-2": "049.991",
        "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
        "Description": "Frequency",
        "Unit": "Hz",
        "1-1-16-7-0-255": {
          "-2": "58.505",
          "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
          "-9": "058.505k",
          "Description": "P",
          "Unit": "W",
          "1-1-2-8-0-255": {
            "-2": "103756.6345",
            "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
            "Description": "Energy A-",
            "Unit": "kWh",
            "1-1-23-7-0-255": {
              "-2": "3.517",
              "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
              "-9": "-03.517k",
              "Description": "Q1",
              "Unit": "W",
              "1-1-3-7-0-255": {
                "-2": "-10.373",
                "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                "-9": "-10.373k",
                "Description": "Q",
                "Unit": "var",
                "1-1-3-8-0-255": {
                  "Description": "Energy R+",
                  "Unit": "kWh",
                  "1-1-31-7-0-255": {
                    "-2": "86.416",
                    "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                    "-9": "086.416",
                    "Description": "I1",
                    "Unit": "A",
                    "1-1-32-7-0-255": {
                      "-2": "237.703",
                      "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                      "-9": "237.703",
                      "Description": "U(1-0)",
                      "Unit": "V",
                      "1-1-33-7-0-255": {
                        "Description": "K1",
                        "Unit": "NoUnit",
                        "1-1-36-7-0-255": {
                          "-2": "19.974",
                          "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                          "-9": "019.974k",
                          "Description": "P1",
                          "Unit": "W",
                          "1-1-4-8-0-255": {
                            "Description": "Energy R-",
                            "Unit": "kWh",
                            "1-1-43-7-0-255": {
                              "-2": "-3.494",
                              "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                              "-9": "-03.494k",
                              "Description": "Q2",
                              "Unit": "W",
                              "1-1-51-7-0-255": {
                                "-2": "81.044",
                                "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                                "-9": "081.044",
                                "Description": "I2",
                                "Unit": "A",
                                "1-1-52-7-0-255": {
                                  "-2": "237.499",
                                  "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                                  "-9": "237.499",
                                  "Description": "U(2-0)",
                                  "Unit": "V",
                                  "1-1-53-7-0-255": {
                                    "Description": "K2",
                                    "Unit": "NoUnit",
                                    "1-1-56-7-0-255": {
                                      "-2": "18.714",
                                      "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                                      "-9": "018.714k",
                                      "Description": "P2",
                                      "Unit": "W",
                                      "1-1-63-7-0-255": {
                                        "-2": "-3.362",
                                        "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                                        "-9": "-03.362k",
                                        "Description": "Q3",
                                        "Unit": "W",
                                        "1-1-71-7-0-255": {
                                          "-2": "85.198",
                                          "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                                          "-9": "085.198",
                                          "Description": "I3",
                                          "Unit": "A",
                                          "1-1-72-7-0-255": {
                                            "-2": "237.607",
                                            "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                                            "-9": "237.607",
                                            "Description": "U(3-0)",
                                            "Unit": "V",
                                            "1-1-73-7-0-255": {
                                              "Description": "K3",
                                              "Unit": "NoUnit",
                                              "1-1-76-7-0-255": {
                                                "-2": "19.816",
                                                "-5": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                                                "-9": "019.816k",
                                                "Description": "P3",
                                                "Unit": "W",
                                                "Voltage": {
                                                  "Unit": "V",
                                                  "_MeterPoint": "Grid MV",
                                                  "_MeterType": "Wally-A",
                                                  "172.16.1.111",
                                                  "_Actor_type": "Network",
                                                  "_City": "Terni",
                                                  "_Country": "Italy",
                                                  "_GPS": "42.569944, 12.651323",
                                                  "_Project": "H2020 Nobel Grid",
                                                  "_RBAC": "SMXcore.2018.04.08.001",
                                                  "_Service": "Providing real-time values for G3M-SCADA service",
                                                  "_User_name": "TERNI-MV",
                                                  "__SMXtimestamp": "05/05/2021 09:59:30",
                                                  "wallya1": {
                                                    "Apparent Energy": {
                                                      "value": "1843105.9369"
                                                    },
                                                    "Apparent Power 3-Phase": {
                                                      "value": "060.026k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Apparent Power Phase L1": {
                                                      "value": "020.539k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Apparent Power Phase L2": {
                                                      "value": "019.246k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Apparent Power Phase L3": {
                                                      "value": "020.242k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Flicker Inst Max L1-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.052"
                                                    },
                                                    "Flicker Inst Max L2-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.044"
                                                    },
                                                    "Flicker Inst Max L3-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.048"
                                                    },
                                                    "Flicker Plt L1-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.373"
                                                    },
                                                    "Flicker Plt L2-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.388"
                                                    },
                                                    "Flicker Plt L3-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.413"
                                                    },
                                                    "Flicker Pst L1-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.073"
                                                    },
                                                    "Flicker Pst L2-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.084"
                                                    },
                                                    "Flicker Pst L3-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.088"
                                                    },
                                                    "Fundamental PF 3-Phase": {
                                                      "value": "0.985"
                                                    },
                                                    "Non-Active Power 3-Phase": {
                                                      "value": "013.404k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Non-Active Power Phase L1": {
                                                      "value": "004.782k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Non-Active Power Phase L2": {
                                                      "value": "004.492k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Non-Active Power Phase L3": {
                                                      "value": "004.129k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Non-Fundamental Power 3-Phase": {
                                                      "value": "008.898k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Non-Fundamental Power Phase L1": {
                                                      "value": "003.405k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Non-Fundamental Power Phase L2": {
                                                      "value": "002.971k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Non-Fundamental Power Phase L3": {
                                                      "value": "002.523k"
                                                    },
                                                    "Q1 Reactive Energy": {
                                                      "value": "104876.6044"
                                                    },
                                                    "Q2 Reactive Energy": {
                                                      "value": "000498.5516"
                                                    },
                                                    "Q3 Reactive Energy": {
                                                      "value": "011564.3003"
                                                    },
                                                    "Q4 Reactive Energy": {
                                                      "value": "084909.6381"
                                                    },
                                                    "Rms Current L4-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.000"
                                                    },
                                                    "Rms Voltage L1-L2": {
                                                      "value": "411.400"
                                                    },
                                                    "Rms Voltage L2-L3": {
                                                      "value": "411.380"
                                                    },
                                                    "Rms Voltage L3-L1": {
                                                      "value": "411.748"
                                                    },
                                                    "Rms Voltage L4-N": {
                                                      "value": "000.000"
                                                    },
                                                    "THDI L1": {
                                                      "value": "016.410"
                                                    },
                                                    "THDI L2": {
                                                      "value": "015.189"
                                                    },
                                                    "THDI L3": {
                                                      "value": "011.966"
                                                    },
                                                    "THDI L4": {
                                                      "value": "n/a"
                                                    },
                                                    "THDV L1-N": {
                                                      "value": "001.554"
                                                    },
                                                    "THDV L2-N": {
                                                      "value": "001.611"
                                                    },
                                                    "THDV L3-N": {
                                                      "value": "001.566"
                                                    },
                                                    "THDV L4-N": {
                                                      "value": "n/a"
                                                    },
                                                    "time": "05/05/2021 09:59:30"
                                                  }
                                                }
                                              }
                                            }
                                          }
                                        }
                                      }
                                    }
                                  }
                                }
                              }
                            }
                          }
                        }
                      }
                    }
                  }
                }
              }
            }
          }
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
```

2. PQA (CSV)

t1	t2	p_TOTAL_avg	q_TOTAL_avg	v_AB_vg	av_BC_vg	av_CA_vg	afreq_avg	a_AN_vg	a_BN_vg	aa_CN_vg
2018-05-22T08:30:00	2018-05-22T08:40:00	-0.64945	-0.71045	5	6	6	00	32	15	12
2018-05-22T08:40:00	2018-05-22T08:50:00	-0.64308	-0.70517	7	8	1	7	31	21	06
2018-05-22T08:50:00	2018-05-22T09:00:00	-0.64393	-0.70882	0	8	2	0	29	20	09
2018-05-22T09:00:00	2018-05-22T09:10:00	-0.63962	-0.70917	5	7	0	5	27	17	06
2018-05-22T09:10:00	2018-05-22T09:20:00	-0.64700	-0.71642	5	1	5	1	28	17	09
2018-05-22T09:20:00	2018-05-22T09:30:00	-0.64624	-0.72066	4	5	9	5	38	17	06
2018-05-22T09:30:00	2018-05-22T09:40:00	-0.64559	-0.72179	6	7	7	6	34	22	03
2018-05-22T09:40:00	2018-05-22T09:50:00	-0.64417	-0.71811	4	6	8	4	40	15	01
2018-05-22T09:50:00	2018-05-22T10:00:00	-0.64939	-0.71475	7	5	5	5	37	19	03

3. BEMS (CSV)

TimeStamp	CT_Temp_Mandata	Coll_Ritorno	CT_Temp_Esterna	Co_RT1_Mandata	Temp_RT1_Ripresa	UTA3_Temp_Mandata	UTA3_Temp_Ripresa
1/5/2000.00	24,4067	30,95107	17,24757	20,89755	26,63229	21,46571	18,90552
1/5/2000.15	24,35468	30,89821	17,19573	21,00144	26,63229	21,41338	18,90388
1/5/2000.30	24,30269	30,84534	17,14386	20,63795	26,88826	21,36098	18,9047
1/5/2000.45	24,25073	30,79245	17,09199	20,89755	26,63311	21,46571	18,9047
1/5/2001.00	24,25073	30,73961	17,09199	20,94948	26,27557	21,46571	18,95578
1/5/2001.15	24,19871	30,68675	17,14386	20,94948	26,2764	21,36098	18,9047
1/5/2001.30	24,14672	30,63391	17,19573	20,89755	26,07244	20,314	17,88554
1/5/2001.45	24,09476	30,58108	17,14386	20,84563	26,17401	20,8374	17,88471

1/5/2	24,09476	30,52821	16,9364	20,94948	25,81977	19,52809	16,97101
0 2.00							

4. PMU data (Messages as JSON objects)

A sample message:

```
{
  "node_id": "",
  "stn": "Station-0",
  "soc": 1602078510,
  "fracsec": 0,
  "vm1": 230.31439208984375,
  "vph1": -47.657395631859266,
  "vm2": 230.9148406982422,
  "vph2": 72.33367040491599,
  "vm3": 231.7793426513672,
  "vph3": -167.5164955836807,
  "vm4": 230.86802673339844,
  "vph4": -167.50331331858257,
  "im1": 0.000057650599046610296,
  "iph1": 52.590786627846114,
  "im2": 0.00003093302439083345,
  "iph2": -111.98963261279414,
  "im3": 0.000042565585317788646,
  "iph3": 76.26046227197222,
  "im4": 0.000029644323149113916,
  "iph4": 149.5296841780724,
  "f": 49.98057174682617,
  "df": 0.06389617919921875,
  "digita": 0,
  "analog": 0,
  "vzsm": 0.3782951235771179,
  "vzsph": -164.22327889422402,
  "izsm": 0.00002246705480501987,
  "izsph": 60.14759522742692
}
```

5.4.4 Pilot 4

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 4 [BFP - Avetrana]

Historical Data available

Short data description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Historical weather data for Avetrana (TA) Historical dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
System providing information	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	69 inverters, 1 meter, radiation sensor
Granularity	15 min
Time window	1 month (from 09/04/2021 To Today)
Nature of data	Open

Live Data available

Short data description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Live weather data for Avetrana (TA) Live dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
Data source	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	69 inverters, 1 meter, radiation sensor
Granularity	15 min
Nature of data	Open

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No.4 [BFP- Manduria]

Historical Data available

Short data description	1. Historical weather data for Manduria (TA) 2. Historical dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
System providing information	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	60 inverters, 1 meter, radiation sensor
Granularity	15 min
Time window	1 month (from 09/04/2021 To Today)
Nature of data	Open

Live Data available

Short data description	1. Live weather data for Manduria (TA) 2. Live dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
Data source	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	60 inverters, 1 meter, radiation sensor
Granularity	15 min
Nature of data	Open

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No.4 [BFP - Badessa]

Historical Data available	
Short data description	1. Historical weather data for Lequile (LE) 2. Historical dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
System providing information	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Time window	1 month (from 09/04/2021 To Today)
Nature of data	Open

Live Data available	
Short data description	1. Live weather data for Lequile (LE) 2. Live dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
Data source	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Nature of data	Open

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]	
Pilot No.4 [BFP – S. Alieni]	
Historical Data available	
Short data description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Historical weather data for CAVALLINO (LE) 2. Historical dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
System providing information	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Time window	1 month (from 09/04/2021 To Today)
Nature of data	Open

Live Data available	
Short data description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Live weather data for CAVALLINO (LE) 2. Live dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
Data source	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Nature of data	Open

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]	
Pilot No.4 [BFP - Lena]	
Historical Data available	
Short data description	1. Historical weather data for CAVALLINO (LE) 2. Historical dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
System providing information	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Time window	1 month (from 09/04/2021 To Today)
Nature of data	Open

Live Data available	
Short data description	1. Live weather data for CAVALLINO (LE) 2. Live dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
Data source	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Nature of data	Open

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No.4 [BFP – Litara’]

Historical Data available

Short data description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Historical weather data for STERNATIA (LE) 2. Historical dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
System providing information	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Time window	1 month (from 09/04/2021 To Today)
Nature of data	Open

Live Data available

Short data description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Live weather data for STERNATIA (LE) 2. Live dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
Data source	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Nature of data	Open

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No.4 [BFP - Milligrani]

Historical Data available

Short data description	1. Historical weather data for MARTIGNANO (LE) 2. Historical dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
System providing information	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Time window	1 month (from 09/04/2021 To Today)
Nature of data	Open

Live Data available

Short data description	13. Live weather data for MARTIGNANO (LE) 14. Live dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
Data source	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	13. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 14. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Nature of data	Open

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]
Pilot No.4 [BFP - Lamelle]

Historical Data available	
Short data description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Historical weather data for MARTIGNANO (LE) 2. Historical dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
System providing information	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 12 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Time window	1 month (from 09/04/2021 To Today)
Nature of data	Open

Live Data available	
Short data description	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Live weather data for MARTIGNANO (LE) 2. Live dataset of PV plant production at inverter level
Data source	Monitoring System
Data Format and information model	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. JSON, Proprietary data model (https://meteocontrol.github.io/vcom-api/?shell#introduction) 3. CSV, Proprietary Data Model
Suggested communication protocol	API, FTP-PUSH
Number of data sources	1 inverter, 1 meter, radiation sensor, 9 string boxes
Granularity	15 min
Nature of data	Open

5.4.5 Pilot 5

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]	
Pilot No. 5 [HERON/PARITY – Greece]	
Historical Data available	
Short data description	Examples (only one per table!): 1. Historical weather data for location X 2. Historical dataset of ... for AI training
System providing information	Example: SCADA, GIS, EMS, DB
Data Format and information model	Examples: 1. JSON, Proprietary data model 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model 3. XML, CIM
Suggested communication protocol	FTP, MQTT, HTTP,...
Number of data sources	Examples: 100 smart meters, 10 homes with EMS,...
Granularity	1 min
Time window	2 years (from 1.1.2019 to 31.12.2020)
Nature of data	Sensitive/Proprietary/open
Live Data available	
Short data description	Examples (only one per table!): 1. Smart meter measurements 2. EV Charging data from EV EMS
Data source	Example: e.g. smart meter, IoT, (x)EMS
Data Format and information model	Examples: 1. JSON, Proprietary data model 2. CSV, Proprietary Data Model 3. XML, CIM
Suggested communication protocol	I1/P1, MQTT, ...
Number of data sources	Examples: 100 smart meters, 10 homes with EMS,...
Granularity	1 min
Nature of data	Sensitive/Proprietary/open

Data examples

Provide the examples of data if already exists from the Data source for example:

1. PMU data (Messages as JSON objects)

A sample message:

```
{
  "node_id": "",
  "stn": "Station-0",
  "soc": 1602078510,
  "fracsec": 0,
  "vm1": 230.31439208984375,
  "vph1": -47.657395631859266,
  "vm2": 230.9148406982422,
  "vph2": 72.33367040491599,
  "vm3": 231.7793426513672,
  "vph3": -167.5164955836807,
  "vm4": 230.86802673339844,
  "vph4": -167.50331331858257,
  "im1": 0.000057650599046610296,
```

```
"iph1": 52.590786627846114,  
"im2": 0.00003093302439083345,  
"iph2": -111.98963261279414,  
"im3": 0.000042565585317788646,  
"iph3": 76.26046227197222,  
"im4": 0.000029644323149113916,  
"iph4": 149.5296841780724,  
"f": 49.98057174682617,  
"df": 0.06389617919921875,  
"digita": 0,  
"analog": 0,  
"vzsm": 0.3782951235771179,  
"vzsph": -164.22327889422402,  
"izsm": 0.00002246705480501987,  
"izsph": 60.14759522742692  
}
```

2. Disaggregated data (Raw data)

Energy:419.895
light_livingroom:1584642981000,7.611,-1.402
stove:1584642383000,-959.607,30.551
light_bathroom:1584642638000,-78.074,1.3575
light_bathroom:1584643985000,78.639,-1.043
light_bathroom:1584644221000,78.375,-1.193

5.4.6 Pilot 6

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 6 [ZEZcoop - Croatia]

Historical Data available

Short data description	1. Historical weather data for location Križevci and Varaždin (TBC)
System providing information	GIS
Data Format and information model	• (TBC)
Suggested communication protocol	-
Number of data sources	-
Granularity	1 day
Time window	At least 2 years
Nature of data	Open

Historical Data available

Short data description	2. Historical dataset for load / consumption
System providing information	AMI (data from the DSO – available on request)
Data Format and information model	CSV
Suggested communication protocol	-
Number of data sources	100 users (to be organised within a virtual renewable energy community)
Granularity	15 min
Time window	At least 2 years
Nature of data	Open, sensitive

Live Data available

Short data description	3. Smart meter measurements (consumption and PV production)
Data source	DB (ZEZcoop database currently being developed)
Data Format and information model	1. XML (TBC)
Suggested communication protocol	-
Number of data sources	100 users (to be organised within a virtual renewable energy community) – data to be collected from smart meters and on the inverter side (third party monitoring)
Granularity	15 min (or 30 min)
Nature of data	Sensitive/Open

Data examples

Provide the examples of data if already exists from the Data source for example:

1. Load/consumption (historical data available on request from DS)
Time LP+ SNAGA [kW] LP+ ENERGIJA [kWh] Q1_T0 INDUKTIVNO [kvarh] Q4_T0 KAPACITIVNO [kvarh]
01.01.2020. 00:15 0.127 0.032 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 00:30 0.135 0.034 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 00:45 0.115 0.029 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 01:00 0.129 0.032 0.003 0

01.01.2020. 01:15 0.124 0.031 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 01:30 0.114 0.028 0 0.001
01.01.2020. 01:45 0.131 0.033 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 02:00 0.123 0.031 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 02:15 0.129 0.032 0 0.001
01.01.2020. 02:30 0.126 0.031 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 02:45 0.128 0.032 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 03:00 0.115 0.029 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 03:15 0.127 0.032 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 03:30 0.122 0.031 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 03:45 0.123 0.031 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 04:00 0.125 0.031 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 04:15 0.138 0.034 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 04:30 0.125 0.031 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 04:45 0.127 0.032 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 05:00 0.115 0.029 0 0.001
01.01.2020. 05:15 0.123 0.031 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 05:30 0.13 0.032 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 05:45 0.115 0.029 0 0.001
01.01.2020. 06:00 0.122 0.031 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 06:15 0.131 0.033 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 06:30 0.116 0.029 0.001 0
01.01.2020. 06:45 0.138 0.034 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 07:00 0.123 0.031 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 07:15 0.121 0.03 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 07:30 0.121 0.03 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 07:45 0.118 0.029 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 08:00 0.107 0.027 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 08:15 0.13 0.033 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 08:30 0.111 0.028 0.002 0.001
01.01.2020. 08:45 0.11 0.027 0.001 0.002
01.01.2020. 09:00 0.109 0.027 0 0.001
01.01.2020. 09:15 0.118 0.03 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 09:30 0.104 0.026 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 09:45 0.118 0.03 0.001 0
01.01.2020. 10:00 0.125 0.031 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 10:15 0.112 0.028 0 0.003
01.01.2020. 10:30 0.113 0.028 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 10:45 0.111 0.028 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 11:00 0.106 0.026 0 0.004
01.01.2020. 11:15 0.117 0.029 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 11:30 0.109 0.027 0.001 0
01.01.2020. 11:45 0.109 0.027 0 0.003
01.01.2020. 12:00 0.114 0.029 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 12:15 0.11 0.028 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 12:30 0.109 0.027 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 12:45 0.138 0.034 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 13:00 0.105 0.026 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 13:15 0.11 0.028 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 13:30 0.119 0.03 0.002 0.001
01.01.2020. 13:45 0.111 0.028 0 0.001
01.01.2020. 14:00 0.107 0.027 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 14:15 0.12 0.03 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 14:30 0.107 0.027 0 0.003
01.01.2020. 14:45 0.113 0.028 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 15:00 0.11 0.028 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 15:15 0.125 0.031 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 15:30 0.111 0.028 0.001 0.001

01.01.2020. 15:45 0.112 0.028 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 16:00 0.108 0.027 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 16:15 0.11 0.028 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 16:30 0.115 0.029 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 16:45 0.105 0.026 0 0.002
01.01.2020. 17:00 0.128 0.032 0.002 0.001
01.01.2020. 17:15 0.129 0.032 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 17:30 0.115 0.029 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 17:45 0.121 0.03 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 18:00 0.13 0.033 0.005 0
01.01.2020. 18:15 0.112 0.028 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 18:30 0.121 0.03 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 18:45 0.142 0.035 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 19:00 0.119 0.03 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 19:15 0.125 0.031 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 19:30 0.123 0.031 0.003 0
01.01.2020. 19:45 0.121 0.03 0 0.001
01.01.2020. 20:00 0.123 0.031 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 20:15 0.122 0.031 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 20:30 0.129 0.032 0.001 0
01.01.2020. 20:45 0.13 0.032 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 21:00 0.118 0.03 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 21:15 0.118 0.03 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 21:30 0.128 0.032 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 21:45 0.113 0.028 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 22:00 0.13 0.032 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 22:15 0.126 0.031 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 22:30 0.121 0.03 0.001 0.001
01.01.2020. 22:45 0.119 0.03 0.002 0
01.01.2020. 23:00 0.124 0.031 0.005 0
01.01.2020. 23:15 0.122 0.031 0.001 0
01.01.2020. 23:30 0.138 0.035 0.002 0.001
01.01.2020. 23:45 0.125 0.031 0.004 0
01.01.2020. 24:00 0.121 0.03 0.002 0
02.01.2020. 00:15 0.12 0.03 0.001 0.001

5.4.7 Pilot 7

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 7 [Sonce – Slovenia]

Historical Data available

Short data description	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heat pumps: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Electrical energy, power ○ Thermal energy measurements ○ Temperature sensors on heat pump and boilers • Solar power plant <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Output (power, energy production...) • District heating <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Thermal energy measurements • Residents <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ the temperature of common areas
System information	providing SCADA, EMS, DB
Data Format and information model	1. JSON 2. CSV
Suggested communication protocol	HTTP
Number of data sources	
Granularity	From 1 min to 60min
Time window	Different on the data source, most have more than 1 year
Nature of data	Sensitive/Proprietary/open

5.4.8 Pilot 9

Pilot Number [Pilot owner - Location]

Pilot No. 9 [FAEN - SPAIN]

Historical Data available

Short data description	Historical information consisting of the exportation data of the software used in the assessment of energy performance of buildings
System providing information	Different software: Lider-Calener, Cerma CE3X, CE3....
Data Format and information model	1. XML
Suggested communication protocol	-----
Number of data sources	50.000 files
Granularity	-----
Time window	2007 – 2017 2020 - present
Nature of data	Sensitive

Data examples

Provide the examples of data if already exists from the Data source for example:

1. XML data

A sample message:

```
{<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8" ?>
<DatosEnergeticosDelEdificio version="2.0">
  <DatosDelCertificador>
    <NIFEntidad>x</NIFEntidad>
    <ComunidadAutonoma>Comunidad Foral de Navarra</ComunidadAutonoma>
    <Titulacion>x</Titulacion>
    <Fecha>26/7/2012</Fecha>
    <NIF>x</NIF>
    <Email>x</Email>
    <RazonSocial>CENER - EFINOVATIC</RazonSocial>
    <Domicilio>x</Domicilio>
    <CodigoPostal>31002</CodigoPostal>
    <Provincia>Navarra</Provincia>
    <Telefono>x</Telefono>
    <NombreyApellidos>CENER - EFINOVATIC</NombreyApellidos>
    <Municipio>Pamplona</Municipio>
  </DatosDelCertificador>
  <IdentificacionEdificio>
    <ReferenciaCatastral>x</ReferenciaCatastral>
    <Procedimiento>CEXv2.1</Procedimiento>
    <Provincia>Navarra</Provincia>
    <ComunidadAutonoma>Comunidad Foral de Navarra</ComunidadAutonoma>
    <ZonaClimatica>D1</ZonaClimatica>
    <TipoDeEdificio>EdificioUsoTerciario</TipoDeEdificio>
    <NormativaVigente>NBE-CT-79</NormativaVigente>
    <Direccion>x</Direccion>
    <AnoConstruccion>1995</AnoConstruccion>
    <CodigoPostal>31002</CodigoPostal>
    <AlcanceInformacionXML>CertificacionExistente</AlcanceInformacionXML>
    <Municipio>Pamplona</Municipio>
    <NombreDelEdificio>Ejemplo de edificio de gran terciario</NombreDelEdificio>
  </IdentificacionEdificio>
  <DatosGeneralesyGeometria>
    <NumeroDePlantasSobreRasante>99999999.99</NumeroDePlantasSobreRasante>
    <PorcentajeSuperficieHabitableCalefactada>100</PorcentajeSuperficieHabitableCalefactada>
    <SuperficieHabitable>2600.0</SuperficieHabitable>
    <DensidadFuentesInternas>14.35</DensidadFuentesInternas>
    <Compacidad>2.77</Compacidad>
  </DatosGeneralesyGeometria>
</DatosEnergeticosDelEdificio>
```

```

<VolumenEspacioHabitable>7800.0</VolumenEspacioHabitable>
<VentilacionTotal>0.19</VentilacionTotal>
<DemandaDiariaACS>546.0</DemandaDiariaACS>
<Plano>iVBORw0KGgoAAAANSUHEUgAAARUAAACGCAIAAAB8CYnsAAEAAE1EQVR4nMySwQ6AIAxDX/H//lioh6m
BMKMHY2w4tYy1Y7LNvxH+GhQAdFK9bFCcldQgD..... 1RuNugPAAD//8Rbyw7AIAij7v9/eewAxTJMdhYHJXuhQKHGy
J/5c5CqRFFInBsJGL1WcAnExII0fGcCGuIhG9dbmEg73lTuTNbJjHo3vYbEmQJRbhmL9rCuIEaNHsw4VJT9VBjfhm
lkflejuGiMiTk7nagm45dkpssdl8W1VCvF32J1vWyVvN0W7yZtvN7ktWZiXJEcbI75wCuNQ6oqkiYmfjB+ZebrWreN
tgDAAD//xrQ/IPHZsZ/qPz/SAkNe18qIvVBuHlyadOgsBGJET2w/8PTGWrTkLBbsecfsgH2Ng92df9RVP9DnT+jMkD
K4pAqFYsCRM7HB1ArQ0KA+ESJ20TUEgrRDoRnBizewQH+wSKXEc2nAAAAAP//Gir5B6KwCmFmUHwSmNRSGQMY09Jd
AGDqcHawEBKMiQ+jGhjJNxxUJrgQhbYAAAAA//8DAAZLVmX4rPc8AAAAAE1FTkSuQmCC</Plano>
<NumeroDePlantasBajoRasante>100000000</NumeroDePlantasBajoRasante> <PorcentajeSuperficieHa
bitableRefrigerada>100</PorcentajeSuperficieHabitacleRefrigerada <Imagen>iVBORw0KGgoAAAANS
UHEUgAAAKgAAACGCAIAAADGj1alAAAF0U1EQVR4nGL8//8/wygYeQAAAAD//2IaaAeMgoEBAAAAAP//Go34EQoAAAA
A//8ajfgRCgAAAAD//xqN+BEKAAAAAP//Go34EQoAAAAA//8ajfgRCgAAAAD//xqN+BEKAAAAAP//Go34EQoAAAAA/
/8ajfgRCgAAAAD//xqN+BEKAAAAAP//Go34EQoAAAAA//8ajfgRCgAAAAD//xqN+BEKAAAAAP//.....8ajfgRCgAAAA
D//xqN+BEKAAAAAP//Go34EQoAAAAA//8ajfgRCgAAAAD//xqN+BEKAAAAAP//AwB+zQQJy31CwQAAAABJRu5ErkJg
gg==</Imagen>
<PorcentajeSuperficieAcrystalada>
<E>0</E>
<NO>50</NO>
<NE>0</NE>
<O>0</O>
<N>0</N>
<S>0</S>
<SO>0</SO>
<SE>50</SE>
</PorcentajeSuperficieAcrystalada>
</DatosGeneralesyGeometria>
<DatosEnvolventeTermica>
<CerramientosOpacos>
<Elemento>
<Tipo>Fachada</Tipo>
<ModoDeObtencion>PorDefecto</ModoDeObtencion>
<Transmitancia>1.4</Transmitancia>
<Superficie>600.0</Superficie>
<Orientacion>NO</Orientacion>
<Nombre>Muro de fachada NO</Nombre>
<Capas/>
</Elemento>
<Elemento>
<Tipo>Fachada</Tipo>
<ModoDeObtencion>PorDefecto</ModoDeObtencion>
<Transmitancia>1.4</Transmitancia>
<Superficie>156.0</Superficie>
<Orientacion>NE</Orientacion>
<Nombre>Muro de fachada NE</Nombre>
<Capas/>
}

```

5.5 APPENDIX V - Usage scenarios

5.5.1 Pilot 1

5.5.1.1 Use Case 1: AI for enhanced network assets predictive maintenance, integrating off-grid data with condition-based monitoring

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 1.1

Involved Persona

Asset Management Division of TSO

Related User story

As a TSO asset manager, **I want to** be able to automatically extract data insights, related to individual circuit breaker tripping incidents (such as fault detection time, elimination time, maximum faulted current or incident type), from COMTRADE files, **so that** faults can be analysed in an automatic and fast way.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Availability of incident data acquisition tools that register circuit breaker tripping incidents
Postcondition	Automatic data insights extraction from single COMTRADE incident report

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Retrieve COMTRADE data to be analyzed	-
2	Read and parse oscillography COMTRADE data into Python data structures (e.g. Pandas DataFrame)	Circuit Breaker Automatic Incident Classification
3	Segment signals and identify fault start, end and reconnection times	Circuit Breaker Automatic Incident Classification
4	Extract operation times	Circuit Breaker Automatic Incident Classification
5	Typify incident	Circuit Breaker Automatic Incident Classification
6	Generate incident report	Circuit Breaker Automatic Incident Classification

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 1.2

Involved Persona

Asset Management Division of TSO

Related User story

As a TSO asset manager, **I want to** be able to correlate faults recorded in COMTRADE files with off-grid data (e.g. time-of-year, weather, forest fires), **so that** that the external factors with the most impact on incidents can be studied.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of circuit breaker incident data in COMTRADE data • Availability of off-grid data
Postcondition	Creation of predictive maintenance plans that take into account relevant off and on-grid factors derived from analytics insights extracted

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Retrieve incident data (included previously derived incident measurements) and off-grid data	
2	Perform time-based analysis of asset state evolution	Predictive Maintenance for Circuit Breakers
3	Correlate incident data with off-grid data	Predictive Maintenance for Circuit Breakers
4	Categorize/Cluster incidents in terms of relevance and priority	Predictive Maintenance for Circuit Breakers
5	Derive maintenance plan based on insights extracted	Predictive Maintenance for Circuit Breakers

5.5.1.2 Use Case 2: AI for network loads and demand forecasting towards efficient operational planning

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 2.1

Involved Persona

System operator

Related User story

As a system operator, **I want to** improve the current methodologies used to forecast net load, using AI techniques, **so that** internal processes which rely on the accuracy of these forecasts (e.g. cross border trading and operational planning) can be optimized

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions

- Availability of load time-series data

Postcondition

Significant improvement in load forecast errors

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Retrieve historical load data	
2	Train and validate ML forecasting algorithm	Net load forecasting
3	Perform online forecast of net load	Net load forecasting

5.5.2 Pilot 2

5.5.2.1 Use Case 3: AI for energy demand prediction to optimise District Heating Network (DHN) operation

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.1

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter DHN manager.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter DHN manager, **I want to** get a better understanding of how the facility operates, **so that** the failures decrease and the efficiency increase.

Usage Scenario conditions

- Preconditions**
- Smart Meters (SMs) are installed and available.
 - Facilities are connected to centralized control and to a monitoring system.
 - Historical data available.

- Postcondition**
- Decrease of failures and breakdowns in the facility.
 - Decrease of the O&M costs.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Identification of the installation's main components.	
3	Development of an AI-based model of the facility to control it.	AI-based model of the facility.
4	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	AI-based model of the facility.
5	Optimize the installation's operating parameters according to the results of the model created.	Optimization of the operation of the network.
6	Creation of a model-based O&M plan.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.2

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter DHN manager.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter DHN manager, I want to forecast the behaviour of the facility and its reaction to potential changes, so that the energy consumption and GHG emissions are reduced.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are installed. • Facilities are connected to centralized control and to a monitoring system. • Historical weather data available.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce energy consumption. • Reduce GHG emissions.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Identification of the installation's main components.	
3	Develop an AI-based model of the facility to control it.	AI-based model of the facility.
4	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	AI-based model of the facility.
5	Forecast the behaviour of the facility depending on the different renovation that could be implemented in the installation.	Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption.
6	Forecast the behaviour of the facility according to weather forecasts.	Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption.
7	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as reductions in GHG emissions.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.3

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter DHN manager.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter DHN manager, I want to get an accurate DHN model, so that network expansion and new energy efficiency measures can be implemented more easily.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are installed. • Facilities are connected to centralized control and to a monitoring system. • There is historical monitored data available.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease of failures and breakdowns in the facility. • Decrease of the O&M costs.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Precise analysis of the operation of the facility.	
3	Identification of the installation's main components.	
4	Definition of relevant installation's KPIs.	
5	Develop an AI-based model of the facility to control it.	Digital Twin of the facility.
6	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	Digital Twin of the facility.
7	Virtually implement the network expansion or ECMs in the virtual lab/model.	Digital Twin of the facility.
8	Find low efficiency or pain points by studying and analyzing the different KPIs.	Optimization of the operation of the network.
9	Implementation of network expansion or ECMs.	
10	Creation of a model-based O&M plan.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.4

Involved Persona

Cost-conscious DHN manager.

Related User story

As a Cost-conscious DHN manager, **I want to** get a better understanding of how the facility operates, **so that** the failures and costs are reduced and the efficiency is increased.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Meters (SMs) are not installed. There are only historical energy consumption data available.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Meters (SMs) installed. Increase the efficiency of the facility. Reduction of the costs. Decrease of failures and breakdowns in the facility.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Installation of the SMs.	
2	Development of a facility's monitoring system.	
3	Connection to the control and central monitoring system.	
4	Data collection and accurate analysis.	
5	Development of based model of the facility to control it.	an AI-based model of the facility.
6	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	AI-based model of the facility.
7	Reports on energy and cost, savings and on the profit generated.	
8	Creation of a model-based O&M plan.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.5

Involved Persona

Cost-conscious DHN manager.

Related User story

As a Cost-conscious DHN manager, **I want to** forecast the behaviour of the facility and its reaction to potential changes, **so that** there is de-risking when implementing energy efficiency measures.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are installed. • There is historical monitoring data available. • Accurate weather prediction.
Postcondition	Implementation of energy efficiency measures.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Identification of the installation's main components.	
3	Definition of relevant installation's KPIs.	
4	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility, including the forecast of the KPIs, energy performance, ROI and profit.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as reductions in GHG emissions.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.6

Involved Persona

Cost-conscious DHN manager.

Related User story

As a Cost-conscious DHN manager, **I want to** get an accurate DHN model, **so that** the risks of expanding or retrofit the DHN and its costs are lowered.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Meters (SMs) are installed. There is historical monitored data available. Accurate weather forecast.
Postcondition	Expansion of the DHN.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation’s available data.	
2	Precise analysis of the operation of the facility.	
3	Identification of the installation’s main components.	
4	Definition of relevant installation’s KPIs.	
5	Develop an AI-based model of the facility to control it.	Digital Twin of the facility.
6	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	Digital Twin of the facility.
7	Virtually implement the network expansion or ECMs in the virtual lab/model.	Digital Twin of the facility.
8	Find low efficiency or pain points by studying and analyzing the different KPIs.	Optimization of the operation of the network.
9	Creation of a model-based O&M plan in order to optimize the costs.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.
10	Implementation of network expansion or ECMs.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.7

Involved Persona

Profit-oriented DHN designer.

Related User story

As a Profit-oriented DHN designer, **I want to** get a better understanding of how the facility operates, **so that** the design can be better adapted to the specifications.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available precise baseline design. • Available databases with the characteristic of each area (type of buildings, estimated consumption, etc.). • Historical weather data are available for each area.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced DHN designing efforts. • Increased accuracy of the DHNs design.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Develop a detailed baseline design.	
3	Creation an operational model of the baseline design, based on an existing model of a real DHN.	AI-based model of the facility.
4	Calibration and adjustment of the operational model with the help of AI	AI-based model of the facility.
5	Recognize how the different configurations affect the facility operation.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
6	Gathering details of the installation to be designed (type of buildings, weather conditions, historical data, etc.).	
7	Design of the new facility taking into account the previous details.	
8	The final design of the DHN.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.8

Involved Persona

Profit-oriented DHN designer.

Related User story

As a Profit-oriented DHN designer, I want to get an accurate DHN baseline model, **so that** it is simpler to design the installation in a more efficient and cost-effective way.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available precise baseline design. • Available characterized database.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced DHN designing efforts. • Increased accuracy of the DHNs design.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Develop a detailed baseline design.	
3	Creation of an operational model of the baseline design based on an existing model of a real DHN.	AI-based model of the facility.
4	Calibration and adjustment of the operational model with the help of AI.	AI-based model of the facility.
5	Recognize how the different configurations affect the facility operation.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
6	Gathering details of the installation to be designed (type of buildings, weather conditions, historical data, etc.).	
7	Design of the new facility taking into account the previous details.	
8	The final design of the DHN.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.9

Involved Persona

Benefit-oriented bank.

Related User story

As a Benefit-oriented bank, **I want to** minimize the risk of DHN renovations investments, **so that** I can invest in more facilities with conviction and obtain profit.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the energy savings prior the investment. • Deep knowledge of the impact of DHN renovations.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the number of investments. • Increase the profit.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Data gathering from the DHN (energy invoices at least).	
2	Evaluation of the effect of the different possible refurbishments (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
3	Predictive accurate analysis of the production and energy consumption before and after the renovation (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
4	Predictive analysis of the profit and the ROI (by the ESCO) linking the energy savings with the economy. Communicate the results to the bank and explanation.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Investment in the renovation of the DHN.	
6	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as the profit generated.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.10

Involved Persona

Benefit-oriented bank.

Related User story

As a Benefit-oriented bank, **I want to** accurately predict the profit and the return on investment when making this kind of investment, **so that** I can make a better forecast about my investment plan.

Usage Scenario conditions

- | | |
|----------------------|---|
| Precondition | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the energy savings prior the investment. • Deep knowledge of the impact of each Energy Conservation Measure (ECM). |
| Postcondition | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the number of investments. • Increase the profit and reduce de ROI. |

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Data gathering from the DHN (energy invoices at least).	
2	Predictive accurate analysis of the production and the consumption of energy before and after the renovation, evaluating the impact of the refurbishment.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
3	Predictive analysis of the profit and the ROI (by the ESCO) linking the energy savings with the economy.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
4	Investment in the implementation of ECMs.	
5	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as profit generated.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.11

Involved Persona

Benefit-oriented bank.

Related User story

As a Benefit-oriented bank, **I want to** match energy savings to profit, **so that** I can comprehend the upsides.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Estimation of the energy savings prior the investment.
Postcondition	Increase the profit.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Data gathering from the DHN (energy invoices at least).	
2	Development of an AI-based model of the facility to control it (by the ESCO).	AI-based model of the facility.
3	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	AI-based model of the facility.
4	Recognize how the different ECMs impact on the facility operation (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Investment in the implementation of ECMs.	
6	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as profit generated.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.12

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter bank.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter bank, **I want to** predict the economic and environmental impact of the DHN renovations, **so that** I can understand the upsides of the intervention, helping me to decide.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the energy savings before the investment. • Deep knowledge of the impact of each Energy Conservation Measure (ECM).
Postconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the number of investments. • Increase the profit. • Reduction of GHG emissions.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Data gathering from the DHN (energy invoices at least).	
2	Development of a model of the installation (by the ESCO).	AI-based model of the facility.
3	Evaluation of the effect, both economic and environmental, of the different possible refurbishments (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
4	Investment in the implementation of ECMs.	
5	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as the environmental impact.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.13

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter bank.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter bank, I want to increase the ROI on my investment, so that I can encourage more energy efficiency interventions.

Usage Scenario conditions

Precondition

- Estimation of the energy savings before the investment.
- Deep knowledge of the impact of each Energy Conservation Measure (ECM).

Postcondition

- Boost the number of investments.
- Increase the profit.
- Reduction of GHG emissions.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Data gathering from the DHN (energy invoices at least)	
2	Development of an AI-based model of the facility to control it (by the ESCO).	AI-based model of the facility.
3	Evaluation of the effect, both economic and environmental, of the possible refurbishments (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
4	Investment in the implementation of ECMs.	
5	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as the environmental impact.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.14

Involved Persona

Informed owner.

Related User story

As an Informed owner, **I want to** benefit from an EP Contract, **so that** I can avoid the initial costs of the DHN renovation.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are not installed. • There is only global energy consumption data available for the baseline period. • Estimation of energy savings. • Estimation of the implementation's cost.
Postcondition	Energy Performance Contract signed.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
	MODEL CREATION	Measurement and verification of energy savings (IPMVP).
1	Development of a new IPMVP.	
2	Definition of the ECMs to be implemented (by the user).	
3	Baseline period establishment.	
4	Independent variables definition.	
5	Provision of the data for the baseline period (by the user).	
6	Selection of the confidence level of the building model.	
7	Adjusted Baseline Energy (ABE) Modelling selection.	
8	Adjusted Baseline Energy (ABE) Modelling creation.	
9	Reporting period definition.	
	INTERACTION WITH OWNERS	
10	EP Contract signed.	
11	Implementation of ECMs with no upfront cost.	
12	Reports on the energy and money savings.	
13	Payment of the implementation through the economic savings generated.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 3.15

Involved Persona

Informed owner.

Related User story

As an Informed owner, **I want** the facility to be more efficient, **so that** there is an increase of service availability and comfort.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Meters (SMs) are not installed. There is only global energy consumption data available for the baseline period.
Postconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EP Contract signed. Decrease of failures and breakdowns in the facility. Decrease of the O&M costs.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Identification of the installation's main components.	
3	Analysis of the available data.	
4	EP Contract signed.	
5	SMs installation.	
6	Design the facility's monitoring system and the connection to the control and central monitoring system.	
7	Definition of relevant installation's KPIs.	
8	Development of an AI-based operational model of the facility to control it.	of an AI-based model of the facility.
9	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model during the operation of the facility, while also adjusting the critical KPIs.	AI-based model of the facility.
10	Creation of a model-based O&M plan.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.
11	Optimization of the installation's operating parameters according to the results of the model created.	Optimization of the operation of the network.
12	Report on energy and economic savings.	

5.5.2.2 Use Case 4: AI for energy saving verification service, increasing the trust on Energy Performance Contracts

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.1

Involved Persona

Advanced ESCO.

Related User story

As an Advanced ESCO, **I want to** implement energy efficiency measures in different facilities, **so that** the efficiency of these facilities is reduced, lowering costs and GHG emissions.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Efficiency Measures (ECMs) are going to be implemented in the building. • Existing global energy consumption bills of the building for the baseline period. • Estimation of the energy savings. • Estimation of the GHG emissions reduction.
Postconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of the ECMs. • Reduction of energy consumption. • Decrease GHG emissions. • Reduction of the costs.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
	MODEL CREATION	Measurement and verification of energy savings (IPMVP).
1	Development of a new IPMVP.	
2	Definition of the ECMs to be implemented (by the user).	
3	Baseline period establishment.	
4	Independent variables definition.	
5	Provision of the data for the baseline period (by the user).	
6	Selection of the confidence level of the building model	
7	Adjusted Baseline Energy (ABE) Modelling selection	
8	Adjusted Baseline Energy (ABE) Modelling creation	
9	Reporting period definition.	
	MEASUREMENTS IMPLEMENTATION	
10	The user provides data of energy consumption after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (consumption and energy price)	
11	Reports on energy and money-saving.	
12	Reports on GHG emissions reduction.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.2

Involved Persona

Advanced ESCO.

Related User story

As an Advanced ESCO, **I want** to be able to obtain accurate energy savings predictions, **so that** the EP Contracts are calculated with more precision.

Usage Scenario conditions

Precondition s

- Energy Efficiency Measures (ECMs) are going to be implemented in the building.
- Existing global energy consumption invoices of the building for the baseline period.

Postcondition

- EP Contract calculated.
- Accurate estimation of the energy savings.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collection of data from the building (at least energy invoices).	
2	Data analytics.	
3	Development of an AI-based model of the facility.	AI-based model of the facility.
	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	AI-based model of the facility.
4	Accurate prediction of the energy savings when implementing the ECM.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Calculation of the EP Contract.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.3

Involved Persona

EPC Facilitator.

Related User story

As an EP Contract facilitator, I want to show the economic and environmental benefits of introducing energy efficiency measures in the buildings, **so that** owners can encourage the building or facility renovation.

Usage Scenario conditions

Precondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Efficiency Measures (ECMs) are going to be implemented in the buildings. Existing global energy consumption bills of the building for the baseline period.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accurate information about the facilities' behaviour before and after an intervention. Precise forecast of the profit and energy savings.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collection of data from the building and analysis.	
2	Definition of the ECMs that are going to be carried out.	
3	Development of an AI-based model of the facility.	Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	Digital Twin of the facility.
5	Introduce the different ECMs in the model.	Digital Twin of the facility.
6	Forecast of the energy savings and profit when implementing the different ECMs.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility. Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption.
7	Communication with the owners.	
8	EP Contract signed and ECMs implementation.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.4

Involved Persona

EPC Facilitator.

Related User story

As an EPC facilitator, I want to provide reliable information about the behaviour of the facilities before and after an intervention, **so that** owners realise the upsides of the energy efficiency measures.

Usage Scenario conditions

- | | |
|-----------------------|---|
| Preconditions | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Efficiency Measures (ECMs) are going to be implemented in the building. • Existing global energy consumption bills of the building for the baseline period. |
| Postconditions | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Precise information about the facilities' behaviour before and after an intervention • Accurate prediction of the profit and energy savings of each Energy Conservation Measure (ECM). • Implementation of the ECM. |

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collection of data from the building (at least energy invoices).	
2	Data analytics.	
3	Development of an AI-based model of the facility.	Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	Digital Twin of the facility.
5	Accurate knowledge about baseline parameters of the facility.	
6	Definition of the ECMs that are going to be carried out.	
7	Prediction of the energy and economic savings after the ECM is carried out.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
8	An EP Contract is signed and implementation of the ECMs.	
9	Reports on energy and cost savings.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.5

Involved Persona

Benefit-oriented bank.

Related User story

As a Benefit-oriented bank, **I want to** decrease the risk in the Investment in energy efficiency measure, **so that** allow me to be more likely to participate in or provide credit for this type of business.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the energy savings prior to the investment. • Deep knowledge of the Energy Conservation Measure (ECM) impact.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the number of investments. • Increase the profit.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collection of data from the building (at least energy invoices).	
2	Data analytics.	
3	Develop a baseline model based on the historical data (energy invoices) to predict the future behaviour of the facility.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Impact evaluation of the ECMs (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Decision of the ECM that is going to be implemented (by the user).	
6	Accurate prediction of the energy and economic savings, and also the ROI.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility. Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption.
7	Investment in the ECMs.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.6

Involved Persona

Benefit-oriented bank.

Related User story

As a Benefit-oriented bank, **I want to** accurately predict the return on investment and the profit obtained when making this kind of investment, **so that** I can make better predictions about my investment plan.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the energy savings prior the investment. • Deep knowledge of the Energy Conservation Measure (ECM) impact.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the number of investments. • Increase the profit and reduce the ROI.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collection of data from the building (at least energy invoices).	
2	Data analytics.	
3	Develop a baseline model based on the historical data (energy invoices) to predict the future behaviour of the facility.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Impact evaluation of the ECMs (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Decision of the ECM that is going to be implemented (by the user).	
6	Accurate prediction of the energy and economic savings, and also the ROI.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility. Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption.
7	Investment in the ECMs.	
8	Reports on energy and cost, savings and on the profit generated.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.7

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter bank.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter bank, I want to predict the economic and environmental impact of the energy efficiency measures, so that I can understand the advantages of the intervention, helping me to decide.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the energy savings prior the investment. • Deep knowledge of the ECM's impact.
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Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the number of investments. • Increase the profit. • Reduce the emissions of GHG.
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Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collection of data from the building (at least energy invoices).	
2	Data analytics.	
3	Develop a baseline model based on the historical data (energy invoices) to predict the future behaviour of the facility.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Impact evaluation of the ECMs (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Decision of the ECM that is going to be implemented (by the user).	
6	Accurate prediction of the energy and economic savings, and also the ROI.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility. Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption.
7	Estimation of the environmental impact of the ECM implementation.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility. Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption.
8	Investment in the ECMs.	
9	Reports on energy and cost, savings and on the profit generated.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.8

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter bank.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter bank, I want to increase the ROI on my investment, so that I can encourage more energy efficiency interventions.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the energy savings prior the investment. • Deep knowledge of the ECM's impact.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the number of investments. • Increase the profit and reduce the ROI.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collection of data from the building (at least energy invoices).	
2	Data analytics.	
3	Develop a baseline model based on the historical data (energy invoices) to predict the future behaviour of the facility.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Impact evaluation of the ECMs (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Decision of the ECM that is going to be implemented (by the user).	
6	Accurate prediction of the energy and economic savings, and also the ROI.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility. Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption.
7	Estimation of the environmental impact of the ECM implementation.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility. Energy demand prediction to optimize the energy consumption.
8	Investment in the ECMs.	
9	Reports on energy and cost, savings and on the profit generated.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.9

Involved Persona

Motivated owner.

Related User story

As a Motivated owner, **I want to** persuade other owners of the upsides of energy efficiency interventions, **so that** they become encouraged to implement these measures too.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available EP Certificate of the building. • SMs (Smart Meters) installed. • Monitoring data (historical data available).
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of the ECM. • Estimation of the energy savings.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Gather the monitoring data.	
2	Development of a new IPMVP (by the ESCO).	Measurement and verification of energy savings (IPMVP).
3	Predictive analysis on production and consumption of energy, and also of economic savings of each ECM.	Energy demand prediction to optimize the energy consumption.
4	Show the owners accurate energy and economic predictions, and also the environmental impact, of the implementation of the different ECMs	Energy demand prediction to optimize the energy consumption.
5	Implementation of the ECMs decided.	
6	Reports on energy and economic saving, and GHG emissions reduction.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.10

Involved Persona

Motivated owner.

Related User story

As a Motivated owner, I want to avoid the initial costs of the interventions by using EP Contracts, **so that** the energy efficiency intervention can be carried out even if I can't afford it

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existing bills of the global energy consumption of the building for the Baseline period (Option C of the IPMVP). Estimation of energy savings. Estimation of the cost of the implementation.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of ECMs. Upfront costs avoided.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
	MODEL CREATION	Measurement and verification of energy savings (IPMVP).
1	Development of a new IPMVP.	
2	Definition of the ECMs to be implemented (by the user).	
3	Baseline period establishment.	
4	Independent variables definition.	
5	Provision of the data for the baseline period (by the user).	
6	Selection of the confidence level of the building model	
7	Adjusted Baseline Energy (ABE) Modelling selection	
8	Adjusted Baseline Energy (ABE) Modelling creation	
9	Reporting period definition.	
	INTERACTION WITH OWNERS	
10	EP Contract signed.	
11	Implementation of the ECMs with no upfront cost.	
12	Reports on the energy and money savings.	
13	Implementation paid through the economic savings generated.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 4.11

Involved Persona

Motivated owner.

Related User story

As a Motivated owner, **I want to** implement energy efficiency measures to my building, **so that** it increases the value of the building.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EP Certificate of the building available. • Existing invoices of the global energy consumption of the building for the Baseline period. • Estimation of energy savings.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of ECMs. • Increase the value of the building.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
	MODEL CREATION	Measurement and verification of energy savings (IPMVP).
1	Development of a new IPMVP.	
2	Definition of the ECMs to be implemented (by the user).	
3	Baseline period establishment.	
4	Independent variables definition.	
5	Provision of the data for the baseline period (by the user).	
6	Selection of the confidence level of the building model	
7	Adjusted Baseline Energy (ABE) Modelling selection	
8	Adjusted Baseline Energy (ABE) Modelling creation	
9	Reporting period definition.	
	INTERACTION WITH OWNERS	
10	Owners see the results of the model and realise about the benefits of ECMs	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
11	EP Contract signed.	
12	Implementation of the ECMs	
13	Reports on the energy and money savings.	
14	Certification of the building	

5.5.2.3 Use Case 5: AI for multi energy systems decision-support - Reina Sofia

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.1

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter FM.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter FM, **I want to** get a better understanding of how the facility operates, **so that** the failures decrease, the efficiency increases and the production mix can be optimized.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are installed and available. • Facilities are connected to centralized control and to a monitoring system. • Historical data are available.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease of failures and breakdowns in the facility. • Decrease of the O&M costs. • Increase of efficiency.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Identification of the installation's main components.	
3	Definition of relevant installation's KPIs.	
4	Development of an AI-based model of the facility to control it.	of an AI-based model of the facility.
5	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	AI-based model of the facility.
6	Find low efficiency or pain points by studying and analyzing the different KPIs.	Optimization of the operation of the network.
7	Creation of a model-based O&M plan.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.
8	Implementation of appropriate corrections and modifications in the installation based on the model results in order to achieve an improvement on the production mix.	Optimization of the production mix.
9	Creation of a strategy to optimize the production mix based on the weather forecast for the next 3 days based on the existing model.	Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption. Optimization of the production mix.

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.2

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter FM.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter FM, **I want to** forecast accurately the facility’s behaviour and its response to potential changes, **so that** the energy consumption and the GHG emissions are reduced.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are installed. • Facilities are connected to centralized control and to a monitoring system. • Historical weather data are available.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce energy consumption. • Reduce GHG emissions.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation’s available data.	
2	Identification of the installation’s main components.	
3	Development of an AI-based model of the facility to control it.	AI-based model of the facility.
4	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	AI-based model of the facility.
5	Forecast the behaviour of the facility depending on the different renovation that could be implemented in the installation.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
6	Develop an accurate weather prediction.	Weather forecast.
7	Forecast the behaviour of the facility according to weather forecasts.	Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption.
8	Creation of a strategy to optimize the production mix based on the weather forecast for the next 3 days based on the existing model.	Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption. Optimization of the production mix.
9	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as reductions in GHG emissions.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.3

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter FM.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter FM, I want to get an accurate facility model, **so that** new energy efficiency measures can be implemented more easily and the production mix can be optimized.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are installed. • Facilities are connected to centralized control and to a monitoring system. • There is historical monitored data available. • Accurate weather forecast available.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease of failures and breakdowns in the facility. • Decrease of the O&M costs.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Precise analysis of the operation of the facility.	
3	Identification of the installation's main components.	
4	Definition of relevant installation's KPIs.	
5	Develop an AI-based model of the facility to control it.	Digital Twin of the facility.
6	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	Digital Twin of the facility.
7	Virtually implement the upgrades or ECMs in the virtual lab/model.	Digital Twin of the facility.
8	Find low efficiency or pain points by studying and analyzing the different KPIs.	Optimization of the operation of the network.
9	Creation of a model-based O&M plan.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.
10	Implementation of appropriate corrections and modifications in the installation based on the model results in order to achieve an improvement on the production mix.	Optimization of the production mix.
11	Creation of a strategy to optimize the production mix based on the weather forecast for the next 3 days.	Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption. Optimization of the production mix.

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.4

Involved Persona

Cost-conscious FM.

Related User story

As a Cost-conscious FM, **I want to** get a better understanding of how the facility operates, **so that** the failures and costs are reduced, and the efficiency is increased.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are installed. • There is historical monitored data available.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase the efficiency of the facility. • Reduction of the costs reduction.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Precise analysis of the operation of the facility.	
3	Develop an AI-based model of the facility.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
5	Find low efficiency or pain points by studying and analyzing the results of the model.	Optimization of the operation of the network.
6	Creation of a model-based O&M plan.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.
7	Reports on energy and cost, savings and on the profit generated.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.5

Involved Persona

Cost-conscious FM.

Related User story

As a Cost-conscious FM, I want to forecast accurately the facility’s behaviour and its response to potential changes, **so that** there is a de-risking when implementing energy efficiency measures.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Meters (SMs) are installed. There is historical monitored data available. Accurate weather prediction.
Postcondition	Implementation of upgrades and energy efficiency measures.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation’s available data.	
2	Identification of the installation’s main components.	
3	Definition of relevant installation’s KPIs.	
4	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility, including the forecast of the KPIs, energy performance, ROI and profit.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as reductions in GHG emissions.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.6

Involved Persona

Cost-conscious FM.

Related User story

As a Cost-conscious FM, **I want to** get an accurate facility model, **so that** the costs of implementing new energy efficiency measures and of the optimization of the production mix are reduced due to the selection of the best choice.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Meters (SMs) are installed. There is historical monitored data available. Accurate weather forecast.
Postcondition	Upgrades in the facility.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation’s available data.	
2	Identification of the installation’s main components.	
3	Definition of relevant installation’s KPIs.	
4	Precise analysis of the operation of the facility.	
5	Development of based model of the facility to control it.	an AI-AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
6	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
7	Virtually implement the upgrades or ECMs in the virtual lab/model.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
8	Find low efficiency or pain points by studying and analyzing the different KPIs.	Optimization of the operation of the network.
9	Creation of a model-based O&M plan in order to minimize the costs.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.
10	Implementation of appropriate corrections and modifications in the installation based on the model results in order to achieve an improvement on the production-mix.	Optimization of the production mix.
11	Creation of a strategy to optimize the production mix based on the weather forecast for the next 3 days.	Energy demand prediction to optimize energy consumption. Optimization of the production mix.
12	Implementation of facility’s upgrades.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.7

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter bank.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter bank, **I want to** predict the economic and environmental impact of the facility optimization, **so that** I can understand the upsides of the intervention, helping me to decide where to invest.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the energy savings before the investment. • Deep knowledge of the impact of each upgrade or Energy Conservation Measure (ECM).
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the number of investments. • Increase the profit. • Reduction of GHG emissions.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Data gathering from the facility (energy invoices at least).	
2	Development of an AI-based model of the facility to control it (by the ESCO).	AI-based model of the facility.
3	Evaluation of the effect, both economic and environmental, of the different possible upgrades or ECMs (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
4	Investment in the implementation of the upgrades or ECMs.	
5	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as the environmental impact.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.8

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporter bank.

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporter bank, I want to increase the ROI on my investment, so that I can encourage more energy efficiency interventions.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Estimation of the energy savings prior to the investment. • Deep knowledge of the upgrades or ECM's impact.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Boost the number of investments. • Increase the profit and reduce the ROI. • Reduction of GHG emissions.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Data gathering from the facility (energy invoices at least).	
2	Development of an AI-based model of the facility to control it (by the ESCO).	AI-based model of the facility.
3	Evaluation of the effect, both economic and environmental, of the different possible upgrades or ECMs (by the ESCO).	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
4	Investment in the implementation of upgrades or ECMs.	
5	Report on energy and economic savings, as well as the environmental impact.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.9

Involved Persona

Efficiency-oriented designer.

Related User story

As an Efficiency-oriented designer, **I want to** easily understand how the facility operates, **so that** I have an accurate picture of how the facility works depending on the different configuration that can be suggested.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Available precise standard network design. • Available databases with the characteristic of each area (type of buildings, estimated consumption, etc.). • Historical weather data are available for each area.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease the effort in the design of the upgrades. • Increased accuracy of the installations design.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Creation of an operational model of the standard network design, based on an existing model of a real facility.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
3	Calibration and adjustment of the operational model with the help of AI.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Recognize how the different configurations affect the facility operation.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
5	Gathering details of the installation to be designed (type of buildings, weather conditions, historical data, etc.).	
6	Design of the new facility taking into account the previous details.	
7	The final design of the facility.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.10

Involved Persona

Efficiency-oriented designer.

Related User story

As an Efficiency-oriented designer, **I want to** get accurate TMY (Typical Meteorological Year), **so that** the installation is designed accurately.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are installed and available. • Facilities are connected to centralized control and to a monitoring system. • Historical data are available. • Accurate weather predictions.
Postcondition	Increased accuracy of the facility design.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Develop a detailed baseline design.	
3	Creation of an operational model of the baseline design, based on an existing model of a real facility.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Calibration and adjustment of the operational model with the help of AI.	AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
5	Forecast the behaviour of the facility depending on the different renovation that could be implemented in the installation.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
6	Forecast the behaviour of the facility according to the TMY.	Prediction of the behaviour of the facility.
7	Design the upgrades taking into account the previous details.	
8	The final design of the facility.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 5.11

Involved Persona

Efficiency-oriented designer.

Related User story

As an Efficiency-oriented designer, **I want to** provide the manager with an accurate model of the installation, **so that** he is able to manage it properly.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Smart Meters (SMs) are installed and available. • Facilities are connected to centralized control and to a monitoring system. • Historical data are available. • Accurate weather predictions.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decrease of failures and breakdowns in the facility. • Decrease of the O&M costs. • Reduce energy consumption. • Reduce GHG emissions.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Identification of the installation's available data.	
2	Identification of the installation's main components.	
3	Development of an AI-based model of the facility to control it.	of an AI-based model or Digital Twin of the facility.
4	Iterative validation and adjustment of the model.	
5	Optimization of the installation's operating parameters according to the results of the model created.	Optimization of the operation of the network.
6	Creation of a model-based O&M plan.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service.

5.5.3 Pilot 3

5.5.3.1 Use Case 6: Cross-functional AI-based predictive analytics to support integrated DSOs asset management and network operation

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 6.1

Involved Persona

Informed utility manager

Related User story

As an Informed utility manager, **I want to** adopt innovative scheduling programmes for maintenance **so that** I can reduce the cost for equipment replacement, penalties related to interruptions and I can improve the maintenance activities.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	The maintenance programmes are not optimised and the Informed utility manager faces several problems related to equipment replacement.
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Postcondition	The maintenance programmes allow reducing the cost for equipment maintenance and interruptions.
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Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The assets of the distribution network that need maintenance programmes are analysed.	Health status evaluation of electrical lines and transformers service
2	Data about maintenance operation are collected and manipulated.	
3	AI-based model of maintenance programmes is elaborated.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service
4	Scenarios with old and new scheduling programmes are studied.	
5	Informed utility manager validates and implements the new scheduling programmes.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 6.2

Involved Persona

Head of the maintenance service

Related User story

As a Head of maintenance, **I want** to use analytics to increase the efficiency of my activities, **so that** I can improve the performances of my department.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Maintenance activity is not optimized and the Head of the maintenance service faces several problems related to equipment replacement.
Postcondition	Maintenance activity have increased their efficiency and have achieved savings.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Current maintenance programmes are analysed in detail	Health status evaluation of electrical lines and transformers service
2	Data about maintenance operation are collected and manipulated.	
3	AI-based model of maintenance programmes is elaborated.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service
4	Scenarios with old and new scheduling programmes are studied.	
5	Head of maintenance services validates and implements the new scheduling programmes.	

5.5.3.2 Use Case 7: AI-based consumption and flexibility prediction for local community optimal aggregation and flexibility trading

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 7.1

Involved Persona

Informed utility manager

Related User story

As an Informed utility manager, **I want to** support the deployment of a flexibility marketplace, **so that** I can participate in the new business model and improve network reliability.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	The flexibility sources are spread in the distribution network but non exploited for improving the distribution network operation.
Postcondition	A flexibility marketplace is deployed in which the DSO can make flexibility requests to better balance the power consumption and production.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The flexibility sources among the distribution network are deeply analysed and categorised.	Flexibility evaluation of assets service
2	A new business model, with a DSO suitable rule, is modelled.	
3	A predictive analysis of production and consumption profiles is carried out.	Production and consumption forecasting service
4	Flexibility exchange between assets is tested and validated by the responsible for the distribution network.	
5	Economic benefits derived from the business model are evaluated and reported.	Technical-economic impact service

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 7.2

Involved Persona

Head of the network operation/ remote management

Related User story

As a Head of the network operation, **I want to** use flexibility in order to manage the distribution network, **so that** I can reduce issues on the distribution grid and improve awareness about the current status of the infrastructure.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	The flexibility sources are spread in the distribution network but non exploited for improving the distribution network operation.
Postcondition	Through flexibility services congestions and other faults in the grid have been reduced and the management of the grid has been optimized.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The flexibility sources among the distribution network are deeply analysed and categorised.	Flexibility evaluation of assets service
2	A new business model, with a DSO suitable rule, is modelled.	
3	Predictive analysis of production and consumption profiles is carried out.	Production and consumption forecasting service
4	Flexibility exchange between assets is tested and validated by the responsible for the distribution network.	
5	Technological benefits derived from the business model are evaluated and reported.	Technical-economic impact service

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 7.3

Involved Persona

Aggregator

Related User story

As an Aggregator, **I want** to participate to flexibility marketplace including customers in a pool, **so that** I can make profits and build up a robust business model.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	The flexibility sources are spread in the distribution network but non exploited for improving the distribution network operation.
Postcondition	The Aggregator has built up a robust business model that allows him to make profits

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The aggregator estimates the amount of flexibility that can be provided by the system	
2	An AI model that allows the management of flexibility service is produced	Identification of optimized flexibility service
3	A platform to support flexibility market is realized	
4	Ways to engage customers in the flexibility market are identified.	
5	Peer to peer communications and contracts are tested and validated	P2P technology testing

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 7.4

Involved Persona

Energy consumers

Related User story

As an Energy consumer, **I want to** take economic advantage, **so that** I can reduce the cost for equipment replacement, penalties related to interruptions and I can improve the maintenance activities.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	The service provided to end consumers is not optimized and the energy consumer faces a high cost for maintenance and replacement of components. SM is installed and available
Postcondition	Flexibility services have allowed Energy consumer to reduce costs for maintenance and equipment replacement.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	An analysis of energy costs associated with operation and maintenance activities is made.	Historical data analysis service
2	Through a technical-economic analysis the flexibility services that can be provided to the market are identified	Flexibility evaluation of assets service
3	The most suitable economic offer on the market for the service to be provided is identified	
4	A technical-economic comparison is made between the benefits that would be obtained over time and the necessary expenses	Technical-economic impact service
5	All necessary equipment is installed	
6	Participation in the flexibility market with P2P contracts is performed and assessed over time	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 7.5

Involved Persona

Prosumers

Related User story

As a prosumer, **I want to** adopt technologies that enable participation to flexibility marketplace, **so that** I can improve the awareness about consumption and increase economic benefits

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	There is a market for flexibility within which the prosumer can perform services. Market entry procedures are simple and clear. SM are installed and available
Postcondition	Prosumer is completely aware about his consumption and his behaviour allowed him to make important savings.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	An analysis was done to identify the flexibility services that the prosumer is able to provide	Flexibility evaluation of assets service
2	The provider researches on the market for an aggregator that provides adequate remuneration for the service provided.	
3	A cost-benefit analysis is carried out to establish whether it is worthwhile to enter the flexibility mechanism.	Technical-economic impact service
4	The provider is equipped with all the necessary devices to guarantee the service (smart meters, storage systems...)	
5	Participation in the flexibility market with P2P contracts is performed and assessed over time	

5.5.3.3 Use Case 8: AI-based energy-driven and non-energy services

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 8.1

Involved Persona

Informed utility manager

Related User story

As an Informed utility manager, **I want to** provide new services and analytics to the final users, **so that** I can increase the interaction with them leading energy transition which is customer centric.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	The end customers are not sufficiently encouraged by the DSO to support the energy transition.
Postcondition	The DSO provides new technologies to increase the interaction with final users and to encourage new sustainable production and consumption management systems.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The existing and available interaction methods with final users are analysed and discussed with the responsible for the distribution network.	
2	Models of end user's behaviour are realized regarding a heterogeneous type of customers.	Customer's behaviour modelling service
3	The social-economic impact of the interaction's improvement between DSO and final users is evaluated.	
4	Scenarios related to new sustainable production and consumption management systems are simulated and tested in the pilot.	
5	The Informed utility manager schedules a plan of infrastructure reinforcement and customers engagement.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 8.2

Involved Persona

Manager of the water system

Related User story

As a Manager of the water system, **I want to** adopt innovative scheduling programmes for the pumps, **so that** I can increase energy efficiency, participate in new business model related to energy flexibility.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Pump operation provides some marginal flexibility that can provide services to the electrical grid. SM are installed and available
Postcondition	Through flexibility services the energy efficiency of the pump operation has increased, allowing economic savings.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The operation of the water pump is analysed taking into account energy consumption and related costs.	Historical data analysis service
2	Data about pump operation are collected and manipulated.	
3	AI-based model of pump operation is elaborated.	
4	Scenarios with old and new scheduling programmes are studied.	Identification of optimized maintenance programmes service
5	The manager of the water system validates and implements the new scheduling programmes.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 8.3

Involved Persona

Technology-aware owner

Related User story

As a Technology-aware owner, **I want to** adopt new services that estimate my flexibility taking into account my needs, **so that** I can participate in energy flexibility marketplace.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Flexibility services are advertised and known by consumers. Market entry procedures are simple and clear. SM are installed and available
Postcondition	The owner is aware of all available flexibility services and is involved in a flexibility market that can produce economic savings.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	An analysis of energy costs associated with operation and maintenance activities is made.	Historical data analysis service
2	Through a technical-economic analysis the flexibility services that can be provided to the market are identified	Flexibility evaluation of assets service
3	The most suitable economic offer on the market for the service to be provided is identified	
4	A technical-economic comparison is made between the benefits that would be obtained over time and the necessary expenses	Technical-economic impact service
5	All necessary equipment is installed (SM, storage systems, controllers...)	
6	Technology aware owner validates and implements the new operation mechanism	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 8.4

Involved Persona

Technology-hater owner

Related User story

As a Technology-hater owner, **I want to** receive static analytics of my consumption patterns, **so that** I can evaluate the feasibility and usefulness of adopting technologies that enable participation in the energy flexibility market.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Flexibility services are clearly advertised and certified by known bodies (institutions, consumer associations...). SM are installed and available
Postcondition	The owner is fully informed about his consumption and the possible savings he would get from flexibility services and his choice to join or not to join flexibility markets is conscious.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	An analysis of energy costs associated with operation and maintenance activities is made.	Historical data analysis service
2	Through a technical-economic analysis the flexibility services that can be provided to the market are identified	Flexibility evaluation of assets service
3	The most suitable economic offer on the market for the service to be provided is identified	
4	A technical-economic comparison is made between the benefits that would be obtained over time and the necessary expenses	Technical-economic impact service
6	Technology hater owner evaluates and compares the different possibilities, consciously making the most convenient choice for himself.	

5.5.4 Pilot 4

5.5.4.1 Use Case 9: AI-based IoT-enabled PV module-level portfolio optimal predictive maintenance and PV-enhanced industrial plant optimal operation

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 9.1

Involved Persona

O&M manager

Related User story

As an O&M manager, I want to evaluate new technical solutions, **so that** I can apply more efficient procedures on-site for reducing electrical faults, the number of interventions, use of spare parts and costs. The new procedure should be time-saving for improving the work conditions on-site.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Availability of asset technical specifications. Data availability. Weather data availability. Data pushing towards I-nergy FTP server.
Postcondition	Predictive maintenance scheduling service. Time saving service. Report of asset health state.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Definition of the service specifications	Predictive maintenance analytics
2	Definition of the asset specifications	Asset mapping
3	Data pushing towards I-nergy FTP server in place	Data transfer
4	Definition of a forecasting algorithm	PV forecasting
5	Machine learning for PV forecasting algorithm	Service development
6	The service is tested in a real environment	Predictive maintenance analytics, visual analytics
7	The service predictions are confirmed on-site and the O&M manager validates the model	Service validation
8	The predictive maintenance service is applied regularly	Service validation

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 9.2

Involved Persona

Asset manager/ Owner representative

Related User story

An an asset manager, **I want to** evaluate innovative, more efficient technical solutions, **so that** I can reduce the stops of the plants which are usually needed for carrying out maintenance. I am also interested in increasing the production, the environmental/energy benefits for the community and the economic ones for the investors.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Availability of reliable innovative tools. Trained maintenance contractors.
Postcondition	Good benefit/cost ratio

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Definition of the service reliability and cost	Predictive maintenance analytics, visual analytics
2	The service is tested in a real environment	Predictive maintenance analytics, visual analytics
3	Old and new procedures and results are compared	Service validation
4	The service is definitively implemented on site.	Service validation

5.5.5 Pilot 5

5.5.5.1 Use Case 10: AI in EV charging infrastructure

Usage Scenario ID
Usage Scenario 10.1

Involved Persona
DSO

Related User story
As an operator of the distribution network, **I want to** integrate EV charging stations into the grid to monitor and control voltage stability as well as power reliability, **so that** it can provide services to flatten the demand during peak hours.

Usage Scenario conditions	
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The flexibility resources are spread in the distribution network, • Existence of smart meter gateways, • Metering data is successfully collected and historical metering data is available, • Appropriate communication protocols.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful communication between the grid and the EVs, • Smart metering infrastructure is operational for supporting grid monitoring and estimation, • A local energy management system is deployed to make use of the flexibility resources.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario		
Step	Action	Service
1	The flexibility resources in the distribution network are monitored and analysed	Visual analytics
2	Monitor EV state of charge	Visual analytics
3	Monitor EV current and history state (incl. energy measurements)	Visual analytics
4	Review EV charging stations occupancy status	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
5	Assess historical and upcoming charging reservation per station	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
6	Day-ahead forecast for charging station occupancy	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 10.2

Involved Persona

Retailer

Related User story

As a retailer, I want to broaden my flexibility pool and deploy demand-side flexibility, **so that I** foster active participation in flexibility market-based programs for favouring dynamic pricing of EV charging.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-user engagement and consideration of user preferences, • EVs are grouped according to their preferences and charging plans, • Existence of smart meters, • Metering data is successfully collected and historical metering data is available, • Hourly wholesale prices are available, • EVs able to shift the start of and/or modulate power consumption, • Appropriate communication protocols.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leverage flexibility in electric vehicle charging, • Develop an application with the support of a technology provider to create incentive schemas in optimal EV charging, • User engagement for peak demand and carbon footprint reduction.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	All available EVs are monitored and analysed	Visual analytics
2	Monitor EV state of charge	Visual analytics
3	Monitor EV current and history state (incl. energy measurements)	Visual analytics
4	Review EV charging stations occupancy status	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
5	Assess historical and upcoming charging reservation per station	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
6	Clusters of EVs owners are identified according to their charging preferences and consumption patterns	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
7	Day-ahead forecast for charging station occupancy	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
8	Proposal of variable pricing schema to EV charging owners	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 10.3

Involved Persona

EV user/owner

Related User story

As an EV owner/user, I want to charge during times when the energy cost is lower and get my EV fully charged as fast as needed, so that I save more money and get my EV charged without losing time.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End-user engagement and consideration of user preferences, • EV owner/user must have control of an EV and have an EV charger installed, • Existence of smart meters, • Metering data is successfully collected and historical metering data is available, • Hourly wholesale prices are available, • EVs able to shift the start of and/or modulate power consumption, • Appropriate communication protocols.
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leverage flexibility in electric vehicle charging, • Develop an application with the support of a technology provider to create incentive schemas in optimal EV charging, • User engagement for peak demand and carbon footprint reduction, • EV is charged up to specified user settings.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	All available end-user's EVs are monitored and analysed	Visual analytics
2	Monitor each EV state of charge	Visual analytics
3	Monitor each EV current and history state (incl. energy measurements)	Visual analytics
4	Review EV charging stations occupancy status	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
5	Assess historical and upcoming charging reservation per station	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
6	Clusters of EVs owners are identified according to their charging preferences and consumption patterns	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
7	Day-ahead forecast for charging station occupancy	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
8	Proposal of variable pricing schema to EV charging owners	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
9	EV is charged up to specified user settings (e.g. charge is enabled when the tariff is low and/or charge is disabled when the tariff is high)	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 10.4

Involved Persona

Technology-aware consumer

Related User story

As a technology-aware consumer, **I want to** charge my EV at the lowest cost within flexibility, **so that** I manage my devices efficiently and optimize my consumption.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	The technology-aware consumer is made aware of the flexibility services and potential savings.
Postcondition	The technology-aware consumer is informed about the available flexibility services so he/she can manage the operation of his/her own assets efficiently.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The technology-aware consumer will be informed about the EV state in real-time	Visual analytics
2	The technology-aware consumer will be able to monitor the EV current and history state (incl. energy measurements)	Visual analytics
3	The technology-aware consumer is informed on the variable pricing schema and potential savings	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres
4	The technology-aware consumer evaluates the proposed solutions and decides whether to opt-in/out	Digital Twins for Electricity demand centres

5.5.6 Pilot 6

5.5.6.1 Use Case 11: AI for peer-to-peer renewable energy trading in virtual energy community

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 11.1

Involved Persona

Citizen prosumer (traditionalist & saver)

Related User story

As a traditionalist owner of a solar PV system for self-consumption, **I want to** optimize the system production, **so that** I achieve bigger financial savings or additional revenues for my households. I want to be able to validate costs and energy savings.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enough users (citizens/households) mobilized to join the virtual renewable energy community Users gave consent to access and utilize their private data Historical data available (weather data for at least 2 locations, consumption data for involved users from the DSO) Live data available, smart meters installed (consumption and PV production) Database operational
Postcondition	<p>Reports on possible financial and energy savings (household and community level). Exploring P2P energy trading and/or trading within the virtual renewable energy community based on the services outputs.</p>

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Mobilisation of pilot users and setting up the virtual renewable energy community	
2	Interviewing the users and defining clusters	
3	Identifying available data sources and integrating with the database (data collection platform)	
4	Disaggregation of household loads based on available data	Disaggregation service
5	Aggregation of results is performed according to user clusters	Disaggregation service
6	Forecasting of cluster or community demand based on available data from individual users (households)	Forecast of energy load / consumption / demand
7	Forecasting of cluster or community flexibility based on available data from individual users (households)	Flexibility forecasting
8	For each cluster, an optimal schedule is identified to maximise self-consumption	EMS optimisation service
9	Reports on possible financial and energy savings (household and community level)	
10	Validating results	
11	Creating reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 11.2

Involved Persona

Citizen prosumer (eco-conscious)

Related User story

As an eco-conscious owner of a solar PV system for self-consumption, **I want to** support distributed renewable energy production. I want to promote green and sustainable solutions (share my experience) e.g. through participation in a renewable energy community.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enough users (citizens/households) mobilized to join the virtual renewable energy community • Users gave consent to access and utilize their private data • Historical data available (weather data for at least 2 locations, consumption data for involved users from the DSO) • Live data available, smart meters installed (consumption and PV production) • Database operational
Postcondition	<p>Reports on mechanisms for participation in the energy market as part of the virtual energy community. Exploring P2P energy trading and/or trading within the virtual renewable energy community based on the services outputs.</p>

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Mobilisation of pilot users and setting up the virtual renewable energy community	
2	Interviewing the users and defining clusters	
3	Identifying available data sources and integrating with the database (data collection platform)	
4	Disaggregation of household loads based on available data	Disaggregation service
5	Aggregation of results is performed according to user clusters	Disaggregation service
6	Forecasting of cluster or community demand based on available data from individual users (households)	Forecast of energy load / consumption / demand
7	Forecasting of cluster or community flexibility based on available data from individual users (households)	Flexibility forecasting
8	For each cluster, an optimal schedule is identified to maximise self-consumption	EMS optimisation service
9	Reports on mechanisms for participation in the energy market as part of the virtual energy community	
10	Validating results	
11	Creating reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 11.3

Involved Persona

Public building (eco-conscious local authorities)

Related User story

As an eco-conscious local authorities and owner of a public building with roof-top solar PV, **I want to** have access to reliable information and validation of cost and energy savings, **so that** I can better plan for future costs and investments.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enough users mobilized to join the virtual renewable energy community • Users gave consent to access and utilize their private data • Historical data available (weather data for at least 2 locations, consumption data for involved users from the DSO) • Live data available, smart meters installed (consumption and PV production) • Database operational
Postcondition	<p>Reports on possible financial and energy savings (for the public building). Exploring P2P energy trading and/or trading within the virtual renewable energy community based on the services outputs.</p>

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Mobilisation of pilot users and setting up the virtual renewable energy community	
2	Interviewing the users and defining clusters	
3	Identifying available data sources and integrating with the database (data collection platform)	
4	Forecasting of cluster or community demand based on available data from individual users (public buildings)	Forecast of energy load / consumption / demand
5	Forecasting of cluster or community flexibility based on available data from individual users (public buildings)	Flexibility forecasting
6	For each cluster, an optimal schedule is identified to maximise self-consumption	EMS optimisation service
7	Reports on possible financial and energy savings	
8	Validating results	
9	Creating reports	

5.5.7 Pilot 7

5.5.7.1 Use Case 12: AI for the Ambient Assisted Living and personal safety/security at home

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 12.1

Involved Persona

Informed Facility Manager

Related User story

As an Informed facility manager working for a retirement home, **I want to** lower the costs of living in the retirement home by participating in DR programs with non-energy services, **so that** I can improve the well-being of the elderly by improving their daily/weekly schedules.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Number of the citizen involved is high enough • Consent on using data • Citizen are grouped according to their preferences • SM are installed and available
Postcondition	Creation of optimized schedules for Elderly.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Informed Facility manager identifies the citizen that will participate in the program	
2	From the installed AMI, the data is collected, and disaggregation of loads is performed	Disaggregation service
3	Aggregation of results is performed according to informed facility manager clustering of citizens	Disaggregation service
4	For each type of citizen, the new optimal schedule is identified.	EMS optimization service
5	The facility manager validates the results and, if needed provides additional parameters	
6	Informed facility manager activates the new schedules	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 12.2

Involved Persona

Sustainability supporting Facility Manager

Related User story

As a Sustainability supporting facility manager working for a retirement home, I want to improve the self-consumption from renewable resources, so that I can decrease the running costs and create a greener image of the retirement home.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SM are installed and available • Accessibility of current running costs of the facility • PV instaled on the roof of the building • Knowledge on the possible renewable energy efficiency • Awareness of the amount of produced energy
Postcondition	Decreased the running costs.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Sustainability supporting Facility manager identifies the self-consumption of the renewable resource of the facility.	
2	The data is collected from the installed AMI, and disaggregation of loads is performed.	Disaggregation service
3	Aggregation of results is performed according to the sustainability supported facility manager clustering of citizens.	Disaggregation service
4	For each type of citizen, the new optimal schedule is identified to maximise self-consumption.	EMS optimisation service
5	The sustainability supporting facility manager validates the results.	
6	Sustainability supported facility manager review if running costs were reduced, otherwise suggesting the corrections.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 12.3

Involved Persona

Cost-conscious Facility Manager

Related User story

As a Cost-conscious facility manager working for a retirement home, **I want to** improve the running cost by increasing self-consumption and better utilising the care facilities, **so that** I can decrease the running costs by optimising schedules for care facilities and employees using them.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions

- Awareness of running costs
- Awareness on self-consumption
- Available consumption data for a better understanding of how to increase self-consumption
- Available citizens schedules

Postcondition

Decreasing the running costs by optimising schedules.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Cost-conscious Facility manager identifies the current running costs.	
2	Having the whole picture of citizens schedules.	
3	Analysing current schedules and consumption of the Home for the elderly.	User profiling (or DT of citizen)
4	For each type of citizen, the new optimal schedule is identified.	EMS optimisation service
5	The cost-conscious facility manager validates the results.	
6	Cost-conscious facility manager activates the new schedules.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 12.4

Involved Persona

Profit-oriented Marketplace operator

Related User story

As a Profit-oriented Marketplace operator, **I want** to extend the P2P energy trading platform also to non-energy related services, **so that** I can get new users to the platform and improve the competitiveness of the business.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of users involved is high enough • Citizen are grouped according to their preferences • SM are installed and available
Postcondition	Extending and improving the P2P energy trading platform.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Profit-oriented marketplace operator identifies the non-energy related services.	
2	Profit-oriented marketplace operator includes non-energy related services on the platform.	
3	Offer users to participate in flexibility schemes with dynamic load management based on energy and non-energy related services.	Disaggregation service
4	Optimise the non-energy services for personal safety/security and AAL based on the deployed sensor infrastructure and aggregated data from the facility manager.	EMS optimisation service
5	Reporting the derogation of consumption or other potential hazards to the user in the form of an alarm.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 12.5

Involved Persona

Profit-oriented Marketplace operator

Related User story

As a Profit-oriented Marketplace operator, **I want to** extend the P2P energy trading platform also by connecting fingerprinting assets on the platform, **so that** I can get an average profile of the assets for a more accurate prediction of consumption and production.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility to connect the fingerprinting assets on the platform • SM are installed and available • Available data of consumption and production of the assets • The number of users involved is high enough
Postcondition	Getting more accurate prediction of user's single asset consumption and production.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Profit-oriented marketplace operator identifies the assets for fingerprinting.	
2	The assets need to be disaggregated to get the average consumption profiles.	Disaggregation service
3	Calculating the predictions of consumption and production.	EMS service
4	Validation and optimisation of predicting consumption/production data and actual data.	EMS optimisation service
5	Recalculation of the predictions.	EMS optimisation service

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 12.6

Involved Persona

Informed Citizens

Related User story

As an Informed citizen living in a retirement home, **I want to** become aware of comfort improvement opportunities, **so that** I can improve my well-being with an optimized schedule.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of the citizen involved is high enough • Consent on using data • Citizen are grouped according to their preferences • SM is installed and available • Determination of the comfort level boundaries
Postcondition	Creation of optimized schedules.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Informed citizen log in the platform.	
2	The citizen provides data on comfort level to the facility manager.	
3	Calculation of the schedules is executed.	
4	The citizen receives the optimised schedule	Optimisation of the flexibility; Consumer Digital Twin

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 12.7

Involved Persona

Informed Citizens

Related User story

As an Informed citizen living in a retirement home, **I want to** participate in DR programs, **so that** I can improve the well-being of the community.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of the citizen involved is high enough • Consent on using data • SM are installed and available • Determination of the comfort level boundaries • Participating in DR programs
Postcondition	Improving the well-being of the community.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Informed citizen identifies the needs and requirements.	
2	Citizen allows managing his/her assets with SM.	
3	Citizen's assets are being monitored and controlled to improve the community's well-being.	EMS service

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 12.8

Involved Persona

Careless Citizens

Related User story

As a Careless citizen living at a retirement home, **I want to** participate only in the DR programs without sacrificing comfort, **so that** I can reduce the costs of living in the retirement home.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of the citizen involved is high enough • Consent on using data • SM are installed and available • Participating in DR programs
Postcondition	Reducing the costs of living.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Careless citizen determines the boundaries of his/her comfort.	
2	Citizen allows managing his/her assets with SM inside the comfort boundaries.	
3	Citizen's assets are being monitored and controlled to reduce the costs of living.	EMS service

5.5.8 Pilot 8

5.5.8.1 Use Case 13: AI for energy efficiency investments de-risking

Usage Scenario ID:
Usage Scenario 13.1.

Involved Persona
Ambitious head of department

Related User story
As an ambitious head of department working for a government, **I want to** know how to manage energy consumption in buildings effectively, **so that** I have a cost assessment and reliable information in the context of each building.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Existing monitoring devices to measure the most significant parameter ■ Energy savings have been estimated
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan	
2	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
3	Definition of the reporting period	
4	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	
5	The platform shows a map where this building and neighbouring buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting: -their estimated energy performance certificate level OR -shows the available energy performance certificates.	Ensure correct measured/estimated calculation/predictions on savings on energy and financial savings.
6	The head of the department is able to select neighbouring buildings to display their main characteristics [year of construction, total surface, cadastral reference, energy demand, energy consumption]	
7		

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.2.

Involved Persona

Ambitious head of department

Related User story

As an ambitious head of department working for a government, **I want to** know which buildings would need to make priority investments in energy efficiency, **so that** I have a cost assessment and reliable information in the context of each building.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Conservation Measures (ECMs) that are going to be deployed on a building ■ Existing monitoring devices to measure the most significant parameter of the ECM to be implemented ■ Energy savings have been estimated
Postcondition	■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	The user defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan before ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation, every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device and energy price)	Ensure correct measured/estimated calculation/predictions on savings on energy and financial savings.
8	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	
9	The platform shows a map where this building and neighbouring buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting: -their estimated energy performance certificate level OR -shows the available energy performance certificates.	
10	The head of the department is able to select neighbouring buildings to display their main characteristics [year of construction, total surface, cadastral reference, energy demand, energy consumption]	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.3.

Involved Persona

Ambitious head of department

Related User story

As an ambitious head of the department working for a local municipality, **I want to** know which buildings would need to make priority investments in energy efficiency, **so that** I know which is the best refurbishment solution for each building.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy conservation measures (ECMs) that are going to be deployed on a building ■ Existing monitoring devices to measure the most significant parameter of the ECM are going to be installed ■ Energy savings have been estimated
Postcondition	■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	The user defines the ECMs are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan – before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, and energy price)	Ensure correct measured/estimated calculation/predictions on savings on energy and financial savings.
	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	
	The platform shows a map where this building and neighbouring buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting: -their estimated energy performance certificate level OR -shows the available energy performance certificates.	
	The head of the department is able to select neighbouring buildings to display their main characteristics [year of construction, total surface, cadastral reference, energy demand, energy consumption]	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.4

Involved Persona

Project Manager

Related User story

As a project manager working for a government institution, **I want to** know how to manage energy consumption in buildings effectively, **so that** I can translate these energy savings into economic ones and establish the investment terms and their recovery.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Energy Conservation Measures (ECMs) that are going to be deployed on a building ■ Existing monitoring devices to measure the most significant parameter of the ECM to be installed ■ Energy savings have been estimated
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	User defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device and energy price)	Open-source tool that queries the database and cluster buildings performance indicators based on features selected by the user.
8	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.5.

Involved Persona

Project Manager

Related User story

As a project manager working for a local municipality, **I want to** spend time as little as possible managing energy consumption in buildings, **so that** I focus on different responsibilities. Energy efficiency is important, but sometimes it just takes too much time

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Energy conservation measures (ECMs) that are going to be deployed on a building ■ Energy savings have been estimated
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Report on energy savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan	
2	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
3	Definition of the reporting period	
4	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	
5	The platform shows a map where this building and neighbouring buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting: -their estimated energy performance certificate level OR -shows the available energy performance certificates.	An open-source tool that queries the database and cluster buildings performance indicators based on features selected by the user.
6	The head of the department is able to select neighbouring buildings to display their main characteristics [year of construction, total surface, cadastral reference, energy demand, energy consumption]	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.6

Involved Persona

Project Manager

Related User story

As a project manager working for a local municipality, **I want** energy consumption data to be recorded on a regular basis, **so that** I can be sure that the results set out in the project have been achieved without financial corrections.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Existing monitoring devices to measure the most significant parameter ■ Energy savings have been estimated
Postcondition	■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan	An open-source tool that queries the database and cluster buildings performance indicators based on features selected by the user.
2	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
3	Definition of the reporting period	
4	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.7.

Involved Persona

Responsible facility manager

Related User story

As a facility manager managing the governmental building, **I want to** be sure which investments in energy efficiency will be the most efficient or most needed, **so that** I know which is the best refurbishment solution for each building.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are available OR estimated energy performance is calculated ■ EPCs are available ■ Energy Performance Estimations are available
Postcondition	■ Indicative information on the energy performance of the building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	The user defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, and energy price)	Provide estimations for the energy demand and consumption and another indicator to be determined.
8	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.8.

Involved Persona

Responsible facility manager

Related User story

As a facility manager managing private business buildings, **I want to** be sure which investments in energy efficiency will be the most efficient or most needed, **so that** I can translate these energy savings into economic ones and establish the investment terms and their recovery.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are available OR estimated energy performance is calculated ■ EPCs are available ■ Energy Performance Estimations are available
Postcondition	■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	The user defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, and energy price)	Provide estimations for the energy demand and consumption and another indicator to be determined.
8	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.9.

Involved Persona

Responsible facility manager

Related User story

As a facility manager managing local school premises, **I want to** be sure which investments in energy efficiency will be the most efficient or most needed, **so that** I know with predictions what will be the energy savings in the future.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are available OR estimated energy performance is calculated ■ EPCs are available ■ Energy Performance Estimations are available
Postcondition	■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
	1. Model Creation	
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	The user defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
	2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)	
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, and energy price)	Provide estimations for the energy demand and consumption and another indicator to be determined.
8	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.10.

Involved Persona

Careless manager

Related User story

As a facility manager managing the governmental building, **I want to** make decisions quickly, without spending too much time analyzing the information, **so that** I know which is the best refurbishment solution for each building.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Existing monitoring devices to measure the most significant parameter of the ECM or they are going to be installed (option A of the IPMVP) ■ Energy savings have been estimated
Postcondition	■ Indicative information on the energy performance of the building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	The user defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, and energy price)	Provide recommendations for building maintenance.
8	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.11.

Involved Persona

Careless manager

Related User story

As a facility manager managing the governmental building, **I want to** make decisions quickly, without spending much time analyzing the information, **so that** I can know with predictions what will be the energy savings.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Existing monitoring devices to measure the most significant parameter of the ECM or they are going to be installed (option A of the IPMVP) ■ Energy savings have been estimated
Postcondition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Indicative information on the energy performance of the building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	The user defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, and energy price)	Provide recommendations for building maintenance.
8	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.12.

Involved Persona

Careless manager

Related User story

As a facility manager managing the governmental building, **I want to** make decisions quickly, without spending too much time on analyzing the information, **so that** I can translate these energy savings into economic ones and establish the investment terms and their recovery.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Existing monitoring devices to measure the most significant parameter of the ECM or they are going to be installed (option A of the IPMVP) ■ Energy savings have been estimated
Postcondition	■ Indicative information on the energy performance of the building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	The user defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, and energy price)	Provide recommendations for building maintenance.
8	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.13.

Involved Persona

Informed policy maker

Related User story

As a policy maker working for a government institution, **I want to** have a sufficient understanding or supporting information of the energy efficiency situation in the state or local government, **so that** I can translate these energy savings into economic ones and establish the investment terms and their recovery.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are available OR estimated energy performance is calculated ■ EPCs are available ■ Energy Performance Estimations are available
Postcondition	■ Indicative information on the energy performance of the building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The policy maker enters the platform and introduces the name of the neighbourhood OR the city he is interested to verify.	Help national authorities or governing bodies to assess policy measures. Support policy-makers, regarding climate change initiatives and action plans.
2	The platform shows a map where the neighbourhood OR the city buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting the available energy performance certificates according to their label.	
3	The policy maker is able to consult the pre-calculated energy performance map.	
4	The policy maker establishes a comparison filter to detect which certificates fall out of range (for instance, those differing more than one letter in the label of a specific value, or other types of filters).	
5	The platform shows a map and a list of the certificates where these deviations are produced (buildings where this occurs are highlighted).	
6	Report generation of selected certificates.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.14.

Involved Persona

Informed policy maker

Related User story

As a policy maker working for a government institution, **I want to** have a sufficient understanding or supporting information on the energy efficiency situation in the state or local government, **so that** I know which building is the priority for investments.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are available OR estimated energy performance is calculated ■ EPCs are available ■ Energy Performance Estimations are available
Postcondition	■ Indicative information on the energy performance of the building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The policy maker enters the platform and introduces the name of the neighbourhood OR the city he is interested to verify.	Help national authorities or governing bodies to assess policy measures. Support policy-makers, regarding climate change initiatives and action plans.
2	The platform shows a map where the neighbourhood OR the city buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting the available energy performance certificates according to their label.	
3	The policy maker is able to consult the pre-calculated energy performance map.	
4	The policy maker establishes a comparison filter to detect which certificates fall out of range (for instance, those differing more than one letter in the label of a specific value, or other types of filters).	
5	The platform shows a map and a list of the certificates where these deviations are produced (buildings where this occurs are highlighted).	
6	Report generation of selected certificates.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.15.

Involved Persona

Informed policy maker

Related User story

As a policy maker working for a government institution, **I want to** have a sufficient understanding or supporting information of the energy efficiency situation in the state or local government, **so that** I know with predictions what will be the energy savings.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are available OR estimated energy performance is calculated ■ EPCs are available ■ Energy Performance Estimations are available
Postcondition	■ Indicative information on the energy performance of the building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	The policy maker enters the platform and introduces the name of the neighbourhood OR the city he is interested to verify.	Help national authorities or governing bodies to assess policy measures. Support policy-makers, regarding climate change initiatives and action plans.
2	The platform shows a map where the neighbourhood OR the city buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting the available energy performance certificates according to their label.	
3	The policy maker is able to consult the pre-calculated energy performance map.	
4	The policy maker establishes a comparison filter to detect which certificates fall out of range (for instance, those differing more than one letter in the label of a specific value, or other types of filters).	
5	The platform shows a map and a list of the certificates where these deviations are produced (buildings where this occurs are highlighted).	
6	Report generation of selected certificates.	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.16.

Involved Persona

Director of Finance

Related User story

As a director of finance overseeing the ongoing project, **I want to** be sure which investments in energy efficiency will be the most efficient or most needed, **so that** I know which is the best refurbishment solution for each building.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are available OR estimated energy performance is calculated ■ EPCs are available ■ Energy Performance Estimations are available
Postcondition	■ Indicative information on energy performance of building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	User defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	User provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, and energy price)	Double-check the planned investment payback. Validate EPC.
8	Generation of the energy and money saving reports	
9	The platform shows a map where this building and neighbouring buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting: -their estimated energy performance certificate level OR -shows the available energy performance certificates.	
10	The head of the department is able to select neighbouring buildings to display their main characteristics [year of construction, total surface, cadastral reference, energy demand, energy consumption]	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.17.

Involved Persona

Director of Finance

Related User story

As a director of finance managing the accounting and economic aspects of a company, **I want to** be sure which investments in energy efficiency will be the most efficient or most needed, **so that** I can translate these energy savings into economic ones and establish the investment terms and their recovery.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are available OR estimated energy performance is calculated ■ EPCs are available ■ Energy Performance Estimations are available
Postcondition	■ Indicative information on the energy performance of the building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	User defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, and energy price)	Double-check the planned investment payback. Validate EPC.
8	Generation of the energy and money saving reports	
9	The platform shows a map where this building and neighbouring buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting: -their estimated energy performance certificate level OR -shows the available energy performance certificates.	
10	The head of the department is able to select neighbouring buildings to display their main characteristics [year of construction, total surface, cadastral reference, energy demand, energy consumption]	

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 13.18.

Involved Persona

Director of Finance

Related User story

As a director of finance managing the accounting and economic aspects of a company, **I want to** be sure which investments in energy efficiency will be the most efficient or most needed, **so that** I know with predictions what will be the energy savings in the future.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Environmental conditions: ■ Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are available OR estimated energy performance is calculated ■ EPCs are available ■ Energy Performance Estimations are available
Postcondition	■ Indicative information on the energy performance of the building and neighbouring buildings ■ Report on energy savings ■ Report on money savings

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1. Model Creation		
1	Creation of a new IPMVP	
2	The user defines the ECMs that are going to be installed	
3	Definition of the most significant parameter and its monitoring plan - before the ECM installation	
4	Estimation of the rest of the parameters	
5	Calculation/estimation of energy consumption, before the installation of the ECM	
6	Definition of the reporting period	
2. Assessment and Reporting (iterative)		
7	The user provides data of the most significant parameter of the ECM after renovation every time defined on the reporting period (measurements of the monitoring device, energy price)	Double-check the planned investment payback. Validate EPC.
8	Generation of the energy and money-saving reports	
9	The platform shows a map where this building and neighbouring buildings are displayed with a colour code depicting: -their estimated energy performance certificate level OR -shows the available energy performance certificates.	
10	The head of the department is able to select neighbouring buildings to display their main characteristics [year of construction, total surface, cadastral reference, energy demand, energy consumption]	

5.5.10 Pilot 9

5.5.10.1 Use Case 14: AI for improved Energy Performance Certificates Reliability

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 14.1

Involved Persona

Policy makers in charge of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)

Related User story

As a Policy maker in charge of managing EPCs working in the Energy Performance Certification Official Register, **I want to** improve the quality of the EPCs, **so that** I will increase confidence in them.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions The number of EPCs is very high (approx. 50.000 EPCs) and the coherence (quality) of the result is not checked.

Postcondition The management of the EPCs is optimised and EPCs are checked in the reception, increasing their quality (and thus, confidence in them).

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collect all the information (EPCs) available	
2	The tool processes the EPCs and performs different verifications (to detect inconsistencies and errors or deviations)	Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement
3	The policy maker in charge of EPCs will obtain from the tool a selection of the Certificates which present inconsistencies.	Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 14.2

Involved Persona

Policy makers in charge of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)

Related User story

As a Policy maker in charge of managing EPCs working in the Energy Performance Certification Official Register, **I want to** obtain a quality checking tool, **so that** I will obtain a more efficient and automatic way to do the verification.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions The number of EPCs is very high (approx. 50.000 EPCs) and they are not verified.

Postcondition The EPCs are checked and verified in an easy way.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collect all the information (EPCs) available	
2	The tool processes the EPCs and performs different verifications (to detect inconsistencies and errors or deviations) in an automatic way.	Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement
3	EPCs are quality checked.	Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 14.3

Involved Persona

Policy makers in charge of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)

Related User story

As a Policy maker in charge of managing EPCs working in the Energy Performance Certification Official Register, **I want to** improve the EPC reception and management, **so that** I will save time and ease the data management work.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions The number of EPCs is very high (approx. 50.000 EPCs) and the management reception is not optimized, so EPCs are not well stored and work accumulates.

Postcondition The management of the EPCs is optimised and EPCs are better received and stored.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collect all the information (EPCs) available	
2	The tool receives and processes the EPCs in an automatic way	Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement
3	EPCs are stored in an orderly manner and can be easily consulted through the tool.	Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement
4	The policy maker in charge of EPCs is able to consult the EPCs and reception and management is optimised.	Energy Performance Certificate data reliability enhancement

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 14.4

Involved Persona

Policy makers in charge of energy retrofitting strategies

Related User story

As a Policy maker in charge of planning and designing the public strategies for the energy retrofitting of buildings, **I want to** obtain an energetic characterization of the stock of buildings, **so that** I will obtain a good vision of its current state.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Difficulties in extracting reliable information about the energetic state of the stock of buildings.
Postcondition	Creation of a tool that helps in the analysis of the current state of the stock of buildings and gives support in the diagnosis.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Extract the relevant information of the building stock through the processing of EPCs	
2	Carry out different analysis to make the diagnosis of the status of the EPCs (by different exploitation areas, age of buildings, if they have been refurbished, their energy systems...)	Energy Performance Certificate data

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 14.5

Involved Persona

Policy makers in charge of energy retrofitting strategies

Related User story

As a Policy maker in charge of planning and designing the public strategies for the energy retrofitting of buildings, **I want to** obtain a better vision of the need for energy improvements plans, **so that** I will obtain a reliable tool to help in the planning of the actions related to the improvement of energy performance in buildings.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Lack of knowledge on the improvements that may be done.
Postcondition	Creation of a tool that helps in the process of decision taking about measures to improve the energy performance of buildings and how to efficiently allocate funds for getting it.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Extract the relevant information of the building stock through the processing of EPCs	
2	Carry out different analysis to make the diagnosis of the status of the EPCs (by different areas, age of buildings, if they have been refurbished, their energy systems...)	Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation
3	Increased and accurate knowledge and information obtained from the building stock status, to be able to propose the most adequate measures in the refurbishment strategies.	Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 14.6

Involved Persona

Policy makers in charge of energy retrofitting strategies

Related User story

As a Policy maker in charge of planning and designing the public strategies for the energy retrofitting of buildings, **I want to** obtain a more effective allocation of funds for the energy rehabilitation of buildings, **so that** I will comply with the national /European energy efficiency commitments in buildings.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Need for a tool that helps in the retrofitting strategy and rehabilitation plans.
Postcondition	Creation of a tool that helps in the process of decision taking about measures to improve the energy performance of buildings and how to efficiently allocate funds for getting it.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Extract the relevant information of the building stock through the processing of EPCs	
2	Carry out different analysis to make the diagnosis of the status of the EPCs (by different areas, age of buildings, if they have been refurbished, their energy systems...)	Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation
3	Increased and accurate knowledge and information obtained from the building stock status, to be able to propose the most adequate measures in the refurbishment strategies.	Energy Performance Certificate data exploitation

5.5.10.2 Use Case 15: AI for predicting the climate change impact in RES and energy demand at regional (local) level

Usage Scenario ID

Usage Scenario 15.1

Involved Persona

FUNDACION ASTURIANA DE LA ENERGÍA

Related User story

As the Regional Energy Agency, work in the planning of renewable energy strategies at regional level, **I want to** know the potential of solar radiation in the different areas (taking into account climate change effects in renewable energy sources), **so that** I can better plan the exploitation of renewable energy resources in Asturias.

Usage Scenario conditions

Preconditions	Data from the meteorological stations of solar radiation. Common systems to calculate the performance of the solar installations. Difficulties in planning the exploitation of solar radiation according to the climate change effects.
Postcondition	A tool that models and predict the effects of Climate Change in solar radiation. Effective planning of solar radiation exploitation for the next years can be carried out based on that information.

Step by step analysis of Usage Scenario

Step	Action	Service
1	Collect the information from the meteorological stations.	
2	Data from solar radiation is mapped and georeferenced.	Solar radiation forecasting
3	The tool analyses the data and identifies variations in the solar radiation and other related parameters that may be assigned to the Climate Change	Solar radiation forecasting